

Towards DDoS Detection with Collaborative Approaches in the SDN Context.

Raja Majid Ali Ujjan

Supervised by Prof Zeeshan Pervez

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Abstract

Currently, Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks are considered the most rampant attacks in the modern network infrastructures. Software-Defined Networking (SDN) is also creating various solutions for the innovation and development of the Internet, also helps to defeat the DDoS attacks in existing networking infrastructure. The emergence of SDN has key advantages over legacy networking because SDN is capable to virtualise the central-control, also provides a feasible network security provisioning. Nevertheless, recent advances in SDN have also brought a contradictory relationship with DDoS attacks. On one hand, SDN capabilities such as software-based packets analysis, packet-sampling, global view, centralized control, updating of rules forwarding, and so on, provide effective solutions to detect and react to the DDoS attacks. However, on the other side, SDN's flexible architecture also manifests a large number of network vulnerabilities that need to be addressed before strengthening SDN security. Due to the preliminary stage of SDN, in the network, sampling-based measurement approaches currently results in low-accuracy, higher memory consumption, higher-overhead in processing and network, and low attack-detection. A few studies exist to collect and analyze truly representative characteristics of DDoS traffic. Current research mostly focuses on DDoS detection and mitigation module with predefined DDoS data-sets. Moreover, SDN also faces various structural vulnerabilities issues, such as single point failure vulnerability mainly at central controller unit (DDoS attacks over central controller), the deployment of standalone legacy IDS sensors cannot guarantee for safeguard against intruders. This thesis mainly focuses to improve the DDoS attack detection rate with the help of packet sampling, entropy estimation in the SDN context. This thesis is based on five contributions.

In our first contribution, we extensively surveyed the existing SDN literature, which is mainly focused on various SDN vulnerabilities and different DDoS security approaches, the proposed survey mainly depicts the advances of industries and various research communities. Most of the persistent attackers' challenges are extensively discussed to provide the safeguard for the network, which enables to design SDN based holistic security architecture. Based on the first SDN survey contribution, our second contribution utilizes the collaborative approach of signature-based

Snort IDSs with Deep Neural Networks (DNN) to capture higher detection in the SDN context. In the first stage of proposed work, a signature-based Snort IDS is implemented for malicious activity detection and traffic monitoring with traffic mirroring in Open vSwitch (OVS), then data is stored in a CSV log file of Barnyard 2. In the second stage, for effective attack detection in the test-bed, flow-based anomaly detection is deployed with DNN to improve the signature-based IDS limitation with a higher detection rate with low false-positive triggers. From the simulation results, our collaborative detection mechanism achieved more than 90% true positive rate with less than 5% of false alarms for all TCP, UDP, and ICMP attacks in general, demonstrating effective malicious traffic detection method as compared to conventional signature-based methodologies.

Our third contribution mainly focuses on the sFlow and adaptive polling-based sampling with Snort Intrusion Detection System (IDS) and deep learning-based model, which helps to lower down the various types of prevalent DDoS attacks inside the network. Firstly, in data-plane, to lower down processing and network overhead of switches, we deployed sFlow and adaptive polling-based sampling individually. Secondly, in control-plane, to optimize detection accuracy, we deployed Snort IDS collaboratively with Stacked Autoencoders (SAE) deep learning model. Furthermore, we quantitatively investigated trade off among attack detection accuracy and resources overhead. The evaluation of the proposed system demonstrates higher detection accuracy with 95% of True Positive rate with less than 4% of False Positive rate within sFlow based implementation compared to adaptive polling.

To deal with the heavy DDoS traffic flow inside SDN controller, our fourth contribution proposes a fast and an effective DDoS detection mechanism, in which we have deployed generalized entropy calculation by combining well-known Shannon entropy and Reyni entropy which enables to distribute most specific and representative characteristics of DDoS traffic to effectively deal heavy malicious traffic. Firstly, to lower down the network traffic overhead, we collect data-plane traffic with signature-based Snort detection, then we analyze collected traffic with entropy formula. Secondly, we improve the detection accuracy of the deep learning model by utilizing specific malicious distributed features. In this contribution, we quantitatively investigated detection accuracy between Stacked Auto Encoder (SAE) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) classifiers with the Ryu platform. SAE classifier achieved higher detection accuracy of 94% with only 6% of FP alerts, similarly, CNN classifier also achieved an average accuracy value of 93%. Moreover, both classifiers were performed with only 10 distributed features-based vector input.

In our final contribution, the proposed work mainly focuses to enhance the feasible detection performance, by utilizing the Collaborative Intrusion Detection Networks (CIDN) and blockchain applications to optimize the trust-based communica-

tion between each of IDS node in CIDN. This work converges the CIDN network and blockchain in the SDN context. In this contribution, we utilized several collaborated Snort IDS to receive the latest signature update from Ryu and then to securely share such signatures updates to all other Snort nodes within test-bed. Our work is motivated to detect seven types of common attacks with collaborated signature-based IDS, which feasibly processes more packets to achieve satisfactory detection results. Overall the evaluation results show that with the adoption of blockchain protocols, the proposed CIDN network achieves 96% of the TP rate detection rate for TCP, UDP, and ICMP packets.

Abbreviation	Full Form
ACC	Accuracy
AE	Autoencoder
AUC	Area Under the Curve
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service Attack
DoS	Denial of Service Attack
DL	Deep Learning
DNN	Deep Neural Network
F1	F1-measure
FP	False Positive
FPR	False Positive Rate
FN	False Negative
R	Recall
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
P	Precision
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
ML	Machine Learning
NN	Neural Network
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection System
SAE	Stacked Autoencoder
SDN	Software Defined Networking
SOM	Self-Organizing Map
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TP	True Positive
TPR	True Positive Rate
TN	True Negative

Declaration of Authorship

I, Raja Majid Ali Ujjan, hereby declares that thesis with the title of “Towards DDoS Detection with Collaborative Approaches in the SDN Context.” is entirely my original work. I have not utilised any authors sources other than those are mentioned in the bibliography. In addition to this, I have not submitted this research work in any other institution for any purpose. I am aware of the University of West of Scotland regulations and plagiarism concerns.

1. Whole work is carried out as major part of achieving a PhD research degree from this university.
2. Wherever I have mentioned the other authors published work has been clearly attributed.
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4. My proposed research also acknowledged with all significant sources.

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Contents

1	Introduction	17
1.1	Motivation	17
1.2	Challenges	20
1.3	Main purpose and Scope of the Thesis	20
1.4	Hypothesis and Research Questions	21
1.5	Limitations and Constraints	22
1.6	Main Contributions and Thesis Outline	23
1.7	Publications	23
2	Background and Overview	27
2.1	Intrusion Detection System	27
2.1.1	Definition	27
2.1.2	Brief History of IDS	28
2.1.3	Classification of IDS	28
2.1.3.1	Host based IDS (HIDS)	29
2.1.3.2	Network Based Intrusion Detection System	30
2.1.4	Intrusion Detection Method	32
2.1.4.1	Signature-based Detection	32
2.1.4.2	Packet-based Detection	33
2.1.4.3	Flow-based Detection	33
2.1.4.4	Anomaly-based Detection	33
2.2	Snort IDS	34
2.2.1	Elements of Snort	35
2.2.1.1	Packet Sniffer	35
2.2.1.2	Pre-processor	36
2.2.1.3	Detection engine	36
2.2.1.4	Snort Rule	36
2.2.1.5	Logging component	36
2.2.2	The Mechanics of Snort	37
2.2.2.1	Sniffing	37
2.2.2.2	Decoding packets	37

2.2.2.3	Processing Packets	37
2.2.2.4	Pre-processors	38
2.3	Software Defined Networking (SDN)	38
2.3.1	SDN Overview	38
2.3.2	SDN Protocols	39
2.3.2.1	OpenFlow Protocol	39
2.3.2.2	Open vSwitch Database Management (OVSDB) Pro- tocol	42
2.3.2.3	Network Configuration (NETCONF) Protocol	42
2.3.3	SDN Controller	43
2.3.4	Network Virtualization	44
2.3.5	Network Function Virtualization	45
2.3.6	Network Monitoring	45
2.3.7	Monitoring Data Generation	45
2.3.8	Data Collection and Storage	46
2.3.9	Processing	46
2.3.10	Transport	46
2.3.11	Orchestration	46
3	Software Defined Networks Security Survey	47
3.1	Introduction	47
3.2	Power of SDN to defeat the DDoS Attacks	50
3.2.1	Main Features of SDN to Defeat DDoS Attacks	50
3.3	Types of DDoS attacks and Classification in SDN Networks	51
3.3.1	Issues with DDoS Defence Mechanisms.	53
3.4	Security Analysis and Potential Attacks in SDN	54
3.4.1	SDN Common Attacks and Vulnerabilities	56
3.4.1.1	Unauthorised-Access	57
3.4.1.2	Data-Leakage	58
3.4.1.3	Data-Modification	58
3.4.1.4	Malicious Application types	59
3.4.1.5	Denial of Service	59
3.4.1.6	Configuration Issues	60
3.4.1.7	System Level SDN Security	60
3.5	Solutions of SDN Vulnerabilities	62
3.5.1	Unauthorized Access	62
3.5.2	Malicious Applications	65
3.5.3	Denial of Service (DoS)	66
3.5.4	Different Solutions to SDN Configuration Issues	68

3.5.4.1	Network errors detection	68
3.5.4.2	Verify real-time policies	70
3.5.4.3	Language-Based issues resolution	70
3.5.4.4	Unified network abstraction view	71
3.5.4.5	Formal verification approaches	72
3.5.5	Different Security Solutions to SDN system Level	73
3.6	SDN Framework to Optimize the Network Security.	74
3.6.1	Collect Detect and Protect	75
3.6.2	Traffic Analysis Attacks Detection and Prevention	78
3.6.3	Protection against DDoS/DoS Attacks	82
3.6.4	Machine Learning based DDoS protection	83
3.6.5	Anomaly/Entropy based DDoS protection	86
3.6.5.1	Maximum Entropy Detector	87
3.6.5.2	Rate-Limiting	89
3.6.5.3	NETAD	89
3.7	Discussion	92
3.8	Recommended Best Practices	93
3.8.1	Mutual Authentication:	93
3.8.2	Control Plane Slicing	94
3.8.3	Applications Containerization	94
3.8.3.1	Snort-IDS/Snort IPS based Logging and Forensics	95
3.9	Future Directions	95
3.9.1	SDN OpenFlow switches	95
3.9.2	SDN OpenFlow controller	96
3.9.3	SDN OpenFlow channel	96
3.9.4	Conclusion	97
4	DDoS Detection in SDN with Collaborative Techniques of Snort and Deep Neural Networks	98
4.1	Introduction	98
4.2	Background	100
4.3	Experiment Design	101
4.3.1	SDN Test-Bed	101
4.3.2	Network Data Acquisition	102
4.3.3	Deep Neural Network Network (DNN) Approach	105
4.3.4	Results	108
5	DDoS Detection with Sampling and Deep Learning in SDN	111
5.1	Introduction	111
5.2	Background Overview	114

5.2.1	Stacked AutoEncoder (SAE) in SDN	114
5.2.2	The sFlow Sampling Approach	116
5.2.3	Adaptive Polling Sampling Approach	117
5.3	Proposed Design	118
5.3.1	sFlow Collector (sFlow Sampling)	119
5.3.2	Snort-IDS (sFlow Sampling)	120
5.3.3	Flow-collector (Adaptive Polling Sampling)	121
5.3.4	Snort-IDS (Adaptive Polling Sampling)	122
5.3.5	CSV-storage (sFlow and adaptive polling Sampling)	123
5.4	Traffic Analysis	123
5.5	Evaluation	126
5.5.1	Experimental Setup	127
5.5.2	Results	130
5.5.3	System Performance Evaluation	133
5.6	Discussion	137
6	Entropy based Features Distribution for Anti-DDoS Model in SDN	139
6.1	Introduction	139
6.2	Background Overview	141
6.2.1	Snort-Ryu based data acquisition	141
6.2.2	Entropy Calculation	142
6.2.3	Feature Distribution and Traffic Processing	145
6.3	Experimental Setup	148
6.3.1	Performance Evaluation	150
6.4	Results	153
6.4.1	Selecting DDoS Classifier	154
6.4.2	Performance Evaluation with CPU Usage at Controller	158
7	Trust aware Blockchain based Collaborative Intrusion Detection in SDN	163
7.1	Introduction	163
7.2	Background	165
7.2.0.1	Collaborative intrusion detection (CIDN)	166
7.2.0.2	Blockchain based IDS	166
7.3	Design of Snort based CIDN Network with blockchain	168
7.4	Evaluation	170
7.4.1	Attack modelling	171
7.4.2	Evaluation with malicious and legitimate traffic in CIDN network	171
7.4.3	Evaluation with legitimate traffic in CIDN network	173

8 Conclusion and Future Directions	176
A Appendix Title	179
A.1 Datasets	179
A.2 Performance Evaluation Methods	180
A.3 Testbed Experiment	181
A.4 Snort Rules and Signatures for TCP, UDP and ICMP	182

List of Figures

1.1	Traditional Network Infrastructure vs SDN Network Infrastructure. . .	18
1.2	Overview of DDoS Detection Model with Sampling and Entropy Calculation in SDN.	21
2.1	Host Based Intrusion System Overview.	29
2.2	Network Intrusion Detection System Overview.	31
2.3	SNORT Architecture.	35
2.4	Software-Defined Network Architecture.	40
2.5	Northbound and Southbound Overview of SDN Controller.	43
2.6	Systematic Schema of SDN.	44
3.1	DDoS attacks Taxonomy based on TCP/IP Model.	52
3.2	SDN Attacks and Vulnerabilities with Different Layers	57
3.3	SDN Security Feedback Control: Collect - Detect - Protect	76
3.4	Recommended Best Practices in SDN	94
4.1	Network Topology.	102
4.2	SM1 Mode Malicious Detection / Data Acquisition.	104
4.3	SM2 Mode Normal and Malicious Data Acquisition.	105
4.4	Proposed Test-Bed of Snort IDS with DNN Co-Detection in SDN. . .	106
4.5	Simple Deep Neural Network Model.	107
4.6	ROC Curve for Binary Classification Model.	109
4.7	Binary Classifier confusion Matrix.	110
5.1	Data Acquisition with sFlow Sampling.	119
5.2	Data Acquisition with Adaptive Polling Interval Sampling.	122
5.3	Proposed System in SDN.	127
5.4	Flow diagram of proposed work.	128
5.5	Confusion Matrix of 2 Class Classification.	133
5.6	Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F-scores and FP-rate for two class model.	134
5.7	ROC Curve of 2 Class Classification.	134
5.8	CPU Utilization of Controller over time.	135

5.9	Controller Network Load over time.	137
6.1	Flowchart of features distribution in SDN-Ryu-controller.	147
6.2	Proposed system of features distribution in SDN-Ryu-controller.	149
6.3	Entropy variation with attack rates.	153
6.4	Entropy variation with attack rates.	154
6.5	SAE and CNN Confusion matrix with 30% Attack Traffic.	156
6.6	SAE and CNN Confusion matrix with 60% Attack Traffic.	157
6.7	Accuracy comparison between Normal and Entropy based features.	159
6.8	CPU utilisation after feature distribution with different attack rates.	160
6.9	CPU utilisation without feature distribution with different attack rates.	161
6.10	SAE and CNN False reports with 30% Attack Traffic.	162
6.11	SAE and CNN False reports with 60% Attack Traffic.	162
7.1	Proposed Test-Bed of Snort IDS with DNN Co-Detection in SDN.	168
7.2	Blockchain trust communication inside CIDN Snort nodes.	169
7.3	CIDN network different attacks TP-rate with different traffic intensity.	173
A.1	Overview of data collection with Ntop tool in SDN.	179
A.2	Overview of data analysis and collection with Wire shark.	180
A.3	Overview of data evaluation with (Training and Testing) in SDN.	181
A.4	Overview of testbed with feasible network application elements in SDN.	182
A.5	Overview of TCP, UDP and ICMP signatures with specific field values.	183
A.6	Overview of Extracted TCP, UDP and ICMP signatures	183

List of Tables

2.1	Summary of Existing SDN OpenFlow controllers.	42
3.1	Summary of SDN-OpenFlow Security Analysis	55
3.2	Security Issues associated with SDN Interface and Layers	56
3.3	Summary of Existing Solutions for SDN Security Issues	61
3.4	Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN Unauthorised Access Issues.	63
3.5	Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN Denial of Service Issues.	67
3.6	Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN Configuration Issues.	69
3.7	Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN System Level Issues.	74
3.8	Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for Collect, Detect, Protect in SDN Network	78
3.9	Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN Traffic Analysis Attacks Detection and Prevention.	79
3.10	Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for DDoS attacks in SDN	83
3.11	Summary of Proposed Machine Learning Solutions for DDoS attacks in SDN	84
3.12	Summary of Proposed Anomaly/Entropy based DDoS Solutions in SDN	88
4.1	Number of Records in all CSV files for normal and attacks data.	106
4.2	Different Learning Rate Accuracy of Model (Testing Phase).	109
4.3	Average computational time for training dataset and test dataset of model.	110
5.1	Existing literature survey for DDoS detection in SDN.	114
5.2	Six Major DDoS attack types in our test-bed	120
5.3	Snort Traffic acquiring modes with sFlow sampling.	121
5.4	Rules to adjust intervals for Polling sampling.	122
5.5	Snort Traffic Acquiring Modes with AP sampling.	123
5.6	Common List of Extracted Headers for TCP, UDP and ICMP packets.	125

5.7	Feature Extraction from TCP Flows.	125
5.8	Feature Extraction from UDP Flows.	126
5.9	Feature Extraction from ICMP Flows.	126
5.10	Representation of normal and attack records for training and testing.	130
5.11	Test-bed tools and technologies.	131
5.12	Proposed model configuration values.	132
5.13	Summary of two class model evaluation for sFlow and adaptive polling sampling.	133
5.14	Summary of total CPU utilization of controller.	136
5.15	Summary of total network load of controller.	136
6.1	Existing DDoS detection literature survey in SDN.	142
6.2	Two modes of Snort.	143
6.3	Selected Traffic Features with GE.	145
6.4	Different Threshold values according to attack rate.	151
6.5	Representation of normal and attack records for training and testing.	155
6.6	Proposed model configuration values.	155
6.7	Performance Metrics of Confusion Matrix for SAE and CNN Model. .	158
7.1	Seven Different Attack types.	170
7.2	Different attacks detection accuracy with blockchain based CIDN. . .	172
7.3	Different CPU and memory utilisation with blockchain based CIDN. .	174
7.4	Different packet-processing and packet-drops with blockchain based CIDN.	175

Chapter 1

Introduction

This Chapter:

Presents the precise introduction and the motivation of overall research presented. Some challenges of Software Defined Networking in context of Intrusion Detection are also discussed, in addition to this, some of the research questions are also critically discussed. Finally, we have depicted the major contributions of work along with the overall thesis organization.

1.1 Motivation

The modern development in computer technology and network communication industries is exponentially increasing in recent years. The Internet has become almost the only medium of source for communicating, sharing and exchanging information locally and globally. The Internet comprises wider information capability, high-speed data transmission, global coverage and a higher degree of interactivity. This is the fact that modern Internet services have dramatically influenced and changed the political, financial, economic, banking, military, cultural and cross-cultural technological development. Due to the rapid increment of Internet technology has also left behind serious vulnerable issues in computer networks, Internet vulnerability is also limiting the modern development in network systems as well. According to Neustar survey, 60% of Internet running companies were affected by DDoS attacks in 2013, and more than 80% of companies were under attack more than once [1]. Most common under attack sectors include gaming, media, and software group, often using DDoS flooding attacks as a political protest to gain media attention. In October 2016, most of Americas Internet was brought down by cyber-attacks by using Mirai botnet attacks and it was very largest in history. Mirai botnet was made up of Internet of Things (IoT) including digital, cameras, digital video recorder, (DVR) players. On 21st October, a very huge attack of about 1.2 Tbps suspended

Figure 1.1: Traditional Network Infrastructure vs SDN Network Infrastructure.

the many famous sites such as Twitter, The Guardian, Netflix, Reddit, CNN and many more throughout America and Europe. The research which is carried out on DDoS attacks and cloud-based security is a very early stage, most of the researchers are often carrying security research only at cloud rather than storing potential data at client local infrastructure [2]. The authors of [3] presented a survey on various types of intrusions in a cloud-based environment and in the proposed work mainly focuses flaws, weakness and security measures within different service layers.

To overcome these complex issues and network limitations, Software Defined Networking (SDN) plays a very feasible role, which is created by the network research community. In SDN networks, network centralised control unit is always decoupled from its data-plane or forwarding unit, addition to this both units can easily be reconfigured via programmable approaches [4]. The decoupling approach of separating the central logical unit from data forwarding devices and components enables SDN to provide more programmable and easily configurable features, in the result it provides unified network applications for the network developers, researchers, and programmers, also provides help to create and design new networks according to requirements. The detailed comparison of legacy network architecture and modern SDN based infrastructure is depicted in Figure 1.1

Recently, most common SDN deployment is directly concerned with OpenFlow, a robust and common communication protocol, which provides feasible access to switches or router's forwarding/data-plane [5], which help most of the researchers to configure the customized data flows using software applications, addition to this, also provides access to flow tables to manipulate and redirect traffic. However, OpenFlow has the capability to provide a safeguard for proprietary routing instructions, which are based on different hardware [6].

In larger cloud-based computing, security has been considered as the dominant barrier for the development of network applications [7]. The feasible design of SDN based features offers the innovative defence mechanism against various kind of DDoS attacks in cloud computing environment [8]. In cloud computing, availability is considered a major security requirement to provide on demanded services on various levels of cloud computing [7]. The Denial of Service (DoS) attacks and Distributed Denial of Service(DDoS) attacks are main flooding methods to make computing network resources unavailable [7]. DoS or DDoS floods can destroy any network machine and can remove the available services from its potential users. These types of DDoS attacks are mainly generated two or more than two attackers or bots [9], similarly, DoS attacks are launched by only two attackers or systems. A bot is a newly created device with the intruder's malware code. Although, DoS attacks are special kind of attacks derived as a subset of distributed DDoS floods. In our proposed research methodologies, we will utilise the term DDoS attacks which represent both DDoS and DoS attacks in SDN context.

Software-Defined Networking (SDN) has emerged as a great enabler to change the way of designing and building network architecture. Despite inserting security policies in the SDN environment, the SDN carries plenty of issues for its security perspective, and these issues create alarming situations which must be justified prior to building a feasible architecture. Some of these concerns are legacy network to network inherited environments and some come from SDN architecture itself [10]. Addition to this, most of the conventional IDS sensors are not capable to be deployed with SDN, despite SDN being highly flexible, and capable to build innovative network applications. On the other hand IDS, sensors are quite outdated so the classical IDS may be insufficient [11].

Moreover, SDN is capable to programme the entire switches and router infrastructure, also provide a feasible facility to analyse and compute the routing table rules set from distributed users into virtually spawned networking platform. Once network number of hosts and switches are increasing then SDN major controller also experiencing overhead bottleneck, such as authors of [12] carried out the experiment on SDN based datacentre with 2 million of virtual switches, in evaluation they depicted 20 million flows per second. Later [13] also presented some OpenFlow

attacks, such as the denial of service (DoS), man-in-the-middle attacks with disturbance of network services. Addition to this, authors in [6] also differentiated that SDN programmable features can be used either in good ways or miss-use.

1.2 Challenges

Generally, there are some potential challenges associated with flow-based intrusion detection system in the SDN platform, as below:

1. Generally, traffic of modern networks is dynamically increasing, which is diverse in nature and constantly changing. In addition to this, network attacks such as DDoS/DoS also keep evolving and aggressive with more modern and intelligent features. Due to the nature of dynamic traffic, most of attack detection models have been becoming more challenging.
2. Legacy NIDS models focus on larger number of hand-crafted modifications to optimise the accuracy of intrusion detection systems. However, due to the preliminary stage of SDN, it only provides a limited number of raw flow features. Therefore, it is becoming challenging to improve the detection accuracy in collaboration of intrusion detection systems and machine learning models.
3. Generally, NIDS models mainly focused on real-time attack detection and mitigation, therefore computational overhead and network complexities are also bringing more challenges to create appropriate detection models.
4. Intrusion detection approaches in collaboration to machine learning/deep learning have a significant impact on network data sets, the datasets are mainly used to train and test intrusion detection systems. Currently, the availability of properly labelled network datasets is challenging, as SDN platform is emerging as the very start of new technology, therefore, majority of datasets from SDN architecture are either unpublished or rarely available. Overall, intrusion detection models face issues to detect intrusions and to evaluate models as a supervised or unsupervised way.

1.3 Main purpose and Scope of the Thesis

The previous section of this thesis represents the motivational introduction of proposed work and some of the challenges associated with it. The major aim of this thesis is to classify the DDoS attacks by utilizing the network packet sampling and entropy calculation in collaboration with deep learning model of DDoS attacks detection under SDN context. Generally, our thesis falls into two categories, firstly,

Figure 1.2: Overview of DDoS Detection Model with Sampling and Entropy Calculation in SDN.

we utilize the SDN based packet sampling approaches with Snort IDS and deep machine learning to detect DDoS attacks. Secondly, we utilize the SDN based entropy calculation with Snort and deep machine learning to classify the DDoS attacks. Figure 1.2 represents the overall systematic overview of our proposed work. The more details of this work will be discussed in Chapter 5 and in Chapter 6.

The main purpose of this report is to provide a collaborative detection technique using the open-source intrusion detection sensor and Deep Neural Networks (DNN). The idea behind this technique is to manipulate the best security mechanism that best suit for known and unknown data-driven attacks rather than conventional pre-defined rules based on IDS detection. Our work aims to focus on higher capturing rate with very few false triggers. This work mainly focuses to present a pragmatic approach for detecting malicious attacks either small and large network platform with using cost-effective open source tools and methods in SDN context. Due to flexibility and openness interaction of SDN based model can be deployed in real-time architecture.

1.4 Hypothesis and Research Questions

The hypothesis is based on SDN flexible emerging technique which enables to deploy a powerful and effective collaborative detection of malicious tactics inside the network with the contribution of sampling approaches, entropy calculation, Snort

IDS, in data-plane, similarly DDoS detection with Deep Neural Networks (DNN) model in control-plane. We also utilised well-known vendor-neutral Application Programming Interface (API) for remotely modification and configuration of data-plane devices with faster and effective OpenFlow protocol. This open development with SDN could help to improve higher DDoS detection rate. Our overall research is based on the following research questions:

1. How to provide a feasible solution for detecting DDoS attacks with high capture rate in Software Defined Networks?
2. Does SDN architecture facilitate to capture and extract suitable flow-based packets for DDoS attack detection model ?
3. Can we improve the accuracy of DDoS attacks by optimizing the limited SDN features in collaboration of Snort IDS and deep learning model ?
4. How can we manipulate and resolve SDN unlabelled dataset issues by using the combined approach of Snort NIDS and deep learning model ?
5. Does SDN paradigm help to create an end to end DDoS detection model that effectively classify the DDoS attacks from the networks ?

1.5 Limitations and Constraints

In our proposed research area, we have some limitations constraints, given as below:

1. In this proposed research, we have acquired network datasets by adapting the conventional datasets in the SDN context. Following by major feature extraction of KDD-99 datasets, we collected real SDN based datasets. As KDD-99 datasets are widely used datasets in various network research, in addition to this, KDD-99 is also considered redundant datasets. We carefully analysed KDD-99 datasets to generalised our real SDN based datasets. Moreover, we have only utilised the most common and basic network features which have similar network features in flow-based and packets-based datasets. We assume that our datasets are interchangeable for both legacy networks and modern SDN based networks.
2. All the attacks in this research are concerned only application layer and network layer such as L2 and L3 on the OSI model. This research is not carried out on the physical layer L1 of the OSI model, which is a significant part of the network. Also, based on our data acquisition model and some limited nature of datasets, we have not performed our research by using all network topologies and our design and deployments.

1.6 Main Contributions and Thesis Outline

1.7 Publications

1. Elsevier Article-**Accepted** Impact Factor 5.66 2019
R. M. A. Ujjan, Z. Pervez, K. Dahal, A. K. Bashir, R. Mumtaz, and J. Gonzalez, Towards sow and adaptive polling sampling for deep learning based ddos detection in sdn,” Future Generation Computer Systems, 2019, issn: 0167-739X. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.10.015>. [Online]. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X19318333>.
2. IEEE Xplore-**Accepted** SKIMA, Maldives, Conference 2019
R. M. A. Ujjan, Z. Pervez, K. Dahal, Snort based Collaborative Intrusion Detection System using Blockchain in SDN, in: 2019 IEEE 13th International Conference on Software, Knowledge, Information Management and Applications (SKIMA) 2019.
3. IEEE Xplore-**Accepted** HPCC, Exeter, UK Conference 2018
R. M. A. Ujjan, Z. Pervez, K. Dahal, Suspicious traffic detection in sdn with collaborative techniques of snort and deep neural networks, in: 2018 IEEE 20th International Conference on High Performance Computing and Communications; IEEE 16th International Conference on Smart City; IEEE 4th International Conference on Data Science and Systems 26 (HPCC/SmartCity/DSS), 2018, pp. 915–920. doi:10.1109/HPCC/SmartCity/DSS.2018.00152
4. IEEE Access Journal -**Submitted** Impact Factor 4.09
2020
R. M. A. Ujjan, Z. Pervez, K. Dahal, W, A, Khan, A, M, Khattak, Entropy based feature distribution for Anti-DDoS model in SDN, IEEE Access Special Section Editorial in IEEE Access
5. Article-**Submitted**
R. M. A. Ujjan, Z. Pervez, K. Dahal, Software Defined Networks Security Survey.

The summary of overall contributions with implementation of each work is provided in the following flow diagram.

The PhD thesis represents the research which is carried out to create DDoS detection by utilising the NIDS and machine learning approaches in the SDN context. Major aim was to improve the DDoS detection rate with very little FP and FN rate, our research also relies on utilizing the minimum network, CPU, memory, and hardware/software resources.

Chapter 2 represents the preliminary background and related work. Firstly, it describes the summary of NIDS systems and also incorporates some of the more popular relevant terminology such as Snort IDS and its corresponding functionalities. Secondly, we discussed the core configuration of the SDN and SDN device, besides this, we have addressed the handling of data collection over SDN controllers. In the next chapter, we provided detailed literature surveys based on the background and preliminary elements, mainly focusing on DDoS detection approaches in the SDN context.

Chapter 3. Detailed literature overview about the SDN based DDoS and DoS detection methodologies are presented in this chapter. In the next chapter, we propose a basic SDN model as the first contribution, in collaboration with Snort IDS and Deep Neural Networks (DNN) to detect DDoS. This contribution fills the general research gap as mentioned in Chapter 3.

Chapter 4: presents the collaborative detection techniques of DDoS attacks in the SDN network. Firstly, signature-based Snort IDS is utilised for malicious activity detection and traffic monitoring with traffic mirroring in Open vSwitch. Secondly, Deep Neural Networks (DNN) based anomaly detection algorithm is utilised to optimise the attacks detection accuracy on collected data of the proposed model. In the next chapter, we provided another contribution with an improved version of Chapter 3. New improvement will be focusing on sFlow and adaptive polling-based sampling, which helps to reduce overhead and enhance the DDoS detection rate.

Chapter 5: pragmatically depicts sFlow and adaptive polling-based sampling with the Snort Intrusion Detection System (IDS) and deep learning-based model, which provides support to reduce the various types of prevalent DDoS attacks in the IoT network. We have utilised the decoupling property of SDN to program network devices to achieve the best results. Firstly, in data-plane, to lower down processing and network overhead of switches, we deployed sFlow and adaptive polling-based sampling individually. Secondly, in control-plane, to optimize detection accuracy, we deployed Snort IDS collaboratively with Stacked Autoencoders (SAE) deep learning model. In the next chapter, the main objective was accomplished with features distribution with the help of entropy calculation by combining well-known Shannon entropy and Reyni entropy. The major aim was to lower down the calculation burden for DDoS detection models, which results in a fast and effective DDoS detection model. Both previous approaches were updated to achieve this goal.

Chapter 6: depicts a fast and an effective DDoS detection mechanism, in which we have deployed generalised entropy calculation by combining well-known Shannon entropy and Reyni entropy which enables to distribute most specific characteristics of DDoS traffic to deal heavy DDoS traffic. We collect data-plane traffic with signature-based Snort detection, then we analyse collected traffic with entropy formula. Secondly, we improve the detection accuracy of the deep learning model by utilising specific malicious distributed features. In the next chapter, a blockchain based trust aware model is utilized to provide trustworthy and effective communication between the various elements of DDoS detection model of the previous contribution.

Chapter 7: converges the blockchain and Collaborative intrusion Detection Networks (CIDN) networks in SDN, the main purpose of this proposed work is to classify and detect major seven types of common DDoS attacks in current networks with trust communication of blockchain protocols, where detection is more responsive and much secure via CIDN Snort agents implementation. The next chapter will conclude the aforementioned work also it will provide the hypothesis responses in nutshell. Chapter 8: concludes the aforementioned work, which comprises of our contributions, implementations and results evaluation in very precise form. In addition to this, we also concluded some of the future directions as results of this work.

Chapter 2

Background and Overview

This Chapter:

Firstly represents the overview of NIDS systems and some of the most common related terms such as Snort IDS and its related functionalities are also introduced. Secondly, we have introduced the basic architecture of the SDN and SDN controller, in addition to this, we also discussed the data collecting processing over SDN controllers.

2.1 Intrusion Detection System

2.1.1 Definition

An intrusion detection system (IDS) is a fundamental part of network security deployment. An IDS system monitor network traffic statistics against malicious probes and then enable network administrator for prevention measures. After the firewall, an IDS system has vital significance as the second secure gateway in the networks. In the current network security research, the IDS system is also considered in the research of the network security field. IDS are classified in various ways [14]. The network based (NIDS), host based (HIDS) [15], anomaly based IDS and misuse based IDS systems. Our research mainly utilizes the NIDS implementation as major data acquisition from the test-bed of SDN, the detail data acquisitions with NIDS is provided in chapter 3, 4, 5 6, 7.

Network Intrusion Detection System is always deployed within strategic locations in order to record entire traffic from all devices. Larger NIDS server can be implemented on a network backbone for huge network traffic flow, and smaller systems are to be deployed only specific locations such as switch, gateway, or router given in Figure 2.1 below. IDS system are capable to be placed in Local Area Network (LAN), De Militarized Zone (DMZ), and remotely connected Internet area.

Moreover, our proposed research is more likely based on NIDS architecture, and we have collected various types of research data from NIDS. Signature based IDS system are known as conventional IDS. It collects network traffic packet by packet then compare against predefined signature in the database in order to detect known malicious activities.

2.1.2 Brief History of IDS

The early concept of intrusion detection was initiated by Anderson J P in 1980. According to author intrusion detection is a threat which is caused by unauthorised access or operating system to make the system unavailable [16]. Anderson J P also proposed intrusion detection concept with the help of operating system records auditing. Many researchers did not focus attention on this idea of intrusion detection, but they focused on data encryption techniques and to make denial access to all unauthenticated computer hosts [16]. In 1985, Denning D E. also created an IDS model known as Intrusion Detection Expert System (IDES), this model comprises host, object, record, characteristics profile, anomalous data records and activity rules. This model is not dependant on platform, application, environment, system weakness and attack types. In 1988, Teresa L proposed an improved model of IDS to identify malicious threats from real time network data, he succeeded in receiving data. This model utilised to detect single host unusual activities [17]. In 1990, Heberlein L T also designed a network-based IDS model and delivered a new technique of Network Security Monitor (NSM). This technique used to identify anomalous tactics of the network. The main focus of data monitoring was to record only network data in local area network, local host data was not audited in this model. Since 1990, intrusion detection research gradually increased. Some of the American research centres carried research with a combination of host-based IDS and network based IDS. The collaborative model of HIDS and NIDS used only at distributed IDS architecture. The author in [18], proposed IDS model to catch intrusions with the help of immune principal. In [19], the method of network information retrieval technology proposed in the IDS systems to detect plenty of intrusions behaviours. The anomaly detection of user behaviour also studied in [20], a machine learning algorithm was utilised to catch user anomalies.

2.1.3 Classification of IDS

The intrusion detection system falls into two main categories such as host based IDS (Intrusion Detection System), and network based (Intrusion Detection System). Each category carries some advantages and disadvantages. Host based IDS examine data on various individual nodes of the network, on the other side network based

IDS monitors the packets which are transferred between network nodes [21].

2.1.3.1 Host based IDS (HIDS)

Host-based intrusion detection systems fall into four types, such as log monitors, integrity monitors, signature scanners, and anomaly detectors. The log monitors detect intrusions after parsing system event logs. [22]. In HIDS systems individuals IDSs are used as depicted in Figure 2.1 to collect and analyze the data from each of the hosts, these were developed and implemented in traditional systems for acquiring information from inside the single computers, such as auditing operating systems files. This enables IDS to analyze all activities sensibly and to determine which users and processes are comprised of the particular attack into the operating system. Similar to other intrusion detection systems, HIDSs also generate multiple false-positive alerts. When systems are correctly designed and adjusted then reduction in false-positive alerts could be achieved remarkably.

However, Comparatively, to NIDSs, HIDSs are only able to watch results of an attempted attack, In addition to this direct access and monitor processes and data file to the attacked system [23].

Figure 2.1: Host Based Intrusion System Overview.

Advantages

- The host-based IDSs can monitor only local events of a host. It can detect attacks that network-based IDSs cannot detect.

- These are more likely used in the environment, where encrypted traffic travels, as the source of information is always analysed before data encryption on the origin host and/or after the destination host data decryption.

Disadvantages

- Host-based IDSs are most costly. It takes much time to configure as host-based IDSs are installed individually on different local host nodes. A network administrator needs to manage and configure all nodes separately.
- These are least feasible for detecting attacks on the entire network (e.g. port scans), although these are supposed to analyse packets which are sent to it.
- Intruders can easily disable these services by flooding certain types of Denial of Services (DoS) attacks.
- HIDSs uses host resources for monitoring purpose, during monitoring time HIDSs influence the performance of the system as well [23].

2.1.3.2 Network Based Intrusion Detection System

The second class of intrusion detection system is comprised of network-based IDS (NIDS) shown in Figure 2.2. NIDS analyses the detection based on datagrams travelling over the entire network, or network section in which switch is installed. Network packets are analysed, sometimes these are compared with pre-stated rules and then their nature is checked with accuracy. Packet sniffing is the main technique for NIDS, this helps to grab data from inside special types of protocols packets, later on, these are matched with predefined packets structure.

Most intrusion detection systems are network-based, these IDSs detect attacks by capturing and analysing only network-level packets. NIDS can monitor multiple hosts connected to the network segment. NIDS are frequently used and easy to install because of their simple general configuration for the entire network segment. The network-based IDSs are implemented at various points of the network, these sensors monitor traffic from local sources then report attack events to the management console. Most of IDS sensors are installed in hidden mode so that attackers cannot identify the presence and location of these sensors.

Figure 2.2: Network Intrusion Detection System Overview.

Advantages of NIDS

- NIDSs can monitor the large network depending upon enough capacity for traffic analysis in total.
- NIDSs have a very low impact on the network, these can work in passive modes without inferring normal operations of the network.
- NIDSs can be configured invisibly in the networks to make the network more secure against intruders.

Disadvantages of NIDS

- NIDSs sensors always analyse packet headers and their contents as well, so it is very hard to process all network packets into a large network. They fail to detect attacks during high traffic flow.
- Network-based IDSs do not analyse the information with encryption. In network, encrypted communication is not examined in these sensors, and unable to assess whether the packet is malicious or not.
- Some time network-based IDSs do not know whether the attack was successful or not, it only knows the launching time of that attack. It means that when

NIDSs detect attack then the administrator must have to investigate all hosts manually to confirm the attack was successful or not.

- Sometime NIDSs face issues to deal with network-based attacks, which are travelling with fragmented packages, these packages make IDSs unsuccessful to find attack.
- As NIDSs are implemented with general configuration within the entire network, due to general configuration they generate plenty of false positive FP attacks. These can report normal traffic activities as an attack. This issue arises when a number of such alarms are very high.
- One of the most common drawbacks of NIDSs is their implementation of the stack for network protocols. Most of the servers and desktops systems do not follow the same TCP/IP standards for implementation.

Network-based systems are more effective and efficient as compared to host-based systems. However, NIDS can carry certain types of drawbacks, such as NIDS systems take much time to analyse certain packets with encrypted payloads, Unicode formatted packets, high-speed networks, and large network with switches [25]. Normally network IDSs are divided into two types, anomaly-based and signature-based. Most popular is the combination of both, which is known as hybrid NIDS.

2.1.4 Intrusion Detection Method

Intrusion detection methods are categorised into the following areas.

2.1.4.1 Signature-based Detection

The signature-based method detects network data which match the signature in the IDS rules library [21]. Each rule in IDS carries specific attributes and conditions against an attack. When the IDS system receives network traffic, then it utilises some stored rules to match the provided data, if matched rule found with data traffic then IDS has to decide either traffic contains intrusions or not. For this perspective, signature-based detection is similar to the anti-virus application.

The main advantage of the signature-based is its very simple and efficient process to analyse data by data. Signature-based IDS false positive rate of detection is very low. In contrast, this IDS technique is also useless for zero-day attacks, in which the predefined ruleset of the attack is not identified. The signature-based IDS are effective when the database of signature and rulesets is updated according to detection attributes and behaviour. Well written signature rulesets can detect the higher probability of known attacks, wrong attack identification is very less in

term of known attacks. Due to these characteristics, signature-based IDS are widely utilised in commercial uses [24].

2.1.4.2 Packet-based Detection

The packet-based detection methods use data sources from network traffic, it uses all packet payload for identifying attacks. Packet-based technique more likely uses signature-based detection engine, but this requires plenty of data attributes as features specific to the Intrusion Prevention System (IPS). However, Snort is very effective popular IDS sensor which is well known for its signature-based and packet-based detection engine. The packet-based detection provides good detection rate due to the fact of detecting targeted traffic which contains all various traffic information from the network. However, this detection method also requires powerful hardware devices to manipulate plenty of network traffic. For addressing this gap, NetFPGA [25] a hardware device which is used for processing heavy traffic flow of packet-based IDS [26].

2.1.4.3 Flow-based Detection

Flow-based detection is the main method to lower down the network overhead during IDS operation inside infrastructure. In flow-based, malicious behaviours are identified based on flows passing through different connections. When there is a larger traffic flow with a big time slot, then this technique reduces the flow of traffic into sub flows or consider it as a single flow. Due to this technique, a flow-based detection method require very less network and hardware resources as compared to packet-based detection. In the flow-based method, both router and network switch collect fundamental traffic flow information within a network, later it propagates information intervals to a specific server. This enables all switches and routers to be installed to the entire network system. The flow-based approach is also capable to catch intrusions inside or outside the network, due to this reason it is widely used in larger enterprises, universities, intra networks, and industrials level. In this approach, any flow comprises of source Internet Protocol (IP) address, destination IP, Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) flags, number of packets in each flow, bytes per flow, and time. This technique works similar to anomaly-based detection.

2.1.4.4 Anomaly-based Detection

Anomaly detection focuses on unusual behaviour identification either in host or network. They work assuming the attacks different from normal activities. Most of the anomaly detectors create profiles that represent normal behaviour for all users, hosts, or network connections. These profiles are created from hierarchical data,

which is collected from normal events. The detectors collect data from normal events after using a variety of measures it determines and monitors deviated activities comparing to normal events. The main techniques for catching anomalies in the system are given below:

- It detects threshold based on specific attributes of users behaviour, such behaviour attributes sometimes contain the number of files which are accessed by a different user in specific time slots, unsuccessful entries to system, amount of CPU used by various processes, and so on. This level is identified as static or heuristic.
- Statistic measures, it could be parametric, where it is assumed as distribution of attributes stored in profiles fits in a certain pattern, or non-parametric, where the distribution of profiled attributes learns from the historical values, which were observed over time.

Advantages

- The IDS based on anomaly detection normally detects unusual behaviour. They have the ability to detect unknown attacks without having specific knowledge.
- The anomaly detectors generate very useful information, which helps to define and create new signatures for attack detection.

Disadvantages

- The anomaly detection generates very high numbers of false alarms due to unpredictable users and networks behaviour.
- They require very complex and costly training for characterizing patterns of normal behaviour.

2.2 Snort IDS

Snort is a widely used and open source network intrusion detection system. It uses packets level monitoring and packets analysis approaches. These packets are used for matching signatures of attacks and protocol anomaly. Snort IDS has a potential signature matching feature and very rich user-friendly signatures system. The signature system can easily be updated and expanded, an overview of the Snort is provided in Figure 2.3. Snort has a broad community that make new rules (Snort refers to the signature as new rules) for improving its performance and also

recommends new suggestions for keeping Snort up-to-date. Snort can perform in the three following modes:

Sniffer mode – This mode reads the packets then displays them into consistent streamflow on the console.

Packets Log mode– This mode writes all packets to disk as a log file.

Network Intrusion Detection System mode – This mode best fits in either simple or large network topology, which enables Snort to analyse traffic for matching to the predefined attack signatures or to detect anomalies in the protocol. Snort architecture is based on a modular system, which consists of a packet decoder, pre-processor, detection engine, and several output plug-ins. Snort sensor uses only LIBPCAP packet sniffer to read the packets from network devices as it has not its own sniffer.

Figure 2.3: SNORT Architecture.

2.2.1 Elements of Snort

The major Snort sensor elements are provided as below:

2.2.1.1 Packet Sniffer

In Snort, a packet sniffer is a device which enables the administration to read network traffic. Sniffer basically allows reading secret data on network devices, as all traffic

is coming through Internet network devices. It listens to IP networks [27].

2.2.1.2 Pre-processor

It is kind of filter that uses some predefined properties then these are checked into other modules. A pre-processor picks raw packets and checks against the plug-ins, which further compare the behaviour of packets with plug-ins. A pre-processor normally takes 1000 of packets then process them for translation. Mostly packets are captured from raw network data to process for various pre-processors implemented by the network administrator, then pre-processor sends them for encoding plug-ins and finally to detection engine unit [27].

2.2.1.3 Detection engine

The detection engine of Snort is the main component. It creates attack signatures with the help of parsing snort rules. When the detection engine receives packets from pre-processor, then it matches to attack signatures, and signatures that matched are sent to output plug-ins. Detection engine analyses these packets with the help of pre-processed rules, when some rules in the database exist and it corresponds to attack, it shows that the Snort detection engine performs its task very well. Snort uses various output plug-ins such as CSV, XML, and Database [27].

2.2.1.4 Snort Rule

Snort rule is another important feature. Snort uses very simple descriptive language. Snort rules have two logical portions. Each rule is divided into the following two parts

1. The rule header, and rule options. The rule header is consist of rules' action (e.g. alert, log, and drop), protocol, source IP address, destination IP addresses with net mask, and source and destination ports numbers.
2. The rule option section comprises of alert messages and information which helps packets to be inspected (e.g payload, flags, and header).

2.2.1.5 Logging component

When the detection engine receives data based on rules if the match occurs then it triggers an alert warning. Later on, these warning messages can be transferred to log files, I/O network connection screens, UNIX sockets Windows pop-ups, and SQL databases [27].

2.2.2 The Mechanics of Snort

The main systematic mechanism of Snort is given as below:

2.2.2.1 Sniffing

Snort can capture plenty of network traffic data when the Network Interface Card (NIC) is set to promiscuous mode. Normally network card is set to default mode, which drops some selected data packets which are not listed in the MAC addresses list. Snort more likely works with a change in behaviour so that MAC addresses are not mandatory to be checked there. If the machine is implemented with Snort, all packets transferring to this machine network card will be unaware of MAC addresses and make these packets available for Data-Link-Layer. When packets reach Data-1997 Link-Layer after capturing process, then Snort utilises libpcap library for keeping packets inside packet decoder module. Libpcap library is an extension to TCPdump program [27]. During start-up, Snort uses inside call Snort.c to libpcap library which checks interfaces and enables promiscuous mode. Snort uses execution loop known as pcap.loop to initialise these interface and its' function. This loop works repeatedly to receive data from the network card, then it calls ProcessPacket() function with the help of decode.c routine links into Data-link layer [27].

2.2.2.2 Decoding packets

When data arrive from network interface card, then these are passed towards Snort decode engine via libpcap library, then second stage (operation loop) has been initiated. Snort decodes all raw packets on the second layer of the OSI model known as the Data-link layer. At this stage the processed packet() function utilises the DecodeEthPkt() function, which enables to decode each protocol information, for e.g TCP/IP protocol is examined then DecodeEthPkt() function calls the DecodeIP() function, at last DecodeTCP() function. Meanwhile processed TCP packets are sent to special data structures for detection purpose. Snort stores these types of data into pointers form in the memory [27].

2.2.2.3 Processing Packets

After getting network data and decoding these data packets into different protocols, then it is ready to send to pre-processors, which is level three in the Snort process. The main purpose of Snort pre-processors is to develop an intelligent framework that drop, alert, modify packets before reaching detection engine [27].

2.2.2.4 Pre-processors

Normalization – Processes packets into a standard format.

Fragmentation – It dissects all packets into pieces so that these can be easily fit into on network wire. Unfortunately, pattern-based IDS can easily be bypassed in fragmentation, fragrouter is a very famous hacking tool for doing this. Fragrouter does the fragmentation of the network traffic into small pieces then evades the pattern matching system.

2.3 Software Defined Networking (SDN)

IP networks are very difficult to manage, these devices comprise lots of issues like tightly coupled to each other, and proprietary based and uses legacy connecting terminals. However, IP based devices are only able to configure via hardware-based interfaces using Command Line Interface (CLI) and Application Programming Interface (APIs) and high-level programming languages. The feasible networking configurations are not achievable as it has not any unified reliable protocol. Secondly, network-planes are vertically linked. Addition to this control and data-planes are closely coupled within hardware-based devices. The device users have limited surrounds to work with vendor-specific policies and interfaces. Therefore, these devices cannot accept daunting logical and management policies. In very large scale data-centre, cost significantly rises for deploying high speed switches [28]. However, the main role of datacentres networking is to lower down the overall cost and to improve the performance. These issues inside networking infrastructures decrease the efficient performance and leaving it more complex for the new development [29].

2.3.1 SDN Overview

The term SDN refers to network control-plane separation from data-plane, in which control-plane has an ability to manage plenty of devices connected through it. The Software-Defined Networking is capable to create a state of the art architecture, which is easy to manage in the terms of cost and upgrading perspective, and it helps to build plenty of modern applications for high bandwidth traffic channel. The fact of keeping control-plane away from data-plane reduces programming complexities [30]. The SDN as an emerging platform provides scalability, security and new policies insertion flexibility in the network. The SDN network comprises mainly following four parts [31].

- Separating data-plane from control-plane.
- Ability to propagate flow-based traffic in the data-plane.

- The centralised control-plane holds instructions set for multiple forwarding planes, and it is the main Network Operating System (NOS) for SDN.
- SDN controller has the potential to program networking devices with the latest trends.

The control-plane in SDN infrastructure is always separated from its data-plane, and the flow of data-plane is manipulated by the instruction of flow table, where forwarding policies utilises flow based table. The implementation of SDN control-plane is done remotely, and its logic controls plenty of data-planes. The SDN also provides an abstracted and global view of the whole network, this abstraction feature is achievable via central controller logic. The SDN comprises very effective methodologies to control network configurations and operation remotely and enables network development solutions in a more suitable way. These SDN solutions fall into two main sections: (i) legacy network function, that is widely used with vertical integration with its supported devices (ii) modern services which were not feasible in legacy network infrastructures. Moreover, the SDN infrastructure due to its flexibility contains good control [32]. Figure 2.4, depicts the separation of the existing network into the control layer and the infrastructure layers, in which basic switches and routers hold the link status and does the forwarding job itself by flow table. These SDN devices have only link status which helps to transmit data and provide management functionalities for network applications and its controller, i.e. Network Address Translator (NAT) and load balancer associated with SDN controller. This main function of network isolation enables the administrator to alter whole network policies.

2.3.2 SDN Protocols

SDN has various protocols, which separate network planes. Each protocol carries various aspects from its architecture. There are several protocols exist in SDN with similar functioning attributes.

2.3.2.1 OpenFlow Protocol

The OpenFlow is widely used protocol in SDN. It provides a bridge between controller and data-plane in SDN context. Inside the switch, OpenFlow policies relatively work with x86 bit instruction set. As x86 bit based instructions programme a computer similarly, OpenFlow policies are inserted into network data-planes. The requirements of OpenFlow logical switch and protocol are extracted from specification details of OpenFlow switch. OpenFlow switch protocol manipulates communication between its controller and data-plane. In the SDN OpenFlow, data-plane

Figure 2.4: Software-Defined Network Architecture.

packets are treated as, when packets enter the OF switch then switch verify similar match in the routing table if the packet is matched with relevant information then switch triggers an action. If there is no match then OF switch initiate request for propagating proper action to the controller by sending packet reply to the controller. In the controller OF propagates packets to its applications. When an application's packet action is reached to the controller, then it initiates responsive action which enables OF switch to propagates data effectively.

Addition to this, OpenFlow has an ability to communicate with switches with its various information, like it has the ability to check port status, status in the flow table and looks up the table. This is the fact that plenty of networks using OpenFlow protocols for new network application adoption.

OpenFlow protocol comprises of major three components like OpenFlow-switch, OpenFlow-channel and OpenFlow-controller.

1. OpenFlow-switch. Switches associated with OpenFlow are mainly manipulated by OpenFlow-Controller via the secure channel of OpenFlow protocol. The switch is a combination of one or more flow tables that are mandatory to process packet forwarding and lookup rules. In general, a flow table is also known as rule-set of flow entries, which carry unique packet header fields, action set, and counter values. Header fields are mainly used to identify the packet matching by verifying VLAN ID, source IPs and destination IPs, ports

and so on. The counter is responsible to calculate and classify the total number of bytes for all processed packets. The actions are used for providing instructions for processing and matching packets flow, such as how to forward given port towards its destination controller and how to allow or drop that packets.

2. OpenFlow-channel. This is a key element for providing a communication interface between OpenFlow switches and OpenFlow controllers. Although, this interface enables the controller to manage and configure switches rules so that switch can easily receive the traffic packet or send these packets towards the destination. In this channel, three different varieties of messages can be sent, which are controller to switch-messages, asynchronous-messages and symmetric-messages. The controller to switches messages is mainly processed by the controller for the purpose of manipulating and analysing switch statistics. Moreover, Asynchronous messages are processed and sent by switches only for the purpose of updating the controller for network statistics and changes in switches. However, controller and switches, both are capable to process and initiate symmetric messages. These messages are easily initiated by either controller or switches without any solicitation involvement.
3. OpenFlow-controller. This is the main centralised unit, which is capable to maintain, to distribute, and to update the network devices instructions. It also provides support how to handle the packets without utilising any valid flows insertion entries, addition to this, it also supports the flow table of switches with the help of adding and removing flow policies via a secure interface. Moreover, the OpenFlow switch is also capable to create a connection between one or more controllers. In the multiple controller platform, the network has stable reliability, if one of the connected switches fails then this platform provides resiliency. However, switches start the connection with controller configuration once OpenFlow protocol is initiated. Once switch configuration is connected with the controller, then switch propagates only corresponding messages. Table 2.1, represents the summary of OpenFlow based controller.

Overall, OpenFlow enabled switch can include the multiple flow tables, each flow table also carries plenty of entries for flow management. In the flow table, every switch is responsible to analyse the flow entries and forwarding decisions for every incoming packet, switches identify the exact matching against each packet. Once the match is successful then flow entries instruction takes place, if the packet is identified with its defined table values then packets with the highest priority are selected. In contrast, if packets fail to match with flow entries inside the flow table then these packets are dropped or sent back to the controller for further actions.

Table 2.1: Summary of Existing SDN OpenFlow controllers.

Controller	Description	Code
Ryu	SDN component based framework, written in Python language.	Python
NOX	Primary, OpenFlow controller written in C++ language.	C++
SNAC	OpenFlow based controller, written in C++, provides a graphical interface.	C++
RouteFlow	Provides support for virtual IPs especially for hardware-based routing.	C++
Maestro	OpenFlow based controller provides support for scalable routing platform.	Java
Beacon	An OpenFlow based controller, used for the event-based and thread based operation.	Java/ Cross-p
Floodlight	Industrail level routing controller based on Apache licensed and OpenFlow.	Java
IRIS	A recursive SDN controller with OpenFlow protocols.	Golang
Jaxon	SDN based controller works in collaboration with NOX controller.	Java
POX	SDN networking controller based on OpenFlow or OVSDB protocol.	Python

OpenFlow version 1.1 provides feasible support for pipeline processing and multiple flow tables. Pipeline processing is capable to forward packets toward the specific tables for further flow processing. Whenever matching entries can not identify the next table flow, then table pipeline processing is normally stopped in the table, this stage enables packet modification forwarding rules. Currently, there are various OpenFlow version has been used and discussed ranges version 1.1.

2.3.2.2 Open vSwitch Database Management (OVSDB) Protocol

Open vSwitch is a virtual switch consisting of multi layers, it is widely used for virtual test-beds. As OVSDB is management protocol to address the core functions of management planes of switches. This protocol can be deployed either in switch or controller and provides a bridge for managing activities inside the switch. The OVSDB more likely uses JSON APIs to encode protocol messages. Moreover, OVSDB protocol is not limited to be used in a virtual environment but it has capabilities to be implemented HP, Pica8 fabrication OVSDB and OF-CONFIG are known as management protocols, and can be deployed on the top level of the environment [30].

2.3.2.3 Network Configuration (NETCONF) Protocol

The NETCONF protocol defines network management responsibilities, where management functions are able to install, modify, deleting any configuration from deployed network devices. The NETCONF uses XML encoder for protocol messages and configuration data streams. The NETCONF is also used as a data transport protocol for OF-CONFIG, which enables to fulfil plenty of requirements for making switch operational throughout its environment [33].

2.3.3 SDN Controller

In SDN environments, the controller of SDN is a very important part, which is responsible for providing an ultimate and well managed global view of the entire network, and provides mandatory functionalities such as, network management and network control. A detailed view of the SDN controller is given in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Northbound and Southbound Overview of SDN Controller.

The southbound interfaces are major protocol drivers to establish reliable communication with network devices. These devices can accept more than one protocols, and these protocols comprise various meaningful device aspects such as control-plane, management plane. The service layer contributes to creating an entire global view in abstraction form, later it implies instruction logic to the network via southbound APIs interface. The instruction set is extracted either from internal components or external application programmes but extraction of instruction is derived via northbound interfaces. The control logic and management section contains centralised functions. Network functions use traditional network functions, such as routing that is now improved as a centralised logical unit. The northbound APIs interfaces utilise SDN controller services to its applications and then enable the network to be programmed. The northbound APIs interfaces broadcast various services from the controller to applications for the purpose of making network programmable. Lastly, east-west APIs interfaces provide support for the controller to controller communication, which comprises high priority for workload equitable distribution and

scalability in its horizontal controller perspective. As SDN platform is based on the centralised logical model, so that it cannot emulate centralised physical services [5]. Moreover, during the production of SDN entities, controller request reliable horizontal distribution for mapping out very feasible network operations based on redundancy in the controller layer. The SDN systematic detailed view is presented in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: Systematic Schema of SDN.

2.3.4 Network Virtualization

Network virtualization gives an effective emerging solution to isolate hardware workload inside big datacentres. It helps to share various hardware and software resources of datacentres, such as storage devices, application and configuration programmes and many network devices. Network virtualization can cater multi-tenancy by emulating virtual network on top of the infrastructure. The cloud-based model delivers provisioned resources for each tenant, interconnected to a virtual network. However, individual tenants require effective transmission between resources of on-premises to off-premises and high bandwidth adaptable virtual network. As current heterogeneous hardware-based networks comprise complexities for workload management and manipulating requirements for resilient and scalable topology. In contrast, network virtualization is feasibly capable to reproduce physical networks and network

services creation, which are completely independent of physical networks and their status and locations [34].

2.3.5 Network Function Virtualization

Network Function Virtualization (NFV) is the main part of SDN, which helps to isolate functional logic of network from hardware devices so that normal servers, storage devices and switches reinforce to all network devices. The SDN achieve this goal by deploying network functions in the software of commodity servers and switches.

Addition to this NFV lowers down the financial expenses for consolidating network services onto various hardware assets. It takes the advantages of network homogeneity and economical deployment scale. Besides these features, NFV utilises independent life cycle of both hardware and software, and later on, it can evolve separately [30].

Overall, SDN and NFV are very dependant to each other, and complement requirements by sharing appropriate features with each other. The collaborative combination of two paradigms potentially advances the latest future network environments and its up-to-date innovations.

2.3.6 Network Monitoring

A real network monitoring framework plays a very significant role in resilient network management and operation and its maintenance [43]. Such framework ensures overall scalable exposure to network data streams and provides an appropriate environment for modern network research and innovation. Network monitoring is a flow-based method, which falls into the following sections, such as Monitoring Data Generation, Data Collection, Storage, Data Processing, Orchestration and Transport shown in Figure 2.6.

2.3.7 Monitoring Data Generation

Monitoring data section uses different sources and network origin features based on network devices such as data type, feature extraction and manipulation perspective. Each device generates traffic statics individually. Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) as an agent-based communicating protocol initiate messages as devices statistics, then transport to the manager [35]. NetFlow is another agent, which utilises flow exporter in the devices to calculate overall packets streams, then generate aggregate flow records. In the payload overhead analysis, packets are deeply

inspected by Deep Packet Inspection (DPI). Later on, records of a targeted traffic stream are sent towards the controller.

2.3.8 Data Collection and Storage

This section is capable to collect and to store data to a reliable location. When data is being stored, the process of data aggregation and data anonymization takes place for reliable processing.

2.3.9 Processing

The monitoring data are extremely high in quantity, the rapid growth of infrastructure exponentially rise data volume. Meantime processing network data holds plenty of features such as trend discovery, capacity planning, and queries into real-time data exploration and decision making with data streams. The current modern network techniques for processing datasets are now enough scalable parallel to well know datasets, and they are not capable of measures relevant real-time timing requirements [36].

2.3.10 Transport

Transport is a vital part of the data monitoring framework. Data monitoring section bisects network to get access to collector and processors. The traffic data quantity, time slots, unprocessed network workload, sensitivity are considered as mandatory components during deploying efficient transport functions.

2.3.11 Orchestration

As we discussed earlier that any significant monitoring framework comprises several nodes, that can achieve a common goal with collaboration with each other. However, orchestration is also capable to select sources for service nodes combination for delivering special monitoring task, it also searches suitable path inside nodes to connect different routing mechanisms, finally, it also implements a path. In orchestration, employed components can have several paths, and enables orchestrator component for path calculation with the most closely related component. After the suitable path selection, the transport network is programmed for propagating monitoring messages.

Chapter 3

Software Defined Networks Security Survey

This Chapter:

This chapter presents the literature survey with a detailed description of DDoS attacks and its classification in SDN. In addition to this, we also provided a detailed comparison of security issues and vulnerabilities on various points of SDN based networks. Finally, we provided the various existing proposed mechanisms to deal with DDoS attacks in SDN with regard of associated SDN issues.

3.1 Introduction

With the recent advancement of computer network development, most of the core network infrastructure and data centers have experienced an exponential increase in network traffic as more and more industries are opting for online presence on social media and digital services. Most of the network system designers need to modify existing network architecture and orchestrate the network resources based on the specific requirements of industries. Legacy network architecture is not a good fit, which fails to provide the proper support and functionalities to the enterprises and end-users. As decision making capability of legacy network architecture is distributed in nature within network elements, it requires a tedious effort to update new services and functionalities to the network [37]. As a result, network service configuration and management become an error-prone and laborious task having dire consequences on the security and privacy of the data, services, and network infrastructure as a whole.

To overcome these issues, Software Defined Networking (SDN) had emerged as

a great enabler to decouple the network control plane from forwarding devices, and program and reconfigure network devices directly [4]. With the help of SDN system designers and researchers can effectively and flexibly design new network applications, protocols, and functions. Security has been a contentious topic in many newly developed networked systems, such as peer-to-peer networks and cloud networks. Following their involvement, researchers and practitioners have investigated their security concerns from various viewpoints to check their health and effectiveness of proposed approaches and security concerns, And it enables them more effective and secure so that in a real-world environment, these approaches can be adapted. Software-Defined Networking (SDN), is one of the recently introduced networking system, which operates the network in a centralized manner, is now supported by both business and academia. As far as the SDN technology is becoming famous, its security issues are becoming more vulnerable. Researchers are therefore studying security issues, as they have carried out various experiments and security analyses with many network approaches and use cases [13], [31], [38], [39].

In the SANE architecture [40], authors have proposed one of the proposals based on decoupling of control and forwarding planes, which depicts SDN platform according to latest SDN features, authors mainly focused the security aspects towards the SDN infrastructures development. The SANE architecture comprises of centralised authentication policies between controller and hosts. The major aim of the research was to incorporate the radical changes toward the SDN based networking infrastructure and end-hosts. The authors of Ethane [41], then extended the SANE model, they utilised less alteration approach to modify and extend the original legacy network. Ethane approach was able to control the network via a centralized controller, also enable the controller to insert global policy, packets based on rules in a flow table to SDN based switches. The proposed simplified approach was capable to be more programmable due to data and control plane separation.

The authors of [42] provided another security mechanism based on OpenFlow security implementation after followed by legacy security approaches, authors utilize SDN programmable networks switches and routers. OpenFlow is created by Stanford University's clean slate project as open-source, the major aim of the project was to design a new platform so that researchers can perform and test their proposed operational network applications. With the adoption of OpenFlow implementation by researchers, the industry has also paced up the SDN functionalities due to the fact that most of the SDN based networks have already been published and proven as successful design such as Google's backbone network [43], Microsoft's public cloud [44] and NTT's edge gateway [45] etc. Furthermore, in collaboration with network virtualization software, SDN significantly increased from trials evaluations to potential developments such as VMWare NSX [46], and Nuage Networks VSP [47]. As

much as SDN development trends were increasing then security vulnerabilities were also increasing in parallel, as initial SDN development were associated with minimal security concerns [48].

SDN architecture also enables to provide security advantages such as data collection for anomaly-detection and traffic analysis, which can be transferred to the controller. Central controller dominantly takes over advantage as a complete global network view, which analyses, and correlate feedback from the main controller. Followed by the global network view, the network controller can easily send various security policies in order to provide safeguard against various attacks. It is often assumed that, when SDN based network programmability is balanced or optimized with different network size, this results in major protection vulnerabilities and degradation of networks. Having significant advantages as compared to legacy network management, SDN has significant security challenges. Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks or Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks in SDN are due to flow table limitation and distributed centralised controller within network devices, trust issues between various network devices, and limitation of latest best practice of SDN programming. Most of these challenges cause network security threats such as how to provide safeguard against communication channels between integrated elements across multiple SDN domains, trusted SDN domains or inside distributed cloud based SDN domain.

In the last decade, most enterprises have created groups to deal with network vulnerabilities and designing new solutions, where researchers were mainly creating solutions to lower down the network issues. These functions included as controller replication during the event of attacks, policies conflict resolution within authenticated channel approaches. It is vitally important that if SDN development is not carried with a degree of attention and security focus is not connected then SDN could become vulnerable and will not be able to provide the potential services inside the data centre or even in a single organization. Main objective of this chapter is to survey the security literature in SDN context, we also enlist a full list of the threats and vulnerable in SDN, which helps to optimise network security and also provide feasible support to design enterprise-level secure, trusted and robust solutions.

The chapter has the following structures: Section 3.2 depicts a major framework by incorporating SDN characteristics. Section 3.3 represents the latest SDN and OpenFlow security analyses, accompanied by a categorisation of potential attacks to the architecture. In Section 3.5, a detailed review of the research work which deals with safety improvements solutions as an alternative view of SDN security. Section 3.6 comparatively analysis different viewpoints on SDN protection (Data Collection, Machine Learning, and Entropy-based solutions) with enhanced features, open challenges and proposed best practises. Section 3.7 presents discussion and

open standards and SDN protection challenges with the future perspective of SDN network. Section 3.8 presents the best recommendations as SDN based security solutions with open-source industrial-based architecture.

3.2 Power of SDN to defeat the DDoS Attacks

SDN has a robust modern and dynamic network architecture, which is more capable via its programmable features for detection and classification of DDoS attacks in various networks. In this section, we provide a brief overview of SDN advantages that it provides a feasible safeguard against DDoS attacks, later, we also depict the existing approaches in SDN context to protect the DDoS attacks.

3.2.1 Main Features of SDN to Defeat DDoS Attacks

SDN networks comprise the various modern and flexible techniques, which help to provide an effective defence mechanism for various DDoS traffic. We aim to provide the feasible SDN features to support out research work as following [10], [49], [50].

1. **Control-plane and Data-plane separation:** SDN is capable to decouple the Data-plane from Control-plane, which enables to establish effective defence mechanism in a larger network. SDN programmable features provide a mandatory separation in virtual based networks to deploy customised experiments on real-time architectures [49]. The innovative SDN based configuration could easily be shifted from operational-phase towards the experimental-phase as an interoperable model. However, feasible network evaluations are only achievable via programmable ability, which brings new configurations, experimental evaluations and new applications. Overall SDN is more flexible to provide new DDoS detection ideas, which effectively mitigate and respond to DDoS traffic either local or distributed platforms.
2. **Centralized and logical controller view:** SDN controller is also capable to provide the global view of system network wide information, the centralised global view mainly supports to design consistent and scalable security policies to manipulate and analyse the network packets in detail. This feature helps to provide a feasible defence approach against network threats. SDN centralised control helps to create effective quarantine mechanisms for DDoS affected hosts, also provide authentication methodologies for legitimate hosts based on hosts end nodes information, Remote Authentication Dial in User Service (RADIUS) server information or system authentication information during registration [49].

3. **Network programmability via an external application:** This feature of SDN provides support to the intelligent harvesting process from existing Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) [51]. Addition to this harvesting process also utilises the existing support from Intrusion Prevention Systems (IPs) [52]. Although, programmability approach caters more innovative ways to design effective and intelligent DDoS detection algorithms.
4. **Software based traffic manipulation:** Traffic analysis with software-based feature optimise the capabilities of network switches. Most of the traffic analysis is performed using machine learning or other software tools on a real-time network. These features of SDN can easily redirect the traffic toward the deployed IPSs system for Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) [49].
5. **Updating flow abstraction and forwarding rules:** SDN based updating rules effectively respond to DDoS attacks. New security policies can be inserted to the network by updating security policies, these security policies are propagated in the form of flow rules [52]. SDN helps to deploy new security updates such as packet forwarding rules to switches, once DDoS attacks are identified, then the malicious traffic is denied before reaching network [49].
6. **Integration of Snort and OpenFlow:** Snort [53] is a widely used open-source network intrusion detection sensor. The Open Information Security Foundation (OISF) created Suricata sensor which is alternative to Snort, Suricata is also an open source network security solution. It supports multi threads function that enables it more effective like Snort. However, Snort is widely recognisable due to its network community and its collaboratively working capability with OpenFlow. Snortflow [54] is a technique, which combines both Snort and OpenFlow in a cloud-based environment for detecting intrusions. Similarly, NICE, also deployed a multi-phase distributed vulnerability detection, measurement, counter-measure section method. It is also utilising both Snort and Openflow to detect cloud based network intrusions. Overall, the system main objective more likely focus to provide safeguard against the virtual machine from being compromised by intruders inside a cloud based network.

3.3 Types of DDoS attacks and Classification in SDN Networks

According to the authors of [55] With the prevalence of cloud computing and advancements in cybersecurity, launching a DDoS attack is relatively straight forward compared to pre-cloud era - most attackers create botnet computer networks to

launch DDoS attacks. However, providing a security mechanism against DDoS attacks is difficult and time consuming. DDoS attacks are mainly classified into the following two categories, which rely on the targeted protocol levels [52]:

1. DDoS flooding attacks on Network/transport Layer. These types of DDoS attacks are generated via TCP, UDP, ICMP, and DNS protocols, these types of DDoS attacks mainly focus on disruption of legitimate network users. These attacks consume the network bandwidth to run down available resources [55].
2. DDoS flooding attacks on Application Layer. These types of DDoS attacks focus on disruption the legitimate user's services by lowering down the server and datacentres resources such as CPU, memory, sockets, and network bandwidth, database bandwidth and I/O resources so on, more detailed DDoS attacks taxonomy is also depicted in Figure 3.1 with TCP/IP protocols[55].

Figure 3.1: DDoS attacks Taxonomy based on TCP/IP Model.

3.3.1 Issues with DDoS Defence Mechanisms.

Most of the existing work mainly focuses to provide the DDoS defence mechanism with various SDN features. However, DDoS attacks trends are exponentially rising, therefore most proposed mechanisms face issues to defeat the DDoS attacks in SDN context [56]. Most common issues are provided as below:

1. **Data-collection:** In most of the DDoS detection and mitigation methods, data collection plays a vital role to create normal traffic profile or to classify and identify the abnormal traffic. For example, plenty of proposed solutions require traffic feature extraction from implemented networks for the purpose of identifying malicious events. In cloud-based computing and IoT environment, DDoS attacks are also increasing, which requires a tremendous amount of data collection from heterogenous based networks. Collecting data from such a heterogenous network also results in lower overhead. In cloud and IoT networks most of the network devices are distributed by multi-tenant and load balancing approaches, therefore a collection of data during attack migration becomes more challenging.
2. **Selecting an intelligent algorithm:** The rapid increment of DDoS attacks has also introduced tremendous network complexities in a larger network. To deal such massive DDoS floods, many machine learning algorithms such as artificial neural networks, Bayesian classifier, chaotic traffic analysis, hidden semi-Markov model (HSMM) model, game-theory, fuzzy-logic and so on have been utilised. However, DDoS attacks are becoming more popular due to complexities, so there is not any feasible solution or single intelligent algorithm that effectively deal with all DDoS attacks. Addition to this, selecting and deploying the correct algorithm to deal with the massive traffic of DDoS is also a challenging task in SDN context.
3. **Prompt response:** To deal with the DDoS attacks and traffic manipulation with the prompt response is a significantly important either smaller or larger network such as local area networking or Cloud based IoT platforms. Although, due to traffic overhead and DDoS attacking complexities, rapid and effective responses has become more challenging. Such as a larger number of heterogenous network security devices of data-centres still, require collaborative interoperable work to provide a quick response against attacks or traffic classification based on malicious or benign features. Interoperability helps to utilise a larger number of protocols to provide flexible compatibility between all devices, nodes, and tools.

3.4 Security Analysis and Potential Attacks in SDN

OpenFlow A larger number of SDN/OpenFlow based security approaches have been discussed in [57] to [58]. In each analyses of work, most of authors investigated that modification of SDN elements and relationship between these elements and SDN approaches introduce new types of security vulnerabilities, these were not available in SDN in previous whole research. However, the authors in [57] to [58] analysis also proposed optimized security approaches introduced in SDN. OpenFlow protocol is widely considered for development of SDN based technologies. Although, most of existing security analyses widely uses OpenFlow protocol. The authors, in [59] provided analysis of OpenFlow by utilizing STRIDE threat analysis mechanism [60]. Major aim of this work relies on Information Disclosure and DoS traffic. Moreover, larger number of mitigation techniques have been published such as flow rules aggregation to lower down the table flow size.

The OpenFlow switch specification investigated the use of Transport Layer Security (TLS) by using bi-directional authentication between controller and switches. Although, in TLS security feature is optional, which is not specified. The authors in [13] have discussed lack of this feature in majority of vendors (including open source controller and switches), and also rules insertion and modification of DoS traffic. In analysis of [57], overall security of the SDN is depicted that new responses are mandatory from centralised control-plane threats and network programmable approach. From seven threat vectors, only three vectors were related to controller and more specific to controller software, control-data interface, and control-application interface. The large number of security solutions provided such as, to replicate controller applications in order to present alternative management for the both of hardware and software faults. Another solution to fix software based vulnerabilities inside any single controller and Trusted Computing Based (TCB) are utilised for providing safeguard for credential security data. The authors of [57] in collaboration of [48] authors have presented SDN based survey, where SDN based security dependencies are investigated with OpenFlow based networks security countermeasures.

The relationship between SDN based networks vulnerabilities and attacks has been depicted in the research of [61] and [62]. The authors of [61] have proposed a ProtoGENI testbed for analysis, they have invested that ProtoGENI testbed users with flooding attacks and malicious information can affect the large Internet network. Currently, feasible research has been presented against fingerprinting attacks in SDN networks [62], during the attack event, firstly most of network parameters are being fingerprinted for identifying nature of OpenFlow switches. Then the control-

Table 3.1: Summary of SDN-OpenFlow Security Analysis

Existing Work via OpenFlow	Year	OF-Security Analysis		OF	SDN-Interfaces				
		Vulnerabilities	Optimisation		Appl	App-Cont	Cont	Con-Data	Data
Surveys on SDN Security [65]	2013	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ProtoGENI [6], OF-Vulnerability [13]	2016 2013	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓
SDN-survey [57]	2015	✓		✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
FLowVisor [66]	2015	✓		✓			✓	✓	
SDN-attacks [62]	2016	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓
SDN-network Security [63]	2014	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	
SDN as Blessing/Curse [64]	2014	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
SDN-wireless Security [67]	2014	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓

plane is affected with DoS attack by using data-plane flow-table of network devices. Although, a DoS attack can easily make any system network resources unavailable for its potential users. In SDN context, most of network related devices require access to control-plan for receiving traffic management policies, these instructions enable to manipulate the flow tables of devices. Due to this fact data-plane of SDN and flow table of these devices are vulnerable to majority of DoS traffic.

The authors of [63], extended the SDN based network security management, they have investigated research into different categories such as software stack, network protocols and nature of platform. According to authors, SDN switches security and communication between controller to controller still require further work with authentication and confidentiality. For the purpose of providing safeguard against SDN based switches and controller attacks, most of researchers have proposed various solutions, which are also provided in this section. The authors in [64], depicted comparison of SDN security with legacy network architecture, for evaluation of SDN security, the authors utilised feasible approach of confidentiality, integrity, availability, consistency and authenticity. As conclusion, they investigated with argument that most of SDN based vulnerability issues still exist in legacy networks, many of researchers have not covered effective detection of large attacks surface on top of SDN layered infrastructures, which causes bad impact on vulnerability of security infrastructures. However, authors of [63] have also provided various future direction to meet up the security challenges inside SDN based deployments.

The authors of [67] recommended the utilisation of SDN for security of wireless networks, they also recommended security enhancement solutions. This work comprises limited SDN based security survey that pragmatically represents the security solution based on vulnerable environments. There have been several studies investigated for SDN security deployment, compatibility, self adaptation and interoperability. Overall, a mobile wireless security infrastructure is proposed on on top of control-plan security layer with implementation of unique agents on data-plane. However, authors of [58] proposed SDN based cloud security and also introduced new issues of SDN based cloud implementation. Although, authors have collaboratively discussed vulnerabilities and opportunities, they provided a feasible experimental

Table 3.2: Security Issues associated with SDN Interface and Layers

Security Issues	Description	Application Layer	App-Con Interface	Control plane	Con-Data Interface	Data-plane
1-Unauthorised Access						
Unauthorised Controller Access	To compromise Controller			✓	✓	✓
Unauthorised Application Access	Unauthentic Application					
2-Data-leakage						
Flow Rule Discovery	Input buffer channel attacks					✓
Credential Management	Apply certificates to network					✓
Forwarding Policy Discovery	Analysis of packet orientation			✓	✓	✓
3-Data-Modification						
Flow Rule Modification	Modify packets for MITM attacks			✓	✓	✓
4-Malicious Applications						
Fraudulent Rule Insertion	Apply false rule for security	✓	✓	✓		
5-Denial of Service (DoS)						
Controller Switch Communication Flooding	Attacks on controller switch			✓	✓	✓
Flooding on Switch Flow Table	Attacks on flow table of switch					✓
6-Configuration Issues						
TLS issues	Adopting different authentications	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Policy Enforcement issues		✓	✓	✓		
Secure Provisioning		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
7-Security of SDN system Level						
Network visibility issues				✓	✓	✓

evaluation to support the expansion of SDN based implementation from a local campus network to wide area networks. Shifting from local to larger area network require more security consideration and policies to make system more secure in SDN.

Table 3.1 represents the security analysis in the term of OpenFlow and SDN interface. Previous research work represents that most of the security analysis of SDN is carried in OpenFlow based protocols, this framework helps to modify network applications and also supports data forwarding via OpenFlow protocol. However, most of the authors such as [10], [57] have provided detailed security analysis especially for control-plan and data-plan interfaces. In their work, the major focus was to highlight security issues caused by introducing 3rd party applications in SDN networks.

3.4.1 SDN Common Attacks and Vulnerabilities

In SDN security analysis, most of the existing work is categorised into the type of nature with SDN based interfaces. As Table 3.2 depicts that most of SDN issues are feasibly divided into seven major categories, in Table 3.2, most of these issues are critically analysed with specific examples arising from these vulnerable issues. The Table 3.2 comprises only attack specific security issues with SDN context. Addition to this, major deployments issues that were easily prone to vulnerabilities are also discussed. Moreover, the Table 3.2 detailed security analysis is utilised to map SDN architecture, which is presented in Figure 3.2, in the Figure 3.2, SDN interfaces which are affected by attacks or some other vulnerabilities caused by 3rd parties applications or deployments concerns are also depicted. Most of common existing SDN attacks with characteristics are given as below:

Figure 3.2: SDN Attacks and Vulnerabilities with Different Layers

3.4.1.1 Unauthorised-Access

This category mainly focuses to get access to control-plan. The SDN control-plan is the most important element of SDN that centrally handles all networking policies. Due to the rapid growth of modern technologies, it has become a widely used centralised approach for security considerations. However, functional deployment of SDN is capable to use multiple controllers to access the larger network data-plane. Similarly, applications from multiple resources, such as 3rd party applications are also supposed to be used with a major controller. The SDN controller helps to provide an abstracted view of all applications so that every network application can be capable to read or write network policies, this is very useful to manage the overall network effectively. When attackers perform an attack on SDN controller application then the attacker can reach the major network resources, and can easily deviate major network changes [56].

3.4.1.2 Data-Leakage

According to the authors of [30], OpenFlow switch has a lot of feasible specifications to handle network packets, such as forward, drop and sent to the controller. During the event of packet processing time analysis, the attacker can easily identify the specific actions utilised for specific packets manipulation. For example, the time required to process packet from input port to output port will be reduced than the packet redirection processing towards the controller. However, attackers pro-actively or re-actively gather feasible network switches configuration information, later, by utilising more detailed crafted attacking approaches, these attackers easily infer potential network devices statistics. Similarly, the authors in [11], also investigated that when the packets are redirected to the central controller, then attacker launches huge volume of malicious request, which results in massive Denial of Service (DoS) attacks. Addition to this, authors also depicted the relationship between data-leakage and DoS attacks.

Moreover, SDN architecture carries another security challenges such as credential secure storage certificates (eg, keys and authentication certificates) especially for multiple paths access towards logical data-plan. In previous research, most authors have evaluated the attacks on cross virtual machines channels, most of these attacks were demonstrated in SDN based cloud networks. The authors of [68] identified vulnerable VM by utilising security certificates attacks vulnerabilities, they extracted secured potential information from targeted VM. Based on the aforementioned literature, SDN also comprises of Data-leakage. Most commonly identified vulnerabilities are of data-leakage are found in OF-Config, multiple OF-logical switches when deployed on top of OpenFlow switch. In every switch, each logical instances are assigned with the unique customer, if the logical switch and its related potential information (such as pair of keys and certificates) are not packed with security isolation then, switch information could be breached and compromised from every logical instance.

3.4.1.3 Data-Modification

In previous literature, it is well mentioned that an SDN controller can easily programme the network devices to control the SDN for table and its forwarding plan when an attacker becomes successful to compromise the controller then the attacker can easily take over the control over entire infrastructure. An attacker can launch a program from privileged position to insert and modify network devices rules, which enables attacker to get access within entire network and to modify data in each network devices.

Similarly, when intermediate entities (such as Flow Visor [69], Open Virtex [70],

and [71] Flow N [72] and Layer 2 and layer 3 agents) are used between data-plane and control-plane, then there should be a robust secured network placed between network devices and components communication channels [5]. The OpenFlow switch in term of the communication channel more likely uses TLS authentication between the central controller and SDN switches. Although, the network security feature is not mandatory and the deployment of TLS is not specified as well. Due to the lack of the implementation of TLS in the majority of proprietary switches and network controller, most of these systems are vulnerable for man-in-the-middle attacker, which can easily launch various attacks, including OpenFlow message to manipulate the controller, which are sent from the controller for resetting the connection. Addition to this, components which are placed between control-plane and data-plane must be secured to avoid more security issues. A man-in-the-middle attack rises when an attacker is capable to infiltrate and monitor messages between two victims, and can easily modify or inject various types of network messages in potential communication interfaces. This only happens, when there is not any authentication deployment between communication endpoint. According to the authors of [38], in the hypervisor of the FlowVisor network, OpenFlow protocol was investigated with a lack of proper network isolation approach [66], which enable potential attackers to reset and modify the credential data with malicious attacks inside communication channels. To split the SDN architecture is more likely concerned with issues of data modification in SDN.

3.4.1.4 Malicious Application types

Normally the controller provides an abstraction of data-plane from the application, it also enables most of the 3rd party applications to effectively work with SDN architecture Majority of malicious applications provide a destructive impact on a compromised network controller. Similarly, if the network application is not systematically designed then it could create vulnerabilities issues in the system. For example, any system related malicious bug can easily be compromised by the attacker, in order to extract application towards an unstable position. This type of security issue in SDN has been discussed by many researchers in Section 3.5

3.4.1.5 Denial of Service

In the SDN network, Denial of Service (DoS) attack is a most vulnerable weakness that can run down the entire SDN system, which is more likely caused due to the fact of combining SDN centralised controller and separation of SDN control-plane and data-plane. An attacker can generate DoS flooding packets on the controller by using packet flow rules then leave the most of services unavailable for the legitimate users.

Similarly, another DoS attack could be launched on the same controller by utilising flow table rules, where limited memory resources are available [10]. Addition to this, there is a chance to launch more DoS traffic by means of inserting and modifying fraudulent rules [13]. The special research community has feasibly discussed these types of attacks in SDN context in Section 3.5 and 3.6.

3.4.1.6 Configuration Issues

Recently developments of security protocols and policies are also bringing new vulnerabilities inside the same networks, most of these issues are detected from the SDN network interface layer. However, during security deployment, if configuration policies are not well maintained or if they are disabled without basic security knowledge then the entire network could be considered unsafe. For a network developer, it is mandatory to deploy security policies such as TLS. Although, as depicted in Table 3.2, most incorrect and misconfigured security parameters of the network can make the entire system malicious and vulnerable for intruders to get each network policies and resources.

Leaving network components to interface openly accessible can also incorporate security issues, these issues are not only occurred between various vendors specific devices but also occurs with data-based communication and management policies with all newly created interfaces. SDN applications are more capable to be programmed with network requirement, also helps to develop more robust data flow policies. This types of SDN approaches may result in various securities vulnerabilities. Moreover, policies implementation on various applications and multiple vendor devices should be identified during configuration, which enables the overall system more secure otherwise unmatched policies could lead to security conflicts. In the existing literature, various security solutions have been proposed by different authors.

3.4.1.7 System Level SDN Security

According to the authors of [56], system level of SDN also comprises major security concerns. One of the most feasible industry level concern is to satisfy the process of auditing, it is significantly considered very important in term of network compliance and operation, which helps to provide manageable network devices implementation. This is due to the fact of having relevant network device knowledge, how these are integrated with this network and devices etc. For example, OpenFlow switches are capable to operate either in standalone mode or in the fail-secure mode. During the event of switch discontinuity from the controller, then default internal logic of that switch decides to be operated in any of the above modes. However, when the

Table 3.3: Summary of Existing Solutions for SDN Security Issues

Existing Work for Security Issues	Application Layer	App-Con Interface	Control plane	Con-Data Interface	Data-plane
Unauthorised Access Issues					
Distributed Control Security [73], Byzantine Resilient Approach [74]			✓	✓	
Resilient Authentication [75]			✓		
PermOF Model [76]	✓	✓			
OperationCheckpoint [77]	✓	✓	✓		
SE-FloodLight [4] [39]	✓	✓	✓	✓	
AuthFlow Model [78]	✓		✓	✓	✓
Denial of Service (DoS)					
AVANT-GUARD Model [11], CPRRecovery Model [79]			✓	✓	✓
VAVE Model [80]	✓		✓	✓	✓
Network Security Delegating Model [81]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Malicious Applications					
FortNOX-model [82]	✓	✓	✓	✓	
ROSEMARY-model [38]	✓		✓		
Configuration Issues					
NICE-Model [83]	✓	✓		✓	
FlowChecker [84], Flover [85], Anteater-Model [86], VeriFlow-Model [87], NetPlumber-Model [88]	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Firewall Security Enhancement [89], FlowGuard-Model [90], [91], LPM-Model [92]	✓		✓	✓	✓
Flow-Based Policy [93], Regular Updating-Model [94], Data Store sharing [95], Splendid-Isolation [96]	✓		✓	✓	✓
Vericare-Model [97], Machine Verification Model [98], VeriCon-Model [99]		✓	✓	✓	
SDN Sytem Level Issues					
SDN Debugger-model [100]	✓			✓	
OFHIP-model [101], Secure-SDMN-model [102]				✓	
FRESCO-model [11]	✓	✓	✓	✓	

connection re-established, then the controller has to decide and take over the entire control of the switch and internal network statistics. The network operator critically has to decide, in which mode, network switch must be operated during the time of connection interruption, data forwarding plane during failure time, affected flow entries, controller status after reconnection. For the purpose of auditing network statics, it is very significant to extract and manage operational information with SDN context [56].

Network security has brought many security challenges, for providing proper access communication to network resources. Most of the security engineers are deploying larger and complex techniques in networks, these complexities bringing various unmanageable security issues in networks. The secure communication networks comprise on confidentiality, integrity and availability of network states, these communication properties are manipulated with the approaches of end to end encryption, authentication and authorisation. The combination of these properties represents a secure network, where most of the datasets, communication transactions are safe from being attacked or other security issues. In this section, our work depicts some possible vulnerabilities and other SDN network-related challenges. Moreover, it is very feasible to critically impose a well-managed and safe infrastructure so that every network components flexibly works in that architecture[56].

3.5 Solutions of SDN Vulnerabilities

As, Table 3.2, represents the seven major attacks types in SDN related network, similarly, we have categorised these solutions of these seven issues in Table 3.3. 3.3 represents some proposed solutions, due to the fact that there is not any existing work published for providing a solution for Data Leakage or Data Modification SDN vulnerabilities. Table 3.3 represents the solution against the SDN issues of Table 3.2 and provides a comparison of different SDN interfaces. According to literature surveys, Configuration Issues and Unauthorised issues are widely considered for various security solutions. Overall, it can be seen that in SDN infrastructure, most of the data-plane interface are least affected and compromised by an attacker, this is due to the fact of focusing only on software-based solution rather than hardware-based security integration.

3.5.1 Unauthorized Access

As depicted in Table 3.2, unauthorised access towards the controller and any network application are defined as attack vectors. These types of attack vectors can severely damage the SDN network or implementation components. Authors of [73] hybrid controller model for providing a solution and improving controller efficiency, in the proposed model, authors have proposed a secure model for distributed controllers. Central major elements are protected by providing TLS security approach. Moreover, the authors of [73] have also proposed an algorithm, which security transfer requests of packets flows and network devices configuration request as well. In this proposed model, central trusted management is utilised for checking model signatures and overhead queue messages transmission.

Authors of [74], analysed SDN network controller vulnerabilities and attacks. Authors have proposed secure SDN architecture, in which each network entity is controlled by distributed multiple controllers via utilising the mechanism of the Byzantine approach. In order to lower down the Byzantine mechanism fault tolerance, various controller with effective and flexible algorithm assignment. Moreover, there are large numbers of solution exists with distributed SDN controller models that support security scalability and reliability in SDN context [5], [103]. As proposed model represents a distributed approach, which significantly rectifies the protection in term of unauthorised SND major controller access. For synchronising the various network groups states in HyperFlow, a distributed mechanism can be utilised, if the model uses multiple controllers [5]. The controller, which is based with HyperFlow more likely broadcasts events that cause the model state deviation, on the other hand, another collaborative controller reconstructs and manages

Table 3.4: Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN Unauthorised Access Issues.

Proposed Model	Year	Major Goals	Methods	Detection Accuracy	Mitigation	Traffic analysis
Distributed Control Security [73]	2013	To secure the distributed controllers to detect DDoS	Inserting flow installation rules via signature algorithm	✓		✓
Secure Byzantine Resilient Approach [74]	2016	To protect SDN control-plane from malicious traffic	Byzantine Fault Tolerant algorithm for multiple controller architecture	✓		✓
Resilient Authentication [75]	2013	To cater a robust and more secured SDN architecture	A hierarchical system to reduce failure points of controller and switches	✓		✓
PermOF Model [76]	2013	To provide OF access to each applications	A permission privilege system to reduce application access	✓	✓	✓
OperationCheckpoint [77]	2015	To Maintain controller operation linked with applications	PermissionCheck solution proposed to secure interface of app-control	✓		✓
Security Enhanced (SE) FloodLight [4], [39]	2015	To maintain the security issues between ata-plane/control-plane and OF modules	A OF control layer security solution with role-based authorisation	✓		✓
AuthFlow Model [78]	2016	To protect against unauthorised access to SDN hosts	An access control solution based authentication	✓		✓

network states to bring the system in working order.

Due to local decision approach in a distributed controller, the response time between control-plane entities is reduced. As authors of [103] with the help of SoftCell utilised local software-based agents for making a repository of policy tags and classifier packets, this enables the controller to reduce network and memory overhead. However, authors of [104] isolated controller local decision-making approach from network level decision approach. In the proposed mechanism, some of the specific applications are manipulated with the utilisation of local controller event process, this also enables the main controller to lower down processing burden.

The authors in [105] depicted the combined recursive approach of Logical xBar and Logical Server for the proposal of utilising building block in their proposed solution. This combined approach enables the local controller to be extended towards a larger network scale. As these approaches cannot provide perfect security mechanism but, due to the distributed controller approach, these designs can mitigate the security issues in the individual SDN controller. However, there are large numbers of open source controller exist (eg. ONOS [106], OpenDaylight [107]), which are capable to deploy multiple controllers with the distributed ability. To make more secure, more additional security measures are still required to resiliency in the SDN network [108].

According to development scenarios especially in legacy applications, unauthorised access is caused due to lack of TLS feature [13]. This is a very feasible consideration, that must be utilised during the implementation of network applications, controllers and their mandatory components, which then caters a trusted Internet network domain. For the purpose of bringing trust between applications and potential network, the authentication and authorisation both play a very vital role. The authors of [109] have investigated the issue in order to lower down the failure locations, they have proposed an SDN based, hierarchical test-bed between controllers and switches. This was achieved after splitting the overall system into layers such as

middle management, and layer between switches fabrication and central controller, this approach was capable to localise the vulnerabilities caused by unauthorised access into the SDN network. As this proposed system considers the central controller as a trusted element. From the investigation, the proposed solution helps to reduce the impact on malicious activities such as compromised network applications. Addition to this, authors also recommend that middle management layer must be utilised with feasible controller protection, to run configuration or code applications. Although authors emphasize that there is still a need to tackle the heterogenous SDN network development issues, in various existing work, authors do not propose proper security achievement process.

In [110], the architecture of fault tolerance is depicted. For achieving flexible transmission between SDN controllers during the event of a controller interface failure, data points from which central controller fetches network statistics should be installed with fault tolerance features. Each connection must be secured for all controllers. The authors in [76], have investigated the issues caused by OpenFlow full privilege access. In this proposed work, they have designed PermOF with combined features of permission and isolation of the entries of Application Programming Interface (APIs). The proposed mechanism implies some security privileges in order to provide a safeguard against control-plane malicious attacks. Similarly, authors of [77] also extended the system which is based on permission, they proposed a system in Floodlight SDN controller with operation checkpoint [111]. This work utilises set of permissions with the help of which, network applications initiate with the perspective controller, then these applications initialise Operation Checkpoint and enable the system to verify permissions for authorised access. This system is also able to classify malicious activities to construct SDN profile with application-layer attacks, this profile is created by using unauthorised operations logs.

A Floodlight controller based Security Enhanced (SE) system is created by Stanford Research Institute [4], [39] with OpenFlow and Floodlight controller extension. This system comprises on Security Enforcement Kernel (SEK), this mechanism is built on the improvement of FortNox, which more likely utilises northbound APIs with digital authentication certificates. An OpenFlow application developed with Java class is mandatory to be signed by the network administrator, then it should be verified by SEK during run-time. However, once applications are signed and verified then permission is granted to modify network or traffic statistics. The granularity is the only difference between SE Floodlight system and PremOF OperationCheckpoint. The system of PremOF OperationCheckpoint helps application to access set of actions.

For the avoiding unauthorised host's access towards SDN, the authentication based access controller approach such as Auth-Flow is depicted in [78]. The pro-

posed system is created with the help of the OpenFlow controller and RADIUS server based on feasible authentication. The process of authentication classifies the messages of Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) into host request, similarly RADIUS authentication server caters responses to OF controller. The controller is capable to either allow or deny traffic based on authentication responses. The trusted host pairing mechanism enables to implement the access control. If there is some unauthorised access to SDN based network, then it is tackled by SDN various layers. The proposed solution is able to provide safeguard with trusted SDN layers. Table 3.4 represents the summary of existing solutions based on research goals based on unauthorised access of SDN elements such as controller and switches. The authors of [73], [75] presented a feasible solution against unauthorised controller access. However, authors in [4], [76] depicted the solutions, which tackle out unauthorised access only for SDN applications. Similarly, authors of [78] proposed host level based solution that lower down classifies the access control.

3.5.2 Malicious Applications

For securing malicious or compromised applications during the deployment phase, there is an alarming demand for creating a trusted connection between controllers and applications of the proposed system, this could only be achieved by means of authentication approach between controllers message exchange. Addition to this, the authors of [38], [82] have also proposed other advanced solutions, such as SEK solution is proposed by [82], which enables the controller to identifies malicious activities on applications which are deployed on the controller. However, FortNox is capable to implements feasible authentication, which is role-based, this approach helps to identify OF application security authorisation. The Fort-Nox engine model manages the possible outcome of flow rules insertion issues, where rules rejection and acceptance is more likely based on administrator security authorisation. Addition to this, Fort-Nox system also identifies new conflicts issues with flow rules. Once new conflicts occur from flow rules request with higher administrator priority, then existing flow rules will be replaced. However, if new conflicts occur from flow rules request with lower administrator priority, then it will be ignored. There are three basic flow rules defined such as OF Operator, OF Security, and OF application. This approach is limited by some security authorisation level. Fort-Nox system cannot identify application identification and priority criteria.

The authors of [38] in ROSEMARY approach proposed a resilient and high performance secured Network Operating System (NOS), in which centralised ROSEMARY element of proposed system helps to rectify control-plan resiliency, which supports to classify buggy and malicious applications. For this objective, authors

also presented the mini architecture of NOS, where each application is allotted to run with an individual approach of ROSEMARY system. ROSEMARY is capable to protect the control-plane application from several vulnerabilities by utilising, protection is achieved by using the sandbox approach. The proposed solution isolates the network applications from secured network resource built on NOS, where each application of NOS consumes more likely monitoring and control networking resources such as calls with the privileged system. NOS system effectively initialises each device from a default state. However, this work is has been published recently ao protect SDN compromised applications.

With the help of LegoSDN system, authors in [112] utilise application failure consequences based on controller reliability. The protection SDN application damage could result in the whole SDN controller crash, in order to avoid this crash in SDN, authors feasibly isolate various SDN application layers, network level transaction system (a layer to update and roll-back major application events) and fault tolerance layer (a layer to identify and manipulate crash handling events). Moreover, ROSEMARY system also motivates LegoSDN with the capabilities of availability and security concerns.

Identifying the 3rd party application is a key element of SDN characteristics. However, SDN has the potential ability to integrate 3rd party applications, which enables the NOS system controller to handle both buggy and malicious applications. Although, ROSEMARY [113] and LegoSDN [114] are a very effective and feasible solution to protect such threats. Moreover, there is more demand to significantly pace up the relevant research to get more optimised solution with capabilities of maintenance and resiliency of failure criteria into large scale network deployments. TABLE V depicts the summary of major solutions against SDN malicious applications issues. The authors of [82] provided authorisation application for safeguard against compromised or malicious SDN applications, in contrast, the authors in [10], [114] provided mechanism to isolate such applications in order to make controller and overall network more robust and secure from such threats.

3.5.3 Denial of Service (DoS)

As discussed in Section III, SDN separation of control-plane and data-plane in SDN comprises a significant weakness, which can result in massive DoS attacks on central SDN controller or its widely used programmable switch flow table. The authors of [11] to [81] have proposed various potential solutions to resolve DoS attacks in SDN context. AVANT-GUARD [11].

In [79], the authors depicted the CPRecovery, a component replication approach to support network resiliency. Once external intruder compromises the network

Table 3.5: Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN Denial of Service Issues.

Proposed Model	Year	Major Goals	Methods	Detection Accuracy	Mitigation	Traffic Analysis
AVANT-GUARD Model [11]	2013	Control-plane safeguard against DDoS attacks to detect respond flow deviation	To migrate the connections is utilised to lower data interaction between flow triggers and data control-plane	✓		✓
CPRecovery Model [79]	2012	To protect centralised network OS failure from malicious DoS traffic	To provide a flexible backup with CPRecovery Model for primary controller	✓		✓
VAVE Model [80]	2011	To provide a robust and more secured SDN architecture with Source Address Validation	Network global view provided to validate rules via NOX controller	✓		✓
Network Security Delegating Model [81]	2009	To deny the administrative bottlenecks from the proposed network	Ident++ protocol is utilised for the purpose of network security policies delegation	✓	✓	✓

operating system, then CPRecovery components seamless provide facility such as shifting the major compromised controller towards the backup location. This proposed approach only performs within a centralised controller.

The authors of [80] proposed preemptive safety approach for IP spoofing later on which results in DoS attacks, they utilised source address validation. The proposed solution is known with Virtual source Address Validation Edge (VAVE), in which authors utilises the traffic analysis feature and rules update feature for providing a safeguard against IP spoofing or DoS attacks. Once incoming packets do not match with predefined rule-set then OpenFlow switch reverses back that packets towards controller for validation of source IP. If the controller identifies spoofed IP, then NOX based effective OpenFlow controller inserts new switches policies to limit and maintain the packet flow rules. For example, once the rule occupies the flow area of various source addresses, then this mechanism reduces the limit of switch flow storage to overcome the flow table attacks.

The authors of [81] proposed ident++ protocol, which can be used for DoS protection in SDN. This protocol queries the networks and host for acquiring more information so that a network operator can effectively enable network security in end-hosts. The proposed method effectively support the network management with appropriate delegation of trust and authentication.

The Solution of DoS utilises the SDN characteristics in order to imply SDN attacks solution. With the help of a distributed controller and dynamic flow table management, most common threats in SDN such as DoS attacks can be mitigated. The Table 3.5 depicts a summary of proposed solutions with existing research work, most of the authors have focused DoS attacks based solution in SDN context. Moreover, the authors of [11], [79] and [81] proposed solution, which mainly focuses on the controller congestion issues, in contrast, the authors in [57] presented an effective solution for mitigating data-layer DoS attacks.

3.5.4 Different Solutions to SDN Configuration Issues

In the existing literature, many authors have proposed different solutions for configuration application issues arising during SDN deployment [83] to [99], [88] to [45]. They have utilised multiple combined modelling techniques based on network statistics. Most of them utilised customised algorithms for the purpose of, to identify networks either carries errors or not [83] to [115], to check policies based on real-time slot [87] to [90], to maintain the maintain different applications flow overlapping via language-based approaches [69,70], similarly process of formal method verification is carried out by authors of [96] [99]. All of these above authors solutions have been categorised into following sub-categories: to identifying network errors, to verify real-time policies, to resolve language-based issues resolution, unified network abstraction view and formal verification approaches.

3.5.4.1 Network errors detection

The authors in NICE [83], combined their model with the approach of symbolic execution that verify OpenFlow application correctness. The proposed model helps to identify errors when network faces inconsistency and unreliable states. Authors in [84] proposed a FlowChecker, to classify intra-switch configuration errors by utilising binary decision classification in the flow table. The authors of Flover [85] utilised modulo theories and set of assertion for the purpose of flow policies verification, where each flow rule is verified with non-bypass values in the network, The model of Flover is capable to handle batch model to optimise controller response time. However, authors of [86] presented an analysis based on statistical network troubleshooting approach for the classification of configuration issues.

These types of methodologies only support the data-plane verification, overall these techniques can be processed either in few seconds or several hours, which can lead to finding issues after a long time and failed to identify with real-time slots. This issue can be vulnerable and left overall architecture easy to damage.

Table 3.6: Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN Configuration Issues.

Proposed Model	Year	Major Goals	Methods	Error Detection	Policy Checking	Network View	Formal Verification
Anteater-Model [86]	2011	To identify the data-plane issues	Utilises a statistical tool for classifying network invariant	✓			
Regular Updating-Model [94]	2011	To maintain configuration instability and deviations inside SDN application	Caters consistent abstraction view to support updates rules		✓	✓	
VeriFlow-Model [87]	2012	To detect network invariant in real-time applications	Utilises OF network slicing to classify the the properties that violate invariant		✓		
NICE-Model [83]	2012	To verify the OF based applications for correctness	To enable intelligent OF testing applications to remove controller bugs	✓			
FlowChecker [85]	2013	Removing OF configuration errors caused by conflicting of flow rules	Utilising binary decision diagram (BDD) for testing switches infrastructure errors	✓			
Flover [85]	2013	To verify the dynamic flow policies not to affect the security concerns	Utilises Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) to verify the violating flow policies if exists	✓			
NetPlumber-Model [88]	2013	To maintain and verify the network correctness in real-time	Utilises computational counter to verify the policy based updates in real-time		✓		
Firewall Security Enhancement [89]	2013	To identify and bypass firewall threats inside OF based infrastructure	Shifted flow graph (HSA) utilised to track the flows then, deny these flows paths		✓		
FlowGuard-Model [90], [91]	2014	To identify and resolve the conflicting firewall policies via OF features	Utilises the automatic real-time resolution method by tracking rules dependencies and flow path		✓		
LPM-Model [92]	2014	Analyse and maintain complex network issues via SDN programmability	Utilises the policy management framework to resolve inter-module,application, intra-table dependencies			✓	
Data Store sharing [95]	2013	To maintain network performance for providing flexible and consistent SDN view	Fault tolerant data-store, highly consistent scalable and distributed in nature			✓	
Splendid-Isolation [96]	2012	Helps to program shared networks devices via secure and reliable channel	To design network programming via network slice to separate network traffic				✓
Vericare-Model [97]	2015	A system to verify that SDN features are stable, reliable, secure and correct	To propose distributed verifiable design for verification network constraints				✓
Machine Verification Model [98]	2013	To cater the system automatic checking tool for SDN infrastructure properties	Mechanism to verifying SDN controller with machine based				✓
VeriCon-Model [99]	2014	To verify the SDN issues correctness with formal method	To design a SDN application for verification				✓

3.5.4.2 Verify real-time policies

In VeriFlow, the authors of [87] investigated the real-time based network information verification, they utilised flow rules interception prior to each network entries. In the VeriFlow model, network with the help of graphs identifies routing table loops and unavailable paths. The main objective is based on real-time invariants verification, in the evaluation, they presented model performance accuracy with less than milliseconds. However, authors of NetPlumber [88], proposed solution based on real-time policy checking that consistently verifies policies based on each network state change compliance, the proposed model is optimised version of previous authors solutions, the major improvement is carried out by utilising Header Space Analysis (HSA) from previous authors [116]. This model performs as computationally increment based on dependencies, however, this model is more robust and fast and effective due to the nature of processing with real-time dependencies analysis.

The authors in [89], also utilise HAS mechanism to develop resolution algorithm in SDN application firewall for error and conflict identification. In SDN switches, it is also possible to bypass firewall policies by insertion of unauthorised flow policies. This approach enables to shift and maintain flow based on the flow space verification and authorising firewall space for misconfigured flow rules, once flows with conflicts rules are identified then deny rules automatically block and refuse each new flow rule entries. This model is deployed with Floodlight firewall application, in which a real-time policy conflict resolution mechanism is depicted as compared to another theoretical model. This solution has a limited ability that it can only manipulate and re-write policies related to firewall related issues.

In the current research, FlowGuard authors [90] [91] also developed a mechanism for verifying network flow path spaces in order to identify firewall policies conflicts during the event of network update. Addition to this, FLOWGuard also provides an effective automatic real-time mechanism to resolve firewall conflicts by rejecting policy updates. In previous work, this function was achieved by utilising five different conflict resolution strategies such as flow rejection, breaking dependency, rejecting updates, removing flows and packet blocking. Moreover, these solutions rely on real-time processing that supports self adoption of policy conflict resolution techniques for potential network development. However, there is more demand that needs to be focused on justifying gap between real-time live network characteristics and theoretical models.

3.5.4.3 Language-Based issues resolution

The authors of the Frenetic model [117] proposed another policy conflict resolution mechanism, which is based on the northbound APIs. This mechanism is suitable

to programme multiple SDN switches, which are centrally controlled by a central controller. During run time, the proposed model converts flow rules into non-overlapping policies before the time of initiating new flow rules in switches. The authors of [93] designed another flow-based policy mechanism in NOX SDN controller application, this model also supports external authentication enforcement along with some network isolation, to provide access to major control.

Contrast to previous work solutions, the authors in [93], [117] provided controller based verification to support a policy conflict resolution mechanism, which is more likely to work between the application layer and control layer. From the abstract view of low-level data-plane invariants, this model is suitable to re-programme network policies to avoid network conflicts. Although, in current existing solutions, there is an alarming demand to extend these approaches towards distributed controller architecture with relevant issues, considerations of distributed environments and with the resilience approach.

3.5.4.4 Unified network abstraction view

The authors of [94] have depicted the abstracted view of each packet and flow consistency in order to resolve SDN based configuration and instability. Each packet consistency is very feasible to ensure that every packet must be presented in update operation either with the old policy or new policy. The flow consistency can be achieved by a generalisation of each packet consistency. Authors of [92] depicted multiple layered policy management approaches. Both intra-related and inter-related module of flow rules dependencies have been solved on the application layer, similarly intra table dependencies are resolved on the data layer. Addition to this, a wide range of dependencies set can also be resolved by undertaking overlapped flow rules conflicts at different layers.

The proposed conflicts resolution mechanisms have an impact due to larger scalability of applications or wide area network with consistent flow rule updating process. In each of the cases, the controller and its related switch control function process extensively in order to identify the misconfiguration of network states, which causes processing overhead. A feasible alternative solution provided by the authors of [95], which does not compromise network processing performance. Major implementation was based on the architecture of distributed and shared data storage rather than a policy conflict resolution approach. To maintain the consistency of the overall network state, data storage architecture must be refined and maintained.

3.5.4.5 Formal verification approaches

Some of the formal methodologies have been discussed that if SDN based control-plane logic is securely and correctly deployed then most of the controller errors such as logical errors, conflicting applications policies and incorrect implementation for operating environment can be resolved [96], [99]. In the model of Splendid Isolation [96], the authors have proposed the approach to classify traffic isolation programme in network slices. Similarly, in the FlowVisor [69] model, authors already presented the hypervisor-based model to be used as a transparent proxy interface between SDN switches and controller, which also helps the administrator to identify slices within relevant flow spaces. However, it is also limited for providing proof for correctness and security in Splendid Isolation. As authors discussed in [66], FlowVisor is not capable to deploy process of isolation rendering and process of isolation vulnerable. For example, due to modification of packet VLAN ID, an infected controller can easily breach or insert or shift packets to a new network slice. There are some proposed solutions such as [72], [96] that are utilised for resolving these issues.

The authors of the model Verificare [97], developed a tool for the purpose of formal verification. The Verificare model helps to employ modelling specification and OpenFlow verification, correctness in network, convergence and mobility. Moreover, In [98] authors presented systematic detailed OpenFlow based operational model, addition to this, they also proposed Coq proof formalisation assistant by utilising their proposed model. The proposed model also comprises a verified compiler and run-time system, these approaches of SDN are considered as verified entities in the controller. However, authors of Verizon [99] model, also verify the infinite SDN running programmes state in a safe and secure way.

From the existing literature and contribution presented in this section, that vulnerabilities and issues which are related to this topic are widely considered as research interest topic. This area is considered as a highly in demand to develop real-time network detection tools and formal verification approaches. As the development of these modern tools with the help of scalable SDN platform rather than OF related is the being considered future topics of research. These types of development are not only application but these are also capable to program a switch to access flow table as depicted in **Fig. 2**. According to authors [30], the OpenFlow switch is capable to identify itself set of suitable flows for programming when the switch requires bootstrapping. In the case of some application, misconfigured the flows then overall switch functionalities could lead to massive vulnerabilities. Addition to this, more issues can also arise, when a network administrator enables the writing privilege access to Secure Shell (SSH) inside the switch table.

The most of configuration issues directly impact on SDN security, For example,

bootstrapping extension towards SDN based network and components life cycle. The adoption of new network applications brings changes such as new users, newly integrated devices etc. It is very feasible for potential network and data security that most of the technical methodologies must have security and maintainability policies. In SDN context, it is more challenging rather than the legacy network, due to the fact that SDN application can easily produce more updates towards an open innovation approach.

Table 3.6 depicts the summary of all SDN configuration issues.

3.5.5 Different Security Solutions to SDN system Level

Table 3.6 depicts the summary of proposed solutions for resolving the major SDN based system configuration issues. This literature is categorised into different categories as presented in this section, these all categories as some of the latest work have been discussed in this section.

For the purpose of securely deploying SDN infrastructure, the researchers of [100] have published significant work to deal with these issues. In this model, a network debugger prototype is proposed, which enables potential SDN application developers to redesign and reconstruct events-chain that is a very useful approach for finding and fixing the root of these issues. This is suitable for both network requirement auditing and network debugging.

Moreover, authors of [101] developed OF-HIP model, which is created with the collaboration of Host Identity Protocol (HIP) [118] and OpenFlow approaches. Authors have utilised IPsec Encapsulation Security Payload (ESP) feature for advanced security in the model. The major aim of OF-HIP model is to deploy robust secured mobility via OpenFlow protocol to resolve the issues which are caused by IP changes in the current platform. For example, an active session of SSL/TLS teardown deviated flow processes and issues of mutual authentication. OF-HIPS model comprises global identities for each HIP, that creates namespace based on encryption, this namespace is almost similar to IPv6 address space, such as unique in nature and can not be modified with mobility events. However, OF-HIP allows OpenFlow switches to security to modify the IP addresses via mobility approach between network entities.

The authors of [102] proposed another solution with the extension of OF-HIP model, in which they considered security threats and various attacks in Software-Defined Mobile Network control channel. The authors designed an effective and secure channel architecture to provide safeguard against IP based attacks. From the evaluation of the overall results, the protection against DoS attacks, Replay attacks, IP spoofing and eavesdropping of intrusion attacks, a secure channel based software

Table 3.7: Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN System Level Issues.

Research Work	Year	Major Goals	Methods	Issues
SDN Interface issues [119]	2019	To lower down the SDN performance monitoring related interface issues	TCP protocols based mitigation	Autonomous network integrity
SDN Debugger [100]	2012	To simplify SDN debugging issues.	SDN based network Debugger	Data modification/Loss
OF-HIPS [101]	2013	Introducing Secure Mobility in OF to optimize the TCP attacks resiliency.	To provide global ID based architecture, to allow OF switches to change IPs.	IPSec and SSL/TLS issues
SDMN Security [102]	2014	Protect SDN security channels.	Provided secure IPSec tunnels and secured gateways.	SDN network connections
Fresco-Model [11]	2013	To simplify the complex SDN security deployment.	Provided, Secure Development Framework.	SDN network connection

defined mobile network can easily be deployed.

The authors in [11] provided an important contribution in which FortNox [82] integrated with OpenFlow Security Application Development Framework, which is robust security enforcing kernel. The major aim of the FRESCO model is to develop the fast and effective security modules, which must be compatible with the OpenFlow based application development, where a reusable module library to detect and mitigate various attacks will be provided.

Most of the solutions for the purpose of SDN system-level security issues are also capable to identify and classify the scalable environments, where SDN application can easily be created such as SDN based clouds, data centres and mobile networks. A more secure and robust security design is also a major concern to protect multiple dynamics networks and cross platforms deployment.

The Table 3.7 presents the summary of the existing solutions for the SDN system-level security issues, this table comprises of a wide range of security solutions ranges from network debugging to flexible and secure mobility approaches.

3.6 SDN Framework to Optimize the Network Security.

From the previous literature surveys, it can be seen that SDN based network architectures are capable to improve network functionalities including security. In this section, we have elaborated the major six security optimising approaches within the SDN networks. Six major security enhancement solutions are depicted in A SDN-oriented DDoS blocking scheme for botnet-based attacks, each solutions categories are also separately discussed in detail. Most of these security solutions more likely utilising multiple SDN characteristics discussed in Section 3.2.1. Although, the authors of most of the existing solutions have demonstrated and evaluated potential security approaches by utilising only OpenFlow protocol on the control data-plane interface. As a result, many researchers have provided future direction to develop a secure and robust application control interface.

3.6.1 Collect Detect and Protect

The process of analysis and collecting data from Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) and Intrusion Prevention Systems (IPS) within the centralised re-programmable network, enable SDN based network more robust and powerhouse of building innovative applications to deal various attacks rather than legacy infrastructure. The authors of [120] have investigated this process of data harvesting for the purpose of security concern. The authors have utilised OpenFlow and sFlow combination to detect and mitigate the network anomalies in SDN context. In the proposed solution, three major modules were created: (i) the Collector, a module to collect the useful switch flow statistics by using sFlow and OpenFlow protocols on the data-layers, (ii) Anomaly Detection, a module to investigate the collected flow statistics to classify anomalies and (iii) Anomaly Mitigation, a module to insert new flow entries and rejecting malicious flow entries to neutralised detected attacks. All modules combination actively work as a feedback control loop for network security. In the results, authors have successfully evaluated detection of DDoS attacks, port-scans and worm propagation. This solution is more likely built on SDN programmability feature and network-wide abstract view of SDN approach [120].

This work detailed illustration is provided with Figure 3.3. The overall model investigation, the controller is utilised to collect network statistics as a separate function which is more related to a specific network.

The authors of [121] have also proposed another flexible and effective feedback control loop approach for network security such as collect, detect and to protect. The proposed model support pro-active network security, which comprises of identifying intrusion detection, analysis of memory content identification and reconfiguration of network policies. The core features of the model are depicted as protect, to sense, to adjust, to collect and counter, all of these features were adopted by SDN programmable and centralised approach.

The authors in [122], depicted a learning-based model such as Learning Intrusion Detection System (L-IDS) solution, in which SDN infrastructure is used to identify and respond to the network malicious activities which are with mobile devices. The switch routing error correctness for end hosts of mobile devices is presented with a learning switch controller. L-IDS approach more likely utilises the SDN architecture with OpenFlow protocol, addition to this IDS logic to manipulate the traffic flow measurement and anomaly detection are also utilised in the central controller. The proposed model feasibly detect and mitigate the various attacks and also provides the support to re-programme network policies with required level.

The authors of [123] also presented a mechanism in OpenFlow to provide protection against traffic overhead. The NetFuse model is based on OF proxy device

Figure 3.3: SDN Security Feedback Control: Collect - Detect - Protect

that manages the OF-control messages, also utilises OF read-state messages for the abstraction of active network flows and resource utilisation. Flow-based aggregation algorithm then applied to classify the flows having overloading behaviour. A group of conditions with aggregate values are defined such as flows volume with specific destination port that may represent the attack. In the final step of the model, suspicious flow is kept limited with adaptive rate limiting approach, which is based on mechanism of toxin-antitoxin, rate-limiting is manipulated based on overloading response of flows.

The authors of OrchSec [124] proposed an orchestrator-based model to work with the SDN control function and network monitoring to create a security application. The SDN based security application deficiencies were identified, such as the impact of performance overhead on SDN controller and single point failure with a single SDN controller. The proposed model utilises multiple controller instances, which monitors packet level of networks with sFlow, and also create applications for the purpose of communicating northbound API (application-control interface), instead of working inside the controller. The authors have evaluated the model functionalities with

detection and mitigation demonstration against DNS amplification attacks.

The feedback control loop concept is also utilised with the extension of Cognition [125] to apply cognitive SDN functions on the application plane of SDN. To optimise the network security, predefined set of open-source controller features are utilised such as global network view, network switch states etc. are considered as non-cognitive solutions. The authors in Cognition also optimised security level by using non-cognitive functions with multi-objective optimisation. The environmental changes can affect the optimisation (e.g. intrusion or attacks), change of network configuration, user changes and traffic changes. The major aim of the cognitive model is to utilise the learning based approaches to identify potential threats and also enables the network to mitigate these potential threats. The proposed model is carried with the theoretical proposal, however, experimental evaluation is defined as future work, which is mainly focusing on potential research directions.

In SDN, a large number of traffic monitoring and collection models are discussed with OpenFlow, most of these models works with Collect and Detect phases of feedback loop control mechanism [48], [126]. The OpenWacth model authors [126] proposed a model based on a prediction algorithm, in which flow granularity measurement can be maintained flexibly. In the model of FleXam [125], the authors provided a sampling mechanism with the help of OpenFlow, so that specific packet level can be manipulated by application or controller. The OpenSketch [75] model is based on software-defined traffic measurement architecture, which uses sketches (compact packet structure which stores the summary of packet states) in order to collect data in a very robust way.

The authors of [31] evaluated a hierarchical based heavy hitter algorithm, which helps to identify large traffic flows. Some proposed solutions potentially can easily identify compatibility to adopt the security applications, these are also capable to be used wider context. Most of the solutions presented in this section have a significant impact on developing network security in SDN context. With the help of existing development and Cognition SDN, flow space can be utilised to predict proactive network security functions.

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Table 3.8: Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for Collect, Detect, Protect in SDN Network

Proposed Model	Year	Major Goals	Methods	Detection Accuracy	Mitigation	Traffic Analysis
Combining OpenFlow with sFlow [127]	2014	To lower down the control-plane overhead to detect DoS via OF flow collection	Sampling-based flow Collection for Anomaly Detection, Mitigation SDN model for IDS and IPS	✓		✓
Active Security-Model [121]	2013	Protect SDN networks by utilising robust and programmable security platform	To provide integrated security features by utilising network feedback control	✓		✓
L-IDS-Model [122]	2013	Providing a robust IDS system, especially designed for embedded mobile devices platform	To reconfigure network and to detect traffic anomalies by using SDN features	✓		✓
NetFuse-Model [123]	2013	To lower down the network and memory overhead inside data centre	Device to detect aggregate OF-flow overload statistic	✓	✓	✓
OrchSec-Model [124]	2014	To fix security issues inside existing network applications	Provides an SDN orchestrator platform to support security application development	✓		✓
Cognition-Model 10.1007/978-3-319-07494-8“6	2014	To optimise the SDN security policies with cognitive functions inside application plane	Application-plane cognitive model utilised with optimisation of robust objective features	✓	✓	✓

of the network. The authors in [123] have utilised rate-limiting instead of network reconfiguration. Similarly, authors of [124], [125] provided applications by improving these features.

3.6.2 Traffic Analysis Attacks Detection and Prevention

In SDN, a potential and unique security optimisation such as detecting specific attacks and resonance prevention was most familiar concerns in SDN as initial security solutions [128]. The resonance has the capability to provide effective control access within network devices, which are based on high-level security policies, most of these high-level security solution policies are designed with traffic analysis of distributed network monitoring devices and programmable SDN switches (updating-rules). The proposed system is developed for providing a safeguard against enterprise security attacks.

The authors in AVANT GUARD [11] proposed a mechanism to communication bottleneck within SDN data-plane by utilising migration tool with flow request limitation towards control-plane. Addition to the migration tool approach, authors of [38] also proposed an actuating triggering approach, which verifies the defined traffic conditions against local packet and flows information, a major focus of actuator was to determine the most appropriate action. Total two options were depicted as an action that enables control-plane to identify either condition have been met or enable the control-plane to install new flow rules in the specific flow table. In the security term, the flow statistics could be individual host flow rate and trigger could be assumed when that flow rate exceeded from defined threshold limit. The AVANT GUARD is presented to protect saturated network attacks, scanning attacks, and malicious intrusions activities. The proposed model only considered TCP flows for evaluations of network security.

Table 3.9: Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for SDN Traffic Analysis Attacks Detection and Prevention.

Proposed Model	Year	Major Goals	Methods	Detection Accuracy	Mitigation	Traffic Analysis
Resonance-model [128]	2009	Method to improve the attack detection response in enterprise level network	Flexible access control system for catering safeguard against enterprise network attacks	✓	✓	✓
AVANT-GUARD Model [11]	2013	Safeguard against DoS attacks in Control-plane for detection and responding flow changes	To migrate the connections for lower down data interaction between flows and data control-plane	✓	✓	✓
Pedigree-model [129]	2009	Providing safety for enterprise networks against network data ex filtration and malware attacks	Provide traffic based VLAN tagging functionality to track flows and filtration policies	✓	✓	✓
OF-RHM-model [130]	2012	Consistently changes the hosts IP addresses for attackers can not reach target machine	Random Host Mutation (RHM) utilised for translating virtual IP to real IP	✓	✓	✓
SDN-MTD-model [131]	2014	To deny the network reconnaissance service discovery and OS fingerprints	SDN based Moving Target Defense (MTD) model for application protection	✓	✓	✓
NICE-NIDS [132]	2013	To deny vulnerability of virtual machines in cloud based network	Network based IDS system, to provide countermeasures and selection approach	✓	✓	✓
ShortFlow-model [133]	2013	To overcome the latency, accuracy and scaleability issues for IPS system	Provide the OF based IPS system	✓	✓	✓
SDN-IPS [134]	2014	To cater the robust IPS mechanism to reconfigure cloud based network policies	Provide the SDN based IPS system	✓	✓	✓
Scalable-IDS [135]	2014	To present the flexible IDS model to deal the larger network traffic in network	A flexible and scalable IDS model with traffic sampling features	✓	✓	✓
Anomaly Detection-revisiting [136]	2011	To identify and detect the home/office network security issues with SDN features	To propose an anomaly detection algorithm with NOX SDN controller	✓	✓	✓
Fuzzy Logic-Security Management [137]	2014	To detect and protect network malicious attacks with SDN programmable features	An SDN based management system for security based on fuzzy logic	✓	✓	✓

The communication of switch to the controller in SDN was exploited in the studies of Pedigree system [129]. Tagstreams helps to initiate every connection which is sent toward the controller, the controller checks each tag with an identifier to identify the secret data or malware. If such tag is identified, the controller inserts a new flow rule at the switch in order to limit or block the associated tagstreams. However Pedigree is capable to stop the malware spread (such as polymorphic worms) and also provides an attack prevention escalation privilege mechanism. However, the proposed solution is not fully scalable with each tagstream sent over control-plane. As most of the intruders utilise various modern approaches to identify network vulnerabilities . First of all, attackers try to identify the IP address of the target network. Moreover, the authors of [130] presented an OpenFlow Random Host Mutation (OF-RHM) approach, which helps to mitigate the address discovery. An OpenFlow protocol is utilised to create virtual IP addresses pool for rendering network hosts, which helps to hide real physical IP address from external access, which is capable to present potential mechanism of security such as moving target defence, in this approach the real IP addresses are unchanged in internal networks but these IP addresses are virtually changed in every regular interval of external connection. To support the OF-RHM model a flow table size is required to increase the network session counter, which is responsible for the session duration, a most challenging task for OF-RHM model development in a large network. The authors of DCPortal [138] designed a traffic isolation mechanism to isolate virtual network especially in virtualised data centres, they utilised packet re-writing header to encapsulate and hide the real source and destination network information. In this approach one virtual machine (VM) tenant traffic cannot be shared with other VM tenant traffic.

The authors of SDN-MTD, investigated the usage of SDN based features to protect network-based moving target defence (MTD). SDN comprises of various initial attacks or exploits such as reconnaissance, network mapping, identification of service discovery and operating system, and vulnerability detection. In the proposed model, the SDN flexible and programmable feature helps to delay and confuse the intruders. For example, to provide a safeguard against network mapping, open network ports. This requires more investigation to the attacker to reach its target due to an increment of cost in attacks, Nmap tool [139] is utilised for attack cost measurement for scanning the SDN-MTD security implementation, which is created with Cisco's One Platform Kit (onePK) [140]. In the proposed model of SDN-MTD, attacks utilise more packets and time, due to network overhead, onePK network filters the controller to classify malicious and benign activities.

The authors in NICE-NIDS [132] proposed a framework to detect intrusions in the virtual network. However, utilising VM machines in cloud security environment can result in various vulnerabilities, which are more concerned with shared stor-

age computing and resources, and cloud-based software installation. The proposed model utilises intrusion detection agents to monitor and analyse network statistics with the help of OpenFlow enabled switches. During the event of suspicious activity detection, malicious VM can be transferred to quarantine vault, then set of potential security countermeasures (such as traffic isolation, port block etc.) are applied to protect these VMs. With SDN feasible characteristics, NICE-NIDS can be dynamically reconfigured and designed so that it could be compatible to work with legacy networks.

Similarly, authors of SnortFlow [133], proposed combined detection solution, in which OpenFlow based configuration are combined with the Snort [141] detection capabilities. In the proposed solution, SnortFlow server captures various packets from agents which are installed on various server points, each agent is also capable to evaluate network security and creates triggers for controllers based on that information controller re-configures the network devices. The model of SnortFlow is based on intrusion prevention system (IPS), where IPS is deployed in the cloud network created with Xen-server. Although, this model only utilises the Snort integration with OpenFlow to detect intrusion but only fully IPS approach. Similarly, the authors of SDNIPS [134] also proposed a method to improve the ability of SDNIPS as compared to legacy IPS implementation. This approach utilises the location of the detection engine at Dom0 interface of SDNIPS model, which directly access to all network tenants to lower down the processing time. IPS network reconfiguration is also evaluated with the help of packet drop and packet redirection to a security appliance.

The authors of [135] proposed another similar proposal for integrating IDS with SDN. The authors of [142] used Suricata as an IDS with the help of a simple sample rate adjustment algorithm for the purpose of optimising IDS architecture scalability. Moreover, authors [102] also utilised SDN in Small Office/Home Office environment for intrusion detection. Four Traffic anomaly detection algorithms are also utilised by the authors [143] with SDN NOX and OpenFlow architecture. These anomaly detection approaches are capable to improve detection capabilities and also able to work with existing other home network applications For example , Access-Control and Quality of Service (QoS). This exploits the standardised SDN programmable feature to cater a robust and effective anomaly detection service, this is only compatible with end-users rather than traditional network core.

Another solution of IDS/IPS was also proposed by authors [137] with the help of fuzzy logic. Authors of [136] utilised the potential SDN characteristics for implementing fast and effective anomaly detection algorithm. The main purpose of utilising fuzzy logic is to lower down the computational process. This section comprises a range of IDS and IPS solution, which specially deals with various network intru-

sions and attacks. SDN, programmability and global monitoring facility help these solutions to effectively detect the various attacks, majority of cases deep analysis of investigation or optimisation is also mandatory to achieve the better performance in larger scale SDN architectures.

Table 3.9 presents a summary of the proposed solution with regard to Traffic Analysis Attacks Detection and Prevention. Most of the solutions based on such as flexible access control to network traffic alarms, filtration processes, and IPS security mechanism to deal with the security issues that arise within the small office/home or enterprises.

3.6.3 Protection against DDoS/DoS Attacks

In Section III, a large number of Denial of Service attack was investigated as major SDN security issues. Moreover, SDN comprises a large solution range that utilises traffic analysis and global traffic view of the controller and programmable feature of data-plane, major focus is concerned to provide DDoS/DoS detection solution. The authors of [144] proposed Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) detection solution, in which an OpenFlow based switches data is monitored with NOX SDN controller with consistent intervals for data acquisition (For example. as average packets per flow, average bytes per flow etc). Later in this proposed solution, authors utilised an artificial neural network Self Organising Maps (SOM) for classifying malicious and benign traffic mainly abnormal traffic-flows. The authors of [145] depicted the solution of content-oriented networking architecture (CONA), where an OpenFlow (OF) agent is utilised as a communication bridge between server and host contents request, OpenFlow agent, creates communication with SDN controller, both sided contents request messages are mandatory to be analysed filtered and intercepted before mitigating DDoS attacks in the proposed model. When the server receives the exceeded content requests more than defined level, then it is considered as a DDoS attack. During this, the controller receives alerts of DDoS identification and apply rate-limiting message to infected CONA agents, this helps to lower down the attack propagation in SDN. In the result evaluation of the proposed model, the time taken by the rate-limiting approach to deal with the DDoS attacks has not been considered.

In [146], a very simple DDoS defending methodology is presented. Moreover, authors [147] have utilised the Locator/ID separation protocol (LISP) mechanism for classifying both authorised and unauthorised malicious traffic sources. The LISP model isolates the identifier and locator of hosts, this separation enables the locator to be changed during nodes migration, whereas, identifier stays unchanged. After this, the proposed model becomes capable to detect DDoS attacks by traffic analysis.

Table 3.10: Summary of Proposed Existing Solution for DDoS attacks in SDN

Research Work	Year	Major Goals	Methods	Detection	Mitigation	Analysis
DDoS Detection Algorithm [149]	2019	Extreme gradient algorithm utilised DDoS traffic with low false-alerts	Machine learning model	✓		
DDoS Detection [150]	2017	Multi vector DDoS analysis and Detection System	Deep learning approach	✓		✓
Lightweight DDoS [144]	2010	To detect DDoS attacks	Self Organizing Map, to classify the normal and benign traffic.	✓	✓	
Conetnt Oriented Network Architecture-CONA [145]	2010	To detect and react DDoS via Conetnt Oriented Network.	To analyse content requests to classify the DDoS.	✓	✓	✓
DDoS-Defender [146]	2010	To detect and react DDoS	To detect and block DDoS via OF and LISP method.		✓	
DDoS-Blocker Model [148]	2014	To lowerdown the issues of blocking and detecting DDoS.	A SDN based managed network to block the DDoS.		✓	✓

If the controller receives the exceeded traffic volume than the predefined threshold, then the controller identifies as malicious packets and drop these packets.

Most of the sophisticated DDoS attacks affect the targeted service providers with larger compromised host bots, which sends the very limited small legitimate traffic volume, which creates the vulnerability for potential attackers to easily break existing security approaches. Moreover, the authors of [148] significantly provided the DDoS Blocking application (DBA) to lower down the botnet based SDN attacks. The DBA model is designed to run in the SDN controller, to monitors the network flows. Once DDoS traffic is classified then legitimate traffic is migrated to server new IP address where bots are already blocked. The mechanism to block the DDoS mainly relies on bots inability for redirecting server traffic, which requires more computational resources for machine decoding format. As discussed before that SDN characteristics are capable to deploy an effective network that can deal with DoS protection, addition to this, a DoS defence level applications can also be customised.

SDN has also anticipated security defence development based on L4-7. Table 3.10 presents the existing summary of the proposed solution for DDoS/DoS security solutions. Most of the cases use traffic statics for detecting DDoS attacks, each case is deployed with the specific configuration according to network infrastructure.

3.6.4 Machine Learning based DDoS protection

Recently, ML-based detection techniques as depicted in Table 3.11 are exponentially growing in SDN infrastructures, such as authors in [150] proposed a semi-supervised one class-based Support Vector Machine (SVM) to classify anomalies, here the small quantity of malicious traffic is utilised as compared to normal traffic. This model is feasibly capable to detect outliers from the initial background traffic phase, this helps to easily manipulate all traffic characteristics with details. The authors have used the Stacked Auto Encoder (SAE) algorithm to train datasets, as this is a very

Table 3.11: Summary of Proposed Machine Learning Solutions for DDoS attacks in SDN

Research Work	Year	Major Goals	Methods	Detection	Mitigation	Analysis
Xtreme-Gradient algorithm [149]	2018	Machine learning approach	Xtreme gradient algorithm to detect DDoS attacks	✓		
SAE [150]	2017	Multi-vector DDoS analysis deep learning approach.	Neural network model-SOM	✓		✓
SOM-model [151]	2010	Uses six SDN based traffic features to detect DDoS.	Neural network model-SOM	✓		✓
GIPA model [154]	2016	IDS/IPS based neural network	Artificial neural network	✓	✓	✓

effective method but consume a lot of time to process model iterations for using plenty of data.

Some of other, well-known methodologies have been published to detect DDoS traffic with SDN based architecture such as, self-Organising Maps (SOM), which is machine learning (ML) based approach to detect malicious [151]. This work uses only six features to classify the malicious attack traffic comprises as Average Packet per flow (APf), Average Duration per flow (ADf), Average Byte per flow (ABf) etc, similarly, more authors [152], [153], also utilised different ML-based approaches to classify traffic patterns. In SDN context, most of the DDoS detection solutions are carried out with the collaboration of ML and knowledge-based techniques to identify malicious attack tactics. Generally, ML-based techniques classify attack flows based on specific feature characteristics. ML-based anomaly detection models are mainly suitable for small networks. However, larger network causes heavy traffic flow overhead, which is unmanageable for traffic collection and analysis inside controller [127] Although during the attacking scenario, response time is more important to improve detection performance. Addition to this ML performance is also dependant upon trained datasets and its rich features.

Authors in [155], proposed detection method based on Self Organizing Map (SOM), which is an unsupervised artificial based neural works. SOM is likely trained with plenty of traffic flow features. The proposed work classifies the traffic flows in attacks and non-attack classes with SOM computation process. In previous work, the SOM detection approach is more likely utilized to identify only abnormal class against normal class network traffic, but in [156], researchers have provided some variation with SOM detection approach. SOM modification comprises to detect traffic attack with good detection accuracy, including increment of artificial neurons grid up to ten of thousands, and a grey relational co-efficient method is also adopted with SOM to rectify neurons nodes weighted sum for each vector. All this work classifies the traffic either in normal class or abnormal class, generally utilises KDD-99 dataset for evaluating the results classification. As authors in [157] traffic log file transformation tcpdump application into various connection points, but during the worst case scenario DDoS flooding attacks caused high CPU and process overhead.

Authors of CIPA [154] developed an artificial neural network based collaborative mechanism to detect system intrusions deployed into a virtual network portion. GIPA system divides the total computation power to programmable switches of network substrate. Artificial neural network scatters the over entire switch function such as integrated, IDS/IPS and provides the global network view for distributed attacks.

In [158], the TRW-CB algorithm proposed to identify the abnormal infections on the network hosts. Each attempt connections probability must be set higher for benign traffic than suspicious traffic. TRW-CB algorithm utilises the sequential hypothesis testing such as like-hood ratio test for classification of all interconnected hosts of system, this classification falls either in attacks and non-attacks. TRW-CB algorithm maintains a new connection queue (such as SYNACK) for all interconnected hosts. If any of the connections time out receiving any reply or TCP RST connection, then this algorithm assigns new connection queues and new like-hood ratio to the hosts which enables it to be initiated a new connection. This enables TRW-CB algorithm to declare as an infected entity. Addition to this, when a successful reply is obtained then the like-hood ratio of hosts is reduced, which enables TRW-CB algorithm to declare it as a normal entity. Moreover, when the like-hood ratio reaches a certain level of threshold i.e. n_1 then it is supposed to be declared only infected entities. For the deployment of TRW-CB algorithm in NOX SDN controller, the authors utilise the fact of earlier initiated connections or responses received from hosts, and there is no need to check and manipulate each and every packet within flows. The OpenFlow version 1.0 calculates if there are no packets match in any flow entry in switch then it is propagated to main SDN controller. After successful connection established then switch flows are inserted in the switches to maintain traffic, in the following example authors implementation is provided in details:

1. When internal host A host sends a TCP SYN response to new neighbour hosts B, both hosts do not hold matched packets then these hosts are supposed to be declared and sent these packets to NOX controller.
2. The TRW-CB algorithm instances are also running at NOX controller for the purpose of propagating these packets via switches with no need of inserting new flow entries. Meanwhile, this algorithm also keeps processing normally such as Adding B host to previously host of A by adding only connection request queue to A.
3. Possible responses from B given below:
4. When A host received TCP SYNACK from B host, then switch is again re-

sponsible to propagate all this to NOX controller (where it does not match any data match). Once SYNACK is received then instances of TRW-CB algorithm implement the two flows to that switch, the first flow of switch matches the packet generated by A host to B host. This flow comprises of A host IP address in IP src field and B host IP address in term of IP dst entities. All other fields in this flow are manipulated with network wildcard other than Ether type field. Second flow has some resemblance to first flow but all matched packets are propagated from B host to A host, and each flow of this host imply an action that helps to put forward all matched packets of the relevant port within the switch. Moreover, TRW-CB algorithm utilises it as normal processing such as, to remove connection request from host A queue and then to reduce the A host like-hood ratio.

5. Whenever any connection time out then TRW-CB algorithm is also responsible to continue regular processing (such as special failure connection) without using any switch interactions. In this stage, no other flow need to be deployed.

The TRW-CB detects horizontal port scans, and it is also responsible for internal hosts to send new connection requests continuously towards various external hosts. However, a normal traffic host can initiate various TCP connections with different source ports to the same server. Destination ports could be the same within all requests (such as http server) or it could be unique for all request. Whenever a successful connection to the external host established with the separate flow in the switch then it exponentially increases the size of that flow table, which causes switch processing overhead. This system only utilises two flow for communicating different hosts. When a new connection request to be connected to the same external host, then after a first attempt this request will be forwarded to the line rate of the switch rather than passing it to the controller. However, any new connection from a new external host still needs to be sent towards the controller. This helps TRW-CB algorithm to receive great accuracy by manipulating every packet.

3.6.5 Anomaly/Entropy based DDoS protection

Some authors utilised entropy-based statistical techniques to analyse traffic [159]–[161]. The authors of [162] proposed an entropy-based technique to detect DDoS at POX controller during initial attack stage, this proposed work has a limitation, once the number of hosts increases, then proposed model generates false positive alerts. The computational overhead from the controller is reduced by deploying fast-entropy approach with flow-based model [161]. The authors in [163] proposed a scheduling based method to detect DDoS, where a single processing queue is divided with subsets of k logical queues, each of them belongs to the network switch.

During heavy traffic burst, the SDN controller utilises logical queues to a satisfying scheduling request. The authors of [164] utilises maximum entropy estimation technique for classifying normal traffic distribution to solve home office network security concerns in SDN context. Most of the experiments were deployed with OpenFlow enabled switches with NOX SDN controller, the proposed work mainly focuses on low rate network traffic for research experiments for detection of malicious traffic in a home-based environment. Addition to this, in another work, authors have used entropy methodologies for identification of port-scan attacks and worm propagation [127]. However, an entropy-based anomaly detection solution was proposed by the authors of [159], to detect DDoS attacks in SDN, this work more likely focuses to reduce control-plane workload. The authors have utilised SDN enabled edge switches for this research. Other authors [165] deployed detection model for locating compromised interfaces, which are used by attackers during attack time. Most of anomaly detection model uses fixed threshold values, once incoming statistical features deviate with abnormal conditions, then it is identified as attack traffic.

In [166] authors employed sFlow to gather flow-based data for anomaly detection and mitigation mechanism in SDN. The proposed system comprises a collector, the anomaly detection and anomaly mitigation components. The collector module collects flow-entries or flows packets with OpenFlow and sFlow approaches. Then an entropy-based algorithm was utilized to classify normal traffic and abnormal traffic. When abnormal traffic was detected, then IP address and port number were provided to anomaly mitigation module for mitigation purpose. As sFlow was used for sampling traffic in implementation, the false-positive rate was very high in the attack detection module. In [167], the authors proposed a stateful SDN platform for DDoS defence and to delegate switch local processes. All switches directly manage traffic monitoring for special features such as IP source and destination, port source and destination. This traffic monitoring is achieved via stateful programming, which also reduces the controller overhead. Accumulated results were fed into the entropy-based detection algorithm to detect malicious activities over the controller. This work presented with a very basic and simple design, where extensive level evaluation is not performed.

3.6.5.1 Maximum Entropy Detector

The Maximum Entropy Detector [168] judges normal traffic distribution class with the help of maximum entropy estimation. The traffic class is divided into 2348 packets classes of the training dataset. Here maximum entropy estimation with training dataset is utilised to create a baseline benign distribution for every class. Packets classes are obtained from the two-dimensional matrix. Where the first dimension comprises of four different classes such as TCP, UDP, TCP SYN, TCP

Table 3.12: Summary of Proposed Anomaly/Entropy based DDoS Solutions in SDN

Research Work	Year	Major Goals	Methods	Detection	Mitigation	Analysis
Shanon entropy [162]	2016	To bypass sources attacks	Shanon entropy estimation to detect early-stage DDoS	✓	✓	✓
Maximum entropy [168]	2005	Classify DDoS via normal traffic distribution classes.	Maximum Entropy Detector	✓		✓
Rate-limiting [169]	2003	Detect attacks in very short time.	Anomaly detection	✓		✓
SPRT method [165]	2016	To classify high rate DDoS traffic	Sequential Probability Ratio Test-SPRT	✓	✓	✓
Flow-based Entropy [127]	2014	To analyse and classify DDoS portscan, and worm propagation	Entropy-based detection via flow traffic	✓	✓	✓
NETAD Model [170]	2010	To filter traffic with common protocols information.	Anomaly detection via protocols	✓		✓

RST. The second dimension creates a subset for each four mentioned classes and splits it into around 587 sub classes which are more likely dependent upon destination port numbers. The packet class distribution is calculated based on the real-time slot (such as t time seconds) then used to be compared with the information of baseline distribution by divergence measure of Kullback -Leibler (KL) technique. When any KL packet class exceeds the limit beyond to threshold of n_k above than h times of last W windows, then an alarm is triggered out. Unlike, TRW-CB algorithm and Rate-Limiting, the Maximum Entropy more likely based on to investigate each and very packets for creating a packet class distribution with every t seconds of time. The main objective is to divert all packets to algorithm instances running over the NOX controller. On the other hand, this technique could result in a performance decrease of OpenFlow protocol. Once packets arrived to switch, id do not match any flow entity then it is forwarded to SDN controller in which deployed algorithm take decision based on the following actions of packet types:

1. When TCP SYN and RST packets arrived then distribution window increases relevant packet class counting then the packet is prepared to put forward via switch without implying any new flows.
2. If TCP SYNACK packet is reached then two different flows for managing each flow in unique direction is deployed. Addition to this, packets iare also forwarded via that switch. These flows comprise of six tuple values such as Ether type, src IP, dst IP, IP proto, src port, dst port, and other features are classified based on network wildcard.
3. Once switch receives UDP packets then two more flows similar to SYNACK feature is utilized then the counting for relevant UDP class is updated.

As discussed earlier, the Maximum Entropy utilizes every packet inspection for creating distributions classes. This algorithm more likely work to TCP SYN and TCP RST classes with OpenFlow of version 1.0.

3.6.5.2 Rate-Limiting

The Rate-Limiting [169], is another popular approach which utilises a technique that when any malicious activity propagates to different machines in the very short time slot, similarly an uninfected machine establishes connection attempts with a lower rate and it is initiated more repeatedly into mostly visited machines. After the arrival of the new connection, it is being verified with the list of connected hosts known as (working set). If any request is presented in a working set of hosts then, it is also propagated forward with normal method, otherwise, it is put inside delay-queue, which is another queue of data structure. After every d seconds, the connection is a time-out from the delay queue and then sent to be processed forward. If delay queue size increases more than T threshold value then an alarm is triggered. The authors utilise the same technique of CRW-CB algorithm for the deployment of Rate-Limiting into NOX controller. Two separate pair of working set and delay queue is integrated into internal hosts, the Rate-Limiting uses the following rules for packet manipulation:

1. If a remote host resides in the working set and new connection request connection arrives, then two flow directions work between the remote host and internal host. The Rate-Limiting is also a host based anomaly detection technique similar to CRW-CB algorithm. It does not use any specific port traffic in the network, therefore most of its flows are identical other than src IP, and dst IP. Ether type is used with a network wildcard mask.
2. If the remote host is not in working set and meantime new connection request arrives then the new delay queue is created to ensure the no other flows implemented into switches.
3. After every d seconds, every new connection request is jumped from the delay queue to the working set. The connection request is forwarded via switch without interfering any flows.
4. When a switch receives positive connection reply such as TCP SYNACK, then it can install two different flows either in direction for handling traffic or connection flows.

3.6.5.3 NETAD

NETAD [170] technique utilizes filtered traffic which is based on rules as a model subset of common protocols. The filter in this methodology reduces unnecessary traffic, only first few request connection packets are considered sufficient for detection traffic anomaly. Which consisting on all non IP packets, TCP packets beyond

100 bytes limit with any port numbers, protocol combination, which is received more than 16 in one minute only. NETAD is also capable to calculate the score of the packet with respect to time and frequency of each packet bytes. Each rare and novel values in packet header receive a high score, and then threshold value is applied to all packets field for ensuring anomalies detection inside all packets. Authors implemented NETAD in NOX controller with the ability of its filtration technique. The filtering rule utilizes only the first few packets in this algorithm. The main aim of this deployment more likely based on passing all network traffic thoroughly controller until any one of them qualify any single filtration rule. Once filtering rule is matched then algorithm installs new flows into switches to propagate all traffic without interfering controller. Moreover, if the algorithm identifies that it cannot accept any TCP packets beyond 100 bytes, then two separate flows are being adopted to divert these sequences of packets with over 100 bytes limit. Each flow comprises six tuple values such as Ether type, src IP, dst IP, proto IP, src port, and dst port. Similar to Maximum Entropy detector each flow contains some specific field values because this algorithm only uses the first few connection packets for all new connection.

Despite huge research work in OpenFlow (OF) with a combination of routing, traffic monitoring, load-balancing, and so on. Intrusion detection was not used. The earlier research was more likely based on flow based detection methodologies, the flow-based intrusion detection was proposed by [144]. In which OF is utilized to support the network devices forwarding plane and to collect up their network statistics, without interfering any manipulation of flow table size features, or control-plane overload. However, this work aims to focus to detect Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) malicious attacks on devices data-plane. Addition to this, overall performance analysis of this work is limited comparatively to other relevant work of IDS based algorithm. Traffic anomalies within data-plane with respect to OF protocol is not addressed properly. In [57], combining intrusion detection system (IDS) with SDN environment enables to create secure and valuable SDN platform. The main purpose of the IDS system is to trigger alarms for malicious activities, and unauthorised attempts. The system basically detects malicious activities and attacks, either in host based IDS or network based IDS. The IDS system falls into two categories, mainly host based IDS (HIDS) and network based IDS (NIDS). HIDS is installed on workstations and to monitor network traffic individually. It triggers alarms on each host rather than the entire network. It has the ability to notify event of potential attacks to authorized user or administrator. NIDS gets access to network traffic with the help of hub, network tap, and preconfigured switch for mirroring traffic to a specific port.

The authors in [10] identified seven major security threats in SDN, which are

spoofed traffic flow, attacks on switches vulnerability, attacks on the communication of control-plane, attacks on controller vulnerability, lack of trusted mechanism between controller and management applications, attacks on vulnerable administrative machines, and lack of trusted resources for mitigation and forensics. The Distributed Denial of Services (DDoS) is the most current security issue that is hardest to identify with full details. A DDoS attack can easily result in services malfunctioning because it is simple to launch and very complex to mitigate and trace. In December 2016, a DDoS attack resulted in massive traffic congestion against Sony PlayStation during holidays worldwide. Anomaly detection does not follow whole data entities, it only searches entities by exposing its various patterns. The anomaly detection technique detects data which is unknown deviated entities within the dataset, such as, outliers, contaminants based on the detection method. Flow based is another popular technique that minimizes network workload during IDS process manipulation. Network switches and routers collect flow information to the relevant server during each interval of flow based technique. This technique is widely used in a small or larger network and capable to detect insider and outsider attacks [112].

Flow-based intrusion detection is widely studied in recent research. In [171] the authors propose an anomaly detection which comprises on Multi-Layer Perception and Gravitation Search Algorithm. The system achieved high accuracy rate with benign and malicious traffic classification. In [136] authors proposed a single-class Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm in NIDS, The false alarm rate was very low from results analysis. However, the NIDS system was trained with only malicious class data, and normal data class was not utilised. In [151] authors use very basic home network router with programming capabilities to detect security issues in Small Office/ Home Office (SOHO) network. Four popular network traffic anomaly detection algorithms such as (threshold random walk with credit based rate-limiting (TRW-CB algorithm), rate-limiting, maximum- entropy-detector and NETAD are implemented in SDN based switches using NOX SDN controller. Overall, the malicious detection rate was more accurate within the SOHO network, but it cannot detect feasible detection rate in a reasonable big ISP (Internet Service Provider). However, anomaly detection approach only works with dedicated lines, and cannot be performed to any new unusual activities.

In [172], the authors proposed a lightweight method to detect DDoS attacks based on traffic flow features is presented with six tuples of feature extraction such as Average of Packet per flow (APf), Average of Bytes per flow (ABf), Average of Duration per flow (ADf), Percentage of Pair flows (PPf), Growth of Single flow (GSf), and Growth of Different Ports (GDP). Moreover, flow streams in OpenFlow due to the fact of hard_timeout is capable to communicate with two hosts in a single flow. Flow is divided into sub components if there exists a larger connection in time

context. Therefore all six features of this work are modified to be used in the form of merging 30-minutes for identical flows.

The authors of [120] utilised Self-Organizing Maps (SOM), a flow-based method. The major aim was to detect DDoS flooding attacks inside kernel based modular detection engine. On the basis of traffic features, detection engine classified in benign traffic and malicious traffic entries. The proposed work can only perform with table flow and cannot be extended to detect DDoS attacks in heavily traffic flow streams inside switches. The authors of [173] proposed a DDoS blocking application (DBA) in SDN, which effectively blocks DDoS attacks. This proposed model collaboratively works with the server to detect attacks. The purpose of demonstrating the prototype was to detect HTTP flooding attack. The authors provided a system to detect DDoS attacks in the controller by entropy calculation. Implementation depends only on the entropy threshold value to detect an attack, which is selected after performing several experiments. The proposed approach may not be reliable due to threshold values variation in different scenarios. In [162] the authors discussed the threshold risk detection approach for DDoS attacks. The fuzzy inference system (FIS) deployed on both states of good traffic and bad traffic of real time network data. Only three basic features were obtained in the model to detect an attack having risk factors: Distribution of Inter-arrival Time, Distribution of Packet quantity per flow and Flow quantity to a server. The Table 3.12 depicts the summary of proposed Anomaly/Entropy based DDoS solutions in SDN.

3.7 Discussion

OpenFlow-based SDN is a new infrastructure compared with conventional networks, to support virtualization, that separates the control plane from the forwarding plane. It has also been a major priority for attackers with exponential growth and growing acceptance. At the SDN switch level, controller uses various southbound APIs and protocols to communicate with the elements of the network, which comprises of OpenFlow, one of the widely adopted and used protocol. Other protocols are known as Open vSwitch Database Management Protocol (OVSDB), Path Computation Element Communication Protocol (PCEP), Interface to the Routing System (I2RS). Each of the SDN based protocols has its mechanisms to provide the safeguard to ensure the communication between the elements of the network. However, most of the protocols are newly developed, which can leave a hole for various vulnerabilities during deployment. For example, an attacker can easily eavesdrop on SDN based flows to check which flows are in use and which network traffic is allowed. Finally, the attackers will compromise and will attempt to eavesdrop between the network elements and the controller on the southbound channel. The information which is

sniffed during the intrusion, may be helpful to repeat attack or for identification.

At the SDN controller level, a large number of specific attacks are established in practice. For example, controllers normally run on certain Linux operating systems, where the vulnerabilities of that OS can cause a controller vulnerability. Northbound APIs are numerous but most of them are not standardized. Once attackers utilize the weak northbound API, then the attacker can get complete control over the network of OpenFlow controllers via, man-in-the-middle attacks or network intrusions. In this case, intruders will build their own SDN rules and take full control of the SDN system accordingly. Besides, OpenFlow controllers interact with high-level applications, where attackers will trick the controller using malicious applications.

In Tables 3.1 and Table 3.2, we have described the various categories of SDN security research. In Table 3.1, we presented the detailed security analysis according to OpenFlow and vulnerabilities, also based on OF-based security deployment. Each table represents the SDN based security issues and solutions according to control-plane and data-plane layers. In addition to this, this chapter also addresses whether SDN introduces security vulnerabilities or provides state of art solutions as the safeguard against attacks. This research work addresses in the term of security issues and solutions, depicted in (Section IV and Table 3.2 and security enhancements, depicted in (Section V and Table 3.2, Table 3.3, Table 3.4, Table 3.5, Table 3.6.

From overall literature surveys, it can be concluded that SDN is capable to provide the feasible security solution, however, SDN also leads some of the open challenges, which are also presented in this Section.

3.8 Recommended Best Practices

Figure 3.4 presents the best recommendation practices that must be considered to deploy the SDN based infrastructure with modern and state of the art requirements, most of the recommended list of security solutions are extensively evaluated and justified from the existing surveys of SDN based deployment.

3.8.1 Mutual Authentication:

Most of the SDN elements must be authenticated throughout fundamental communication channels between data-planes and control-planes. These communicating entities must be deployed with active trust aware applications such as (IPSec tunnels, SSL/TLS access, and blockchain) in order to avoid the suspicious and insecure network resources access. This could be feasibly helpful to deny or limit most data manipulation attacks, SDN based implementation elements impersonation.

Figure 3.4: Recommended Best Practices in SDN

3.8.2 Control Plane Slicing

With the help of slicing the network resources, we can easily create the partition, also can allocate these resources to potential users for the purpose of sharing the infrastructure. Based on the security perspective, this mechanism helps to isolate the SDN environment and provide the safeguard against the unauthorized access, data manipulations and data leakages as well. Resources isolation can also be utilised to provide the guaranteed dedicated allocation towards various individual tenants of a big network.

3.8.3 Applications Containerization

In order to access the various implemented controller elements from network application, most of the network applications must be compiled either with controller code with static APIs or compiled as flexible and dynamic such as Open Daylight (ODL) controller-based applications provide the dynamic environment to easily create and share a larger information between data planes as third parties applications

via remote access towards controller.

In order to limit the behaviour of malicious applications, it is important to cater the containerized application, which can feasibly authenticate the applications during the deployment process. In addition to this, it can provide the effective access of infrastructure so that each of the application resources can be isolated and limited based on the access. This facility enables third-party applications towards infrastructure with secure access. Although, the aforementioned malicious activities of previous sections can be avoided by utilising these best practices in SDN context.

3.8.3.1 Snort-IDS/Snort IPS based Logging and Forensics

Most of the network services and applications, which are used to monitor, and capture data are mainly based logging critical information of such network, such data information helps to troubleshoot and debug the infrastructure in an effective way. In Section 3.5 of the literature, network events recording specific data significantly helpful to create and improve the network security operations for various infrastructure.

3.9 Future Directions

SDN is an innovative architecture that fits the high-bandwidth, interactive design of today's applications. It will help various organizations to speed up the implementation of applications and delivery, which helps to cut IT costs dramatically through policy-enabled workflow automation. This also supports cloud systems by offering automatic, on-demand application deployment, and on-scale mobility (Cisco: Software Dened Networking, SDN). Further work will be undertaken to provide the safeguard for the switches, controllers, and communication channel via the potential architecture of OpenFlow-based SDN.

3.9.1 SDN OpenFlow switches

Further research work will be conducted at the switch-level for the safety of flows and specific switch vulnerabilities. Based on our aforementioned analyses, intruders can easily target flows, flow rules, and flow tables in different ways. Such as an intruder can use network elements such as switches, servers and personal computers to launch a DoS attack on OpenFlow switches [48]. Intrusion detection systems can be deployed as the first security line to secure the OpenFlow switches, Furthermore, security policies can be explicitly implemented with traffic flows under SDN. On the other hand, followed by vulnerabilities in switching, attackers will quickly breach the security of the whole network. Once the SDN switch is seized, it may be used

to drop or slow down network packets, clone, and deviate network traffic (e.g., data theft), this may be used to inject traffic or to flood controller or adjacent switches with fake requests. Besides, SDN based monitoring systems are useful to detect irregular activities of network devices and can help to rapidly recognize such malicious activities.

3.9.2 SDN OpenFlow controller

The controller is a vital item in SDN-based OpenFlow, more work is demanded on access control and policy enforcement to protect against multiple intrusions. DDoS/DoS attacks comprise a major threat to the controller, as it is the entity that dictates the behavior of the network. If an attacker compromises the control plane, it can accumulate enough power to conduct DDoS attacks on other elements and enable data leakage in normal flows of traffic. Setting up trust models with multiple certification authorities as a defense is a promising solution to reduce unauthorized linkages. Additionally, to protect the controller interface, the use of complex, automatic, and guaranteed system interaction processes can be considered. By utilizing dynamic address allocation will help to detect malicious entities easily and reduce illegal traffic. Additionally, attackers can utilize top-level malicious applications to compromise the controller and trigger infectious configuration to the underlying infrastructure. Autonomous trust management can be used to protect against such malicious. Moreover, It is necessary to protect all critical elements within the controller and apply policy compliance, or to restrict what interfaces an application can utilize and what rules it can define for network programming.

3.9.3 SDN OpenFlow channel

The SDN based OpenFlow channel is a very important element, which helps to communicate controller and switches. Indeed, most channel-level enhancements and protections can benefit both the controller and the switches. More studies are anticipated in the literature to explore how to build a safe and clean medium of the communication channel. Ensuring TLS in both switches and controllers as an easy and effective approach, while on network providers this will add extra hardware costs. Another approach to secure plaintext communication is by using auto-generated keys and the trust-of-first-use mechanism that operates in the same approach known as SSH. This can allow a network operator to test the thumbprint of the public key of each system when a switch is attached to a controller for the first time [13]. This involves creating a more reliable security system between the controller and the switches to protect against man-in-the-middle attacks. Furthermore, it can lower down the malicious behavior window to a small-time frame between the connection

of the switch to the network and the first connection to the controller.

3.9.4 Conclusion

Followed by the detailed surveys, we can identify and analyse a large number of security issues related to SDN based security vulnerabilities and SDN based security enhancement. As in Section 3.3, Data Leakage and Data Modification both of these issues have not been extensively considered in the above literature, there is an alarming needs to tackle out these issues. In addition to this, before secure SDN deployment, there is a demand to identify and to resolve the unauthorized controller/application access and DDoS attack safeguard mechanisms. Overall, individual survey contribution is not enough to deploy a proper and secure SDN framework.

The survey depicts that security enhancement contributions are limited as compared to security issues contribution presented in Table 3.2. In order to achieve the full security of SDN network, most of the security implementation must be carried out in collaboration of interoperability with multi-vendor platforms, third party-based network applications and network function virtualization, which helps to lower down the larger number of network security vulnerabilities during SDN framework development.

However, based on the development perspective, SDN is not clear in the development area, how to optimise the operational security functions such as forwarding-rules, system-reliability, system-audit, system-recovery etc. Overall existing literature shows that SDN-based security solutions are still limited that cannot completely replace the traditional functions. In order to achieve the improved SDN based security practices, there is a feasible demand to provide the detailed security development assessment that how an SDN-based infrastructure is designed, created and managed with real-time data-based infrastructures. Following such technical assessments, fast, effective and up to date security solutions such as collaborative techniques and novel algorithms can easily be designed and proposed, that can enable to develop the wide ranges of the dynamics of security in network infrastructures.

Chapter 4

DDoS Detection in SDN with Collaborative Techniques of Snort and Deep Neural Networks

This Chapter:

Presents the collaborative detection techniques of DDoS attacks in the SDN network. Firstly, signature-based Snort IDS is utilised for malicious activity detection and traffic monitoring with traffic mirroring in Open vSwitch. Secondly, Deep Neural Networks (DNN) based anomaly detection algorithm is utilised to optimise the attacks detection accuracy on collected data of the proposed model.

4.1 Introduction

The SDN network comprises various vulnerabilities, such as Unauthorised-Access, Data-Leakage, Data-Modification, Denial of Service, mentioned in Chapter 4, Section. 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 4.1.3, and 4.1.5 respectively. These kinds of vulnerabilities are caused due to the deployment of standalone legacy IDS sensors mainly at the central controller unit, finally failed to provide safeguard against such issues. Therefore, in the first stage of this chapter, a signature-based Snort IDS is implemented for malicious activity detection and traffic monitoring with traffic mirroring in Open vSwitch (OVS), then store in CSV log file of Barnyard 2. In the second stage, for effective attack detection in the test-bed, flow-based anomaly detection is deployed with Deep Neural Networks (DNN) to improve the signature-based IDS limitation with a higher detection rate with low false-positive triggers. To assess the efficacy of our proposed collaborative detection technique, a test-bed is developed to sim-

ulate malicious and benign traffic. From the simulation results, our collaborative detection mechanism achieved more than 90% true positive rate with less than 5% of false alarms for all TCP, UDP and ICMP attacks in general, demonstrating effective malicious traffic detection methods as compared to conventional signature-based methodologies.

Software Defined Networking (SDN) has emerged as a great enabler to change the way of designing and building network architecture. Shifting from proprietary based traditional infrastructure to flexible, open, and programmable infrastructure.

According to [57], current public and private cloud computing network infrastructure has gain popularity in everyday life. Network infrastructure is exponentially increasing with implementation complexities; while, traditional networks have become very slow and too complex in the context of innovative modification and cost effective development. The author of [174] deployed scalable IDS system in SDN context, Suricata IDS is implemented to gather the sampled data for suspicious flow, main objective was to improve detection rate. In [1] SDN architecture, control-plane logically manages network at central location, while the forwarding plane sends only forwarding packets with control-plane manipulation. Due to its flexibility, programmability, central manageability SDN has been widely considered for creating its applications as backbone networks, data centres, access networks, enterprise networks, wireless networks, and so on. Despite inserting security policies in SDN environment, the SDN carries plenty of issues for its security perspective, and these issues create alarming situations which must be justified prior to building a feasible architecture. Some of these concerns are legacy network to network inherited environments and some come from SDN architecture itself. Addition to this, most of the conventional IDS sensors are not capable to be deployed with SDN, despite SDN being highly flexible, and capable to build innovative network applications. On the other hand IDS sensors are quite outdated so the classical IDS may be insufficient [172].

Due to the flexibility and flow-based nature of SDN, we proposed a collaborative attack detection model, with Snort-IDS data acquisition and then we apply the Stacked Autoencoder (SAE) algorithm [175], a Deep Neural Network Model (DNN) in SDN platform. The major aim of the collaborative model is to improve the DDoS detection rate with minimum features, as Snort IDS collects features effectively, which are then transformed and processed with SAE. With the help of the SAE algorithm, we train and evaluate our model using the dataset acquired from our system, SAE also reconstructs the 22 features input and also stabilize the dimensionality reduction. the detail is provided in Section III. From the experiment, we find feasible parameters for DNN. The model achieved performance with 85% accuracy using only 22 common features obtained from the real network. This performance

is reasonable because our collaborative model collects realistic network data along with malicious traffic to create a realistic attack scenario using signature-based and flow-based methodologies.

4.2 Background

In [48], combining intrusion detection system (IDS) with SDN environment enables to create secure and valuable SDN platform. The main purpose of the IDS system is to trigger alarms for malicious activities, and unauthorised attempts. The system detects malicious activities and attacks, either in host-based IDS or network-based IDS. The IDS system falls into two categories, mainly host-based IDS (HIDS) and network-based IDS (NIDS). HIDS is installed on workstations and to monitor network traffic individually. It triggers alarms on each host rather than the entire network. It can notify event of potential attacks to authorized user or administrator. NIDS gets access to network traffic with the help of hub, network tap, and preconfigured switch for mirroring traffic to a specific port.

In [176], the authors proposed a lightweight method to detect DDoS attacks based on traffic flow features is presented with six tuples of feature extraction such as Average of Packet per flow (APf), Average of Bytes per flow (ABf), Average of Duration per flow (ADf), Percentage of Pair flows (PPf), Growth of Single flow (GSf), and Growth of Different Ports (GDP). Moreover, flow streams in OpenFlow due to the fact of hard timeout is capable to communicate with two hosts in a single flow. Flow is divided into sub-components if there exists a larger connection in time context. Therefore all six features of this work are modified to be used in the form of merging 30-minutes for identical flows.

The authors of [120] utilised Self-Organizing Maps (SOM), a flow-based method. The major aim was to detect DDoS flooding attacks inside kernel-based modular detection engine. Based on traffic features, detection engine classified in benign traffic and malicious traffic entries. The proposed work can only perform with table flow and cannot be extended to detect DDoS attacks in heavily traffic flow streams inside switches. In [166] authors employed sFlow to gather flow-based data for anomaly detection and mitigation mechanism in SDN. The proposed system comprises a collector, the anomaly detection and anomaly mitigation components. The collector module collects flow-entries or flows packets with OpenFlow and sFlow approaches. Then an entropy-based algorithm was utilized to classify normal traffic and abnormal traffic. When abnormal traffic was detected, the IP address and port number were provided to anomaly mitigation module for mitigation purpose. As sFlow was used for sampling traffic in implementation, the false-positive rate was very high in the attack detection module.

In contrast to discussed work, we use Snort a well-known signature-based intrusion detection technique, Snort IDS system is specific to integrate with SDN architecture, integration of Snort IDS in SDN refers NIDS throughout all work unless it is specified otherwise. Addition to this, we also use anomaly detection with Stacked Autoencoder (SAE) algorithm, in collaboration with SDN based NIDS. The main difference between our work and others is that we apply our model on a dataset collected from IDS environment. We use 22 important features extracted from our IDS network. Such as, TCP/UDP incoming flows, TCP/UDP outgoing flows, symmetric TCP/UDP incoming flows, asymmetric TCP/UDP incoming flows, bytes per incoming TCP/UDP flows, bytes per outgoing TCP/UDP flows, TTL (Time to Live) values for incoming TCP/UDP flows, TTL values for outgoing TCP/UDP flows, protocol types, source bytes, destination bytes, source ports, destination port, and so on. These features were extracted in SDN control-plane remotely connected to data-plane. The proposed work is capable of detecting attacks on data-plane and is implemented in SDN.

4.3 Experiment Design

The SDN testbed is created to emulate both attack and benign traffic. As signature-based IDS cannot provide a safeguard against all types of attacks, to overcome this issue we provide an alternative approach of anomaly-based detection with Deep Neural Network (DNN) model. It uses features comparison between malicious traffic and benign traffic such as packets payloads, packet sizes, source or destination port numbers, IP sequence with same characteristics of time to live (TTL). Our proposed work uses two main approaches to fill the gap in this problem. The first one is to create an SDN testbed to mimic real network environment to provide solution of signature-based attacks and data acquisition for the next stage. The second method provides a DNN model, which works with the integration of signature-based architecture and then detects anomalies which are unknown to signature-based NIDS in SDN context.

4.3.1 SDN Test-Bed

Virtual machine (VM1) with Ubuntu LTS 16.04 64 bit OS is created for implementing Mininet network simulator [177], Snort [178] IDS and DDoS attacks tool such Low Orbital Ion Cannon [179] (LOIC) and hping3 [180]. The Mininet network simulator is used to create OVS switches and host system. Attack emulation scenario is also created with the help of the LOIC tool on the same machine. Our work utilises Ryu as coding application, which helps to manipulate and manage

control-plane[181].

As shown in Figure 4.1, with the help of Mininet simulator a realistic network topology is developed with five OVS switches as a central hub for acquiring optimal performance of network traffic and five VM hosts are also created in which four hosts generate malicious traffic using manual attacks process and one generating benign traffic. All hosts are interconnected with OVS switch. Communication established between OVS switches and hosts with Open Flow 1.3 protocol.

Figure 4.1: Network Topology.

LOIC DDoS attack tool and hping3, a command-line oriented (transmission control protocol/ internet protocol) TCP/IP packet analyzer are used to emulate malicious traffic such as TCP, UDP, ICMP and RAW IP protocols. On the other hand, normal or benign traffic is created by logging web surfing activity of a user. The malicious and benign traffic is launched from VM hosts.

4.3.2 Network Data Acquisition

NSL Data Ltd provides the dataset, which is the rectified version of KDD-Cup 99 [28-aa]. It is widely used the dataset in research for training and evaluation purpose in NIDS models. Although it is a quite old dataset and does not represent existing real network data, and this dataset carries a huge quantity of redundant records, which is not sufficient to recent attack scenario. Data inputs reduce the learning algorithm output towards one-sided redundant results [182]. Data acquisition with virtual machine (VM) is utilised in our work which collects malicious data such as signature-based attacks and anomalies and benign data. VM1 is prepared with Snort-IDS, Barnyard2 is also integrated with its detection engine to reduce the workload of the Snort sensor with maximum data capturing and monitoring. As

Snort [178] is based on the signature, so we customized its configuration file with specific rules to generate DDoS alerts. Overall, we use 20 rules in snort.conf refers to Snort-mode (SM1) file within specific protocols, ports, rules features so that it could catch only specified DDoS traffic and effectively store it to Barnyard2 log file integrated to Snort. Similarly, snort.conf refers to Snort-mode (SM2) file is also customized with alert signatures of TCP, UDP, and ICMP, for catching normal traffic and anomalies. This configuration file is individually run during an attack and normal traffic events which enables to correctly label benign datasets and overall network anomalies which are unknown to SM1.

Wireshark tool, is also used with the mirrored port of the Mininet network which monitors overall traffic using traffic filter of Wireshark with any option. The main objective for using Wireshark is to validate Snort-IDS output file and to increase features for anomaly detection algorithm. Moreover, our model uses Snort –IDS sensor, Barnyard2 and Wireshark tools in the following two data capturing modes for the proposed research.

- **Snort-mode (SM1)** : This data capturing mode comprises Snort IDS sensor with 20 DDoS attack signatures for (DDoS attacks), output alert_csv as CSV1, Barnyard2 as snort.log.1xx file, Wireshark tool to analyse features.
- **Snort-mode (SM2)** : This data capturing mode comprises Snort IDS sensor with 10 signatures for (normal traffic, and anomalous traffic), output alert_csv as CSV2 and, CSV3 Barnyard2 snort.log.2xx, Wireshark to analyse features.

As shown in Figure 4.2, from HOST1 of the network we run Low Orbital Ion Cannon (LOIC) DDoS tool and emulate packets of UDP, ICMP and TCP DDoS flood attacks on various ports, the total number of packets were around 9000 for each category. All malicious packets from network passed to Snort SM1 mode that only parses packets which match to the predefined set of DDoS signatures then it sends to Barnyard2 log file. In addition to this Wireshark was also monitoring DDoS traffic parallel to Snort-IDS. Ryu Snort integration enables to create CSV1 file comprises of signature-based TCP, UDP, and ICMP DDoS attacks.

Figure 4.3, we run Snort-IDS two times individually with SM2 mode. Although SM2 is specially configured with simple alert signatures of TCP, UDP, and ICMP rules, with the help of customized signatures and Snort output alert_csv two csv files such as CSV2 and CSV3 are created for normal and network anomalous respectively; network anomalies are also types of malicious activities which Snort SM1 mode cannot capture this is because SM1 signatures are only designed to capture signature-based DDoS attacks.

Firstly, from network HOST2 we manually surf the web browsing such as Google searches, audio/ video streaming then allow Snort-IDS with SM2 mode to catch

Figure 4.2: SM1 Mode Malicious Detection / Data Acquisition.

normal activities of our network. In the Barnyard2 log file, another CSV2 file is created with 10,000 normal packets. Secondly, from network HOST3, we once again emulate same quantity of malicious traffic (UDP, ICMP and TCP packets) with the help of LOIC tool, but this time Snort SM2 mode implemented to record network anomalous in CSV3 file.

Data was manually acquired from the network into three different csv files such as CSV1, CSV2, and CSV3. All these files were correctly labelled into a single csv file based on benign and malicious features. Addition to this Snort is also integrated to SDN Controller Ryu, where Snort uses eth0 interface which is configured to promiscuous mode [141], which receives all traffic from the entire network and then forward these packets on mirrored port 3 of OpenFlow switch [181]. Snort eth1 with IP 192.168.232.x is configured in Ryu socket to receive packets remotely. Snort sends csv file to Ryu control-plan to run detection algorithm with its collaboration.

Ryu controller is installed and configured on Ubuntu LTS 16.04 64 bit OS on the virtual machine (VM2). Ryu manages Open Virtual Switches (OVS) with OpenFlow 1.3 protocol remotely connected to Mininet simulator. On the top of Ryu controller Snort switch (switch_snort.py) application is installed, which support L2 Switch main coding, and also enable to redirect all OpenFlow switch traffic via promiscuous mode from one of the Snort port to Ryu (Unix Socket) port. There are two standard Snort integration options available with Ryu. Option 1 is very basic and suitable for demonstration purpose. However, we use Option 2, in which Snort as a sensor is installed to another remote machine. Ryu receives Snort alerts with the help of

network socket known as unixsock. The unixsock=false, receives all port mirrored Snort sensor traffic from Barnyard2 log file. In this way, data-plan of network and hosts packets are controlled and flexibly monitored with SDN Controller Ryu.

Figure 4.3: SM2 Mode Normal and Malicious Data Acquisition.

4.3.3 Deep Neural Network Network (DNN) Approach

SAE works with minimal feature inputs as it is capable to reconstruct limited inputs vector, which only utilizes hidden layers such as encoders and decoders to reconstruct the features. SAE is also capable to learn inherent features automatically from the multi-layer backpropagation neural network (BPNN) in an unsupervised manner. SAE is created on the basis that; it preserves the minimum number of features during evaluation with lower-dimensional compression. SAE is feasibly used for effective DDoS classification with minimum features numbers.

Stacked Autoencoder (SAE) is a DNN approach, which comprises stacked sparse autoencoder entities, and soft-max classifier for unsupervised input features learning and classification respectively. The SAE is a neural network comprises only three layers, both input and output layers. Input values are model feature values, which are used for model training, and output layer utilizes two similar function values. The model also utilizes vector biased values during learning approximation function with the help of Back Propagation algorithm [183] The sigmoid activation function is utilized for hidden and output layers. The model uses AdamOptimizer for training. Overall this model continued until the last layer is trained, finally, all SAE model layers rectified to improve the proposed collaborative performance. In addition to

Snort-IDS, an anomaly-based DNN model is also designed to be implemented with the system as shown in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Proposed Test-Bed of Snort IDS with DNN Co-Detection in SDN.

Anomaly detection with DNN model is used to compliment the signature-based system. However, inside virtual test-bed, the manipulation of each attack categories has limited space. This proposed model has a diversified approach to detect various attacks. The experiment uses 20 features of subset dataset, which is a combination of three different csv files. The detail is provided in Table 4.1. All of these features are obtained from live SDN test-bed.

Table 4.1: Number of Records in all CSV files for normal and attacks data.

File	Malicious Data	Normal Data	Anomalies Data	No of Records
CSV1	TCP UDP ICMP			8,000
CSV2		TCP UDP ICMP		10,000
CSV3			TCP UDP ICMP	10,000
Total	TCP UDP ICMP	TCP UDP ICMP	TCP UDP ICMP	28,000

Our experiment comprises the construction of DNN approach, in which a single input-layer is utilized with three hidden-layers and an out-layer shown in Figure 4.5. The hidden-layer uses ten, five and three neurons respectively. Our model uses 20 input dimensions (the combination of the malicious and benign dataset from SDN based Snort-Ryu data acquisition). The model uses initiation parameters 20 for

epochs and 50 for batch size. Learning rate is set up at 0.0001 for initial training, in the experiment it will be provided in detail.

Figure 4.5: Simple Deep Neural Network Model.

After normalization and processing dataset is divided into training and testing datasets; we used training dataset for model classification and testing dataset for performance evaluation. Our csv dataset features are positive real-valued numbers. We pre-process dataset with max_min normalization.

Generally, the performance output of the NIDS system is calculated using accuracy (AC), precision (P), recall (R), and F-measure (F), these are standard benchmarks and commonly used parameters [19] for the evaluation of machine learning models thus DNN. Our model evaluates above parameters using confusion matrix. From the confusion matrix, True Positive (TP) values are correctly identified attacks records. True Negative (TN) values are correctly identified as non-attack values. The False Positive (FP) output values are incorrectly predicted attack records. False Negative (FN) output values are incorrectly identified as non-attacks. Below equations are derived with the help of confusion matrix to obtain parameters of our proposed model evaluation [19].

Accuracy (AC): calculates the proportion of correct predictions from total records:

$$AC = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (4.1)$$

Precision (P): calculates proportion of predicted positive cases (real attacks) with correct values:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (4.2)$$

Recall (R): calculates percentage of predicted NIDS attacks against all presented attacks. We need R with higher value:

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4.3)$$

F-measure (F): calculates test accuracy in NIDS model by considering harmonic mean for both precision (P) and the recall (R), we need high F score:

$$F = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{P+R}} \quad (4.4)$$

4.3.4 Results

Firstly, the classification model deployed with two classes i.e. normal class and anomaly class. The optimization in our model is achieved after varying learning rate values amongst 0.01, 0.001, and 0.0001. During model training time, we focused to reduce loss and to get optimal accuracy level. When we decrease the learning rate to 0.0001 then we get the best results during the training phase. However, in the testing phase, detail of the model is calculated using the parameters, accuracy (AC), precision (P), recall (R), and F-measure (F). With the help of test dataset, we evaluated the overall performance of our DNN model. Table 4.2 depicts model performance with three different learning rates. It shows that the model results of learning rate (0.0001) are not good enough compared to the learning rate of (0.001). This is due to nature that, when the model is using very small learning rate, then most of NIDS models can easily be biased to be trained very accurately, and then these models cannot learn special detailed characteristics provided during the training session. We have used limited records of data inputs such as 28,000 with 22 features, where the 0.001 learning rate provides best results during all metrics evaluation, and NIDS model gradually decreases performance when the learning rate is 0.0001. During the testing phase, the model trained accurately with the learning rate of 0.01 due to limited features and generated 10% more loss than learning rate of (0.001 and 0.0001).

In the following Receiver Operating Curve (ROC), we visualized classifier performance by plotting rate of (TP) against the rate of (FP) in the classifier. The area under the curve (ROC) gives a standard measure to compare classifier average performance. Higher the area, greater the system performance. Figure 4.6 shows the ROC of the binary class model with learning rate 0.0001, where model achieves

Table 4.2: Different Learning Rate Accuracy of Model (Testing Phase).

Learning Rate	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
0.01	83%	89.8%	71.2%	80.6%
0.001	85%	92%	74.2%	81.7%
0.0001	84%	91.2%	74.6%	82.2%

TP rate higher than 90% with an FP rate of below 5% for all TCP, UDP and ICMP attacks in general.

Figure 4.6: ROC Curve for Binary Classification Model.

We also evaluated our binary class classification by considering all kind of DDoS attacks to compare our works with others. Figure 4.7 depicts the overall performance of binary class classification. This model achieved detection accuracy AC 85% with f-measure value as 81.2 % and 81.75% for normal class and attack class respectively, derived from the confusion matrix shown in below Figure 4.7. On the contrary, we evaluated our work with closely related work [151], the author uses six basic features such as APf, ABf, ADf, PPf, GSf, and GDP from NSL-KDD dataset for general attack detection. In the results, the AC detection rate is less than 80% with 46% of falsely identified triggers such as FP rate, and did not focus any special kind of attack.

However, our results have shown better performance in term of collaborative detection of Snort IDS and SAE DNN anomaly detection approach. The main reason could be the selection of our special feature that can help for training and testing a real-time data to catch various types of anomalies, and we have utilised only very small 30% (6000) of a total dataset in the model training. This is due to the nature of our model uses live traffic for both normal and malicious class.

This helps to be implemented in any type of network to catch network intrusion with a good detection rate. We also calculated the computational time for both training and testing dataset of our model using the machine with Intel (R) Xeon (R) X5560 CPU with 2.88 GHz processor and 16 GB RAM running TensorFlow 1.0.0 on Ubuntu LTS 16.04 64 bit. Table 4.3 shows the computation time for training dataset of 6,000 records and test dataset of 14,000 records.

Table 4.3: Average computational time for training dataset and test dataset of model.

Training dataset time	Test dataset time
800 Sec	0.907 Sec

Figure 4.7: Binary Classifier confusion Matrix.

Chapter 5

DDoS Detection with Sampling and Deep Learning in SDN

This Chapter:

pragmatically depicts sFlow and adaptive polling-based sampling with the Snort Intrusion Detection System (IDS) and deep learning-based model, which provides support to reduce the various types of prevalent DDoS attacks in the IoT network. We have utilised the decoupling property of SDN to program network devices to achieve the best results. Firstly, in data-plane, to lower down processing and network overhead of switches, we deployed sFlow and adaptive polling-based sampling individually. Secondly, in control-plane, to optimize detection accuracy, we deployed Snort IDS collaboratively with Stacked Autoencoders (SAE) deep learning model. The evaluation based on SAE algorithm achieved the higher detection accuracy with 95% of True Positive rate. We also quantitatively investigate trade off among attack detection accuracy of both samplings.

5.1 Introduction

In chapter 4, we deployed fundamentals elements of Snort IDS, to collect and store datasets, then we utilised simple DNN network to classify the attacks based on Snort datasets. Chapter 5 addresses the research question from 1 up to 4 and it also provides the effective solution as compared to the Rate Limiting, Maximum Entropy Detector, identified in Chapter 3. Chapter 5 is improved version of Chapter 4, which utilises sFlow and adaptive polling-based sampling with Snort Intrusion Detection System (IDS) and deep learning-based model, which helps to lower down the various types of prevalent DDoS attacks. The result evaluation of the proposed system

demonstrates higher detection accuracy with 95% of True Positive rate with less than 4% of False Positive rate within sFlow based implementation compared to adaptive polling.

The rapid growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) has become very popular throughout the world, it has emerged in our modern smart homes, vehicles and many other wearable gadgets. IoT is a combination of large interconnected devices, such as household appliances, wearable devices, medical devices, smart vehicles and public facilities provider [184], [185]. According to the research [186], tens of billions of vulnerable devices will be connected to IoT. Most of these devices do not use secure communication protocols or appropriate security measures when interfacing with computing and storage units. These vulnerabilities provide temptation not only for enterprises wanting to acquire data for the adoption of intelligent management system or digital proof but also for malicious users (i.e., attackers), which diffuse intrusion or service disruption such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS). Once a DDoS attack occurs then it can severely threaten human life safety directly or indirectly - for instance, connected medical devices, home or critical infrastructure monitoring. Current studies in [187], [188] depict that IoT is also vulnerable to viruses. Studies of current DDoS attacks have also proved that IoT has ubiquitous loopholes with the initial stage. If the security approaches have not been deployed in IoT then DDoS attacks unwillingly arise. DDoS attacks are capable to make most of the network services unavailable by utilizing all available server resources with continuous undesirable traffic floods. Cisco Visual Networking Index (VNI) has depicted in a survey, nearly 17 millions of DDoS intrusion activities can happen by 2020, as a triple increment to 2015 incidents [140]. Nature of attacks is also switching from a single flooding attack to multiple attack vectors.

In 2016, the largest DDoS attacks [189] were recorded, these DDoS attacks were caused due to unauthorised remote access to IoT devices and security weakness. This vulnerability enables the undetected attackers to instal Botnet at various nodes of IoT devices, where compromised IoT devices nodes generate the high traffic and exhausts the resources.

Software Defined Networking (SDN) in collaboration with packet sampling and deep learning based applications have received much attention from researchers [120], [183], [190]. SDN provides the centralized global view of the entire infrastructure with programmable control-plane and data-plane individually. As intrusion detection technology is exponentially rising in current network security approaches, researchers are facing challenges on how to manage a large significant amount of sampled traffic load in an effective way. The researchers have proposed network traffic characteristics which comprise the size of flow table [191], deviation in traffic flow [192] and anomaly statistics with sampling [115]. The authors in [191] proposed sam-

pling technique based on flow-size. According to the authors, most of the network attacks use the small size of traffic flow from a malicious traffic source. From experiments, they depicted that malicious traffic flow size is much smaller than certain sampled threshold values with constant probability. The authors of [192] proposed an IDS based method on statistics of traffic flow. The research studies represent that flow rapidly increased during the event of a network attack. The sampled traffic was partitioned into sub-sections followed by a source autonomous system data. Moreover, their experimental analysis pragmatically improves the overall intrusion detection ability. In [115], the authors presented that sampling approaches reduce detection ability for non-volume dependent anomalies. The authors implemented three different intrusion detection algorithms for detecting non-volume malicious traffic from both sampled traffic and original data trace. Their results depicted that sampling network traffic can increase false-positive triggers and reduce overall detection capability of IDS. The authors of [193] proposed a feasible pattern matching approach to improve Snort IDS performance, the research work mainly focused to reduce false-positive alarms. The deployment of IDS was based on co-detection of misuse and anomaly approaches. The overall system proposed fast and reliable packet inspection with very fewer resources utilization. Most of the authors have proposed DDoS detection approaches in SDN with unreal and redundant datasets, which mainly focus only on SDN control-layer. The existing literature comprises control-plane sampling approaches due to the initial stage of SDN features, which also lead to low detection accuracy and higher resource consumption. Summary of existing work is presented in the Table 5.1.

To solve the aforementioned problems, we proposed a novel solution to effectively detect DDoS traffic in IoT. Our proposed solution uses sFlow and adaptive polling based sampling in data-plane to manage heavy traffic flows. These sampling approaches lower down network burden and enables IDS to record malicious activities effectively. Our work uses Snort and Stacked Autoencoders (SAE), an unsupervised algorithm to improve detection accuracy with real-time network traces collected with IDS in SDN. In this work, we utilized packet based sFlow and time-oriented adaptive polling based sampling approaches inside data-plane switches, to rebuild real-time network flows statistic with low CPU and network overhead. This enables the DDoS detection model to effectively classify traffic during DDoS floods. We also provided a comparison between OpenFlow based sFlow and adaptive polling based sampling schemes to improve the IDS detection inaccuracies, while keeping total sampled flows lower than IDS processing power. This enables to acquire data with Snort IDS over the controller. Our work achieved less than 4% of False Positive alerts with 95% True Positive rate in packet-based sampling, which is comparatively better than time oriented sampling. Proposed work is evaluated in Tensorflow 1.4

Table 5.1: Existing literature survey for DDoS detection in SDN.

Author	Year	Description	Methods	Weakness	Strength
[151]	2010	Proposed work utilizes six SDN based traffic features to detect DDoS attacks.	Neural network model,SOM.	Detection of DDoS is harder due to the similarities of normal and malicious data.	Light weight method to detect DDoS with very low overhead of CPU.
[194]	2010	Packet-in Bloom filter used in switch memory to manage the DDoS traffic.	Load balancing, Bloom filter	Utilises more CPU and memory due to OF army of Rack Managers	Model provides scalability, performance and fault-tolerance.
[195]	2011	this work utilizes SDN TE application for effectively detection in networks.	SDN TE, load balancing.	Controller can exploit wildcard rules support for switches.	Distributed wildcard used to handle load balancing via NOX controller.
[136]	2011	Depicted various traffic collection and for effectively detection in networks.	TRW-CB, maximum entropy, Rate Limiting	Poorly management within SOHO networks in OF switches.	Accurate to identify malicious activities in the home networks.
[196]	2012	Block-based neural network (BBNN) used with IDS to detect DDoS in FPGA	BBNN algorithm, IDS,	Higher packet loss and low detection accuracy.	Higher frequency-based FPGA design to classify real-time intrusions.
[111]	2013	Proposed method lower down the burden between control-plane and data-plane.	Interface mitigation.	Repeat communication bottleneck between data plane and the control plane.	Actuating triggers helps to collect statistics from the data planes.
[197]	2013	Utilized Snort with combined techniques f anomaly detection and misuse detection	Anomaly, misuse detection, Snort IDS	limitations of the firewall and IDS systems.	Novel and faster packet matching technique.
[120]	2014	Flow based feature extraction to detect worm propagation, DDoS, portscan attacks.	Entropy detection.	The packet can be acquired with hardware software OF devices only.	Fast effective anomaly detection and mitigation in SDN
[190]	2015	Heavy traffic request handled using scheduling based traffic scenarios.	multiple direction DDoS	Slower accuracy inside larger network	Sampling approaches helps to improve the detection.
[159]	2015	Detection model employed in edge switch to reduce traffic flows at controller.	Entropy based detection	Larger networks, unmanageable DDoS traffic.	Entropy-based lightweight DDoS detection
[198]	2016	Utilized semi-supervised SVM to detect anomalies in SDN.	SVM, anomaly detection	Redundant t features cause various anomalies.	Higher dimensional anomaly detection with unsupervised features extraction.
[162]	2016	Quantitative Shannon entropy utilized to classify early stage DDoS attacks.	Shannon method of entropy	Single point failure can lower down DDoS and entire network.	Cost effective and fast response with Entropy calculations.
[199]	2016	A heavy DDoS attack rate is detected via Sequential Probability Ratio Test	SPRT method.	Attacker generates continuous malicious flows to controller.	Model identify the locations under attacks to defeat it.
[150]	2017	Deep learning based, multi-vector DDoS traffic monitoring and detection system.	Deep learning, SAE algorithm	Features redundancy causes issues.	A multi-vectored DDoS detection without 3rd parties.
[200]	2017	Counter measure mitigation implemented as SLICOTS at controller for TCP SYN floods.	SLICOTS methods	Over saturation of TCP SYN floods with control-plane.	Rapid and fast DDoS mitigation over TCP connections.
[201]	2018	Extreme gradient algorithm proposed to classify DDoS attacks with low false triggers.	Machine learning.	Private cloud-based isolation causes DDoS.	A flow based XGBoost classification to collect traffic.

by utilizing a confusion matrix.

This Chapter is organised as: in Section II, we present background and related work. In the Section III, we discuss main architectural components of the proposed system. In Section IV, we present traffic analysis.Finally, we discuss experimental setup and results evaluation in Section V and VI respectively. Finally, conclusion is provided in Section VII.

5.2 Background Overview

This chapter mainly focuses on IoT DDoS attack detection model by first utilising sFlow and adaptive polling sampling with Snort IDS to identify the network traffic, and then classify the traffic with Stacked AutoEncoder (SAE) into benign and malicious traffic. In the following, we present the building block of our proposed DDoS attack detection.

5.2.1 Stacked AutoEncoder (SAE) in SDN

The SAE comprises several auto-encoders, its structure consists of three layers, input or visible layer, hidden layer, and reconstruction or output layer. The data inputs are fed into a visible layer. The reconstruction layer generates output. SAE algorithm is unique in nature as compared to CNN, DBN, and RBM deep neural networks. Firstly, SAE is made up of simple and straightforward structure, it is trained in very less time as compared to other mentioned Deep Neural Network (DNN) algorithms [183]. Secondly, SAE does not use labelled datasets due to the nature of the unsupervised learning approach. In contrast, CNN is based on supervised learn-

ing, whereas, DBN and RBM utilize semi-supervised datasets. Finally, the SAE algorithm also utilizes the outputs as inputs, and detailed features from flows can be extracted with good training approach in SAE. This chapter utilizes detailed features of a dataset based on the SAE approach to improve the detection rate of DDoS attacks in SDN. SAE as deep neural networks (DNN) utilizes sparse auto-encoders and soft-max classifier for extraction and classification of unsupervised datasets. A sparse AutoEncoder is a neural network that uses three layers, where input and output layers work with P nodes and hidden nodes with Q nodes. The M nodes from input layers show records with P features such as $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_p\}$. The training function manipulates the output layer as the input layer. The main objective of sparse auto-encoders as network is to calculate feasible values for the weighted matrices like $U \in \sigma e^{q \times p} = (WW^T)$ and $U' \in \sigma e^{p \times q} = (W'^T W')$. The bias vectors are given as $b_v \in \sigma e^{Q \times 1}$, similarly, $b'_v \in \sigma e^{P \times 1}$. We set a learning identity approximation function $X^\wedge \approx X$ by using back propagation algorithm [202]. There is a large number of activation functions used for hidden and output nodes but we utilized Sigmoid activation function to activate the function of sU, b_v , which is formulated in the following equations:

$$J(W) = sU, b_v = s(UX + b_v) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(UX + b_v)}} \quad (5.1)$$

$$J(W) = \frac{0.5}{r} \sum ||P(X)_n - P(X^\wedge)_n|| + 0.5\lambda(WW_T + W'^T W') \quad (5.2)$$

$$J_{sparse}(W) = J(W) + \beta \sum_{J=1}^q d_{KL}(\rho || \rho_J^\wedge) \quad (5.3)$$

In equation 5.2, we optimize SAE generalization ability to get feasible features representation of datasets. For this objective we added cost function to achieve feasible weight learning in sparse SAE, backpropagation is utilized for minimization. In this equation term of $\frac{0.5}{r} \sum ||P(X)_n - P(X^\wedge)_n||$ represents the all data inputs average of sum-of-square errors records with corresponding model output values with number of r records. The second term of $0.5\lambda(WW_T + W'^T W')$ is used for weight decay with the help of λ to maintain over fitting inside our model. In equation 5.3, β represents the weight coefficient of sparsity penalty with Kullback-Leibler divergence function. This divergence function is used to manipulate low average activation values, this function reaches the minimum values of 0 when $\rho = \rho_J^\wedge$, among them ρ is sparsity coefficient and ρ_J^\wedge is known as average activation of J th hidden node during training input. The divergence function of Kullback-Leibler (KL) is provided in equation 5.4 as below:

$$KL((\rho||\rho_j^\wedge) = \rho \log \frac{\rho}{\rho_j^\wedge} + (1 - \rho) \log \frac{(1 - \rho)}{(1 - \rho_j^\wedge)} \quad (5.4)$$

5.2.2 The sFlow Sampling Approach

To deal IDS aforementioned issues which are depicted in Section II, we implemented packet sampling with sFlow capability in our proposed design. The sFlow sampling technique creates mandatory flow statistics, which is normally used for manipulation purpose [120]. Due to this nature sFlow approach gathers sampled packets and then rebuilds the new flow patterns by updating packet counters for each flow entries in OpenFlow (OF) enabled controller. The sFlow collector propagates all related traffic statistics to malicious detection model. The sFlow approach enables data-plane forwarding logic in more efficient and aggregate way, which reduces network overhead from all deployed infrastructure. This approach of sFlow does not rely on specific flow entries but the major aim is to reduce the number of flow entries up to the relevant level for detection model.

According to [203], sFlow is a suitable technology to monitor real-time and virtual networks. sFlow agents are utilized in network switches to collect switch statistics with the required sample rate then transfer to common sFlow collector. Normally, mechanism of sampled data gathering comprises either replicating real packet's header or feature extraction from network packets, then sample packets after being decoded transferred to cache flow record, every flow record is updated and saved to look up each flow record entry. Following by protocol information such as FIN flags, timeout, inactivity or once cache memory is full then records are wiped out from its cache memory and transferred to traffic analysis application. However, in sFlow case, all monitoring, decoded hash flow, flush functionality are wiped out from switches then these are propagated to centralized sFlow analyses also known as a collector, this runs on an individual server with abundant resources to support a large number of request flows with network stabilization.

Moreover, the sFlow helps to overcome possible table size flow limitation which is mandatory for specific OF hardware deployed infrastructure [120]. Meanwhile, the sFlow data collection technique gathers appropriate statistics for the effective anomaly detection process. As sFlow collector gathers packet samples consistently, it also updates relevant counters for monitoring module with a specific time window. Therefore, each flow entry does not require further maintenance for manipulating detailed flow statistics, this enables to lower down the complexities for flow collection models. In Section VI, low CPU and resources usage of the model will be presented to support sFlow mechanism in our proposed work.

5.2.3 Adaptive Polling Sampling Approach

According to the authors of [204], it is significantly challenging to create a model that helps to deal with large amounts of data. One potential approach to working with large volumes of data is to take a random sample and perform data processing on it. But, as some scholars have suggested, random sampling is difficult to use due to the difficulties of calculating reasonable sample size. Thus, the sample size is not fixed with priority; rather it depends on the condition in an adaptive manner. Many existing traffic management systems use deep packet inspection (DPI) to analyze network traffic. In this chapter, we suggest a new adaptive sampling algorithm that chooses the maximum number of packets that the DPI system can receive from the network. Because of this adaptability, our algorithm adapts its sampling rate to the existing network traffic and the number of packets that can be handled by a control program.

In proposed work, adaptive polling sampling algorithm is used to refine polling intervals based on the rate of change of each flow. If switches flow rapidly changes then polling interval is reduced, on contrast, if polling intervals increased then flow remains stable. The polling interval becomes unchanged when flow fluctuates. We dynamically manipulated polling frequency by predicting future flow rates on the basis of historical data. The polling interval is calculated with the help of predicted future flow rates rather than the current live flow rate. We utilized the combined approach of proportional linear prediction (PLP) and weighted linear prediction (WLP) to estimate the next flow rate. This approach in the SDN environment is also discussed in [205]. Firstly, we implemented a low pass filter [206] to estimate the future flow rate. Low pass filter for flow rate prediction is provided in equation 5.5.

$$Z_{(X+1)} = \beta C + (1 - \beta)W \quad (5.5)$$

In equation 5.5, $Z_{(X+1)}$ represents the predicted values for flow rate pf next upcoming polling, C is currently calculated value and W depicts two different current polling values such as $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, based on the network load, it is implemented in experiment. Afterwards, next flow rate is calculated with PLP given as below:

$$Z_{(X+1)}^P = Z_X \left(1 + \frac{\delta(Z_X - Z_X)}{Z_{(X-1)}} \right) \quad (5.6)$$

$$Z_{(X+1)} = \beta Z_{(X+1)}^P + (1 - \beta)Z_X \quad (5.7)$$

Overall, aggregated rate of change in flow is provided as below in equation: 5.8:

$$M = \frac{|Z_{(X+1)} - Z_X|}{Z_X} \quad (5.8)$$

In equation 5.8, M represents overall flow changes where, two threshold values of M_{min} and M_{max} used with $0 \leq M \leq 1$ conditions. If the value of $M < M_{min}$ then detected flow gradually changes as compared to current conditions. When $M \geq M_{min}$ then it brings increment in polling interval thresholds, and detected flow rate rapidly changes in contrast to current predictions, it leaves polling threshold values slow down here. Other than these depicted conditions, the detected flow rate becomes proportional to current predictions and leaves polling thresholds unchanged.

Algorithm 1 Adaptive polling sampling in SDN switches

```

1: Input:  $M_{min}, M_{max}, UB_{max}, LB_{min}$ , polling intervals, active flows, historic flows
2: Ensure Output:  $Time_{int}$ , next polling intervals
3: if active flow in packet – in – event, return False
4: function DO NOT SEND (flow to Switches table)
5:   else if polling table  $\Delta T_{sect} = Curr_{sect} - Pre_{sect}$  return True
6:   Utilize equation 5.6 ,3, to calculate next flow rate;
7:   Utilize equation 5.8 to compute aggregate flow change;
8:   if  $M < LB_{min}$  then do;
9:      $T_{Intervals} = \min(T_{intervals} + 1, T_{max})$ ;
10:  else if  $M \geq UB_{max}$  then do;
11:     $T_{Intervals} = \max(\lceil T_{intervals}/2 \rceil, T_{min})$ ;
12:  else  $T_{intervals} = \min(T_{intervals}, T_{max})$ ;
13:  end if

```

The adaptive polling algorithm to sample SDN switches is depicted in algorithm 2. This algorithm uses UB_{max} and LB_{min} as upper bound and lower bound intervals respectively. ΔT_N is polling intervals for N_{th} intervals numbers, in the algorithm, the line 3 and 4 represent overall flow which is currently active in switches with no sampling rate adjustment. Afterwards, we utilized the equations 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 to get the next predicted sample rate with the rate of change of flow in line 7. The given algorithm line 8 to 11 depicts adopted polling intervals rules. The line 8 and 9, if $M < LB_{min}$, represent that polling interval is higher, similarly if $M \geq UB_{max}$, pragmatically depicts the polling interval is reduced shown in line 10, 11. Finally, line 11 and 12 leave the overall polling intervals unchanged.

5.3 Proposed Design

In our proposed design, we mainly utilized open source tools and technology such as sFlow-RT [207] collector and Ntopng [208] collector for sFlow and adaptive polling based sampling respectively in data-plane. Snort as Network Intrusion Detection

Figure 5.1: Data Acquisition with sFlow Sampling.

System (NIDS) with Barnyard2 is also used for creating a database to store datasets inside Ryu SDN controller.

5.3.1 sFlow Collector (sFlow Sampling)

In the sFlow sampling approach, we utilized three main modules consisting on *sFlow-collector*, *Snort-IDS*, and *Data-storage*. This section of the proposed design utilizes sFlow sampling and Snort IDS to manipulate flow classification for higher rate DDoS detection model. This approach collaboratively works with OpenFlow SDN controller and northbound interface communication, which is feasible to create new insertion policies for traffic engineering in Open vSwitch (OVS) switches.

The sFlow module is used to apply packet flow sampling with individual sampling agents on each OVS switches. All sFlow agents deployed remotely via northbound APIs with sampling decision rates of 1/28, 1/64/, 1/256, 1/512, 1/1024 [209]. These sFlow agents standalone deliver collected sampled traffic streams with suitable sampling rate from all deployed switches towards sFlow-RT. The sFlow-RT is a real-time network monitoring tool that collects and analyze sampled streams in detailed visualized form. The sFlow-RT is an industry standard and helps to incorporates InMon asynchronous analytics[210]. The sFlow-RT [209] real-time analytics engine is capable to receive the continuous flow streams from agents of network-embedded switches. The sFlow-RT decodes the received flow from sFlow agents into actionable

metrics via RestFlow API [211]. The RestFlow API is capable to customize the configuration of setting up thresholds, metrics manipulation and flow measurements. These API works with HTTP and rest calls with external applications, in addition to this embedded JavaScript and standardized ECMA scripts enable to work internally. Overall, sFlow-RT provides detailed visible pipeline which helps to bring the sustainable performance of all hosts, servers, applications and embedded devices in a single global view. This helps to classify and analyze feasible network features so that the deployed model can work effectively.

5.3.2 Snort-IDS (sFlow Sampling)

Table 5.2: Six Major DDoS attack types in our test-bed

DDoS Attacks	Sever based	Network based	Application based	Description
HTTP-DDoS floods			✓	Volumetric attacks with HTTP GET or HTTP POST request.
DNS-DDoS floods			✓	Attacks to infect DNS resolution, such as application or API.
ICMP-DDoS floods		✓		ping floods attacks, to overwhelm the ICMP-echo requests
UDP-DDoS floods		✓		These attacks disrupt the device processing ability.
Smurf-DDoS floods		✓		These attacks launch spoofed IP addresses to target.
IP-DDoS floods	✓			Attacks on server source and destination IP addresses

Our chapter uses Snort as NIDS to collect malicious traffic and benign traffic, We used various frameworks and tools eg. The Metasploit framework [212], hping3 [180] and Low Orbit Ion Cannon (LOIC) [213] to launch various DDoS attacks with customized TCP/IP packets, we utilize the hping3 tool to emulate customized DDoS attacks. Our model also uses the LOIC DDoS tool to launch TCP, UDP and ICMP floods. By utilising Metasploit and Kali Linux framework, LOIC, and hping3, we generated six most common types of DDoS attack, which are provided in Table 5.2.

The main purpose of the Metasploit framework is to generate malicious traffic with some payloads. Snort collects malicious traffic with SM1-mode and benign traffic is acquired using SM2-mode shown below in Table 5.3. Both benign and malicious traffic is manually emulated from hosts connected directly to OVS switches, attacking hosts are assumed to perform DDoS attack flooding with port scanning using hping3 and LOIC DDoS tool. We implemented a standalone rule set in Snort detection-engine configuration file for both modes mentioned with details in Table 5.3. In test-bed, once traffic is collected with deployed sFlow sampling agents, then all sampled traffic stream is mirrored with port 6343 to the sFlow-collector module. In Figure 5.1, sFlow-collector module is integrated with sFlow-RT. Due to the flexibility of SDN Ryu controller modular design, we utilized sFlow-collector module traffic into Snort-IDS module. In this module Snort is configured with packet logging mode, if traffic is emulated from malicious hosts then it utilizes SM1-mode and if traffic is coming from benign hosts then SM2-mode is used to record logs followed

by Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Snort Traffic acquiring modes with sFlow sampling.

Description	Snort Two Modes	
	SM1 (Malicious)	SM2 (Benign)
TCP rules	15 signatures	8 signatures
UDP rules	10 signatures	6 signatures
ICMP rules	6 signatures	6signatures
CSV Database	Barnyard2	Barnyard2
Log file	snort.log.xx1	snort.log.xx2
Traffic Monitor	sFlow-RT	sFlow-RT
Traffic Manipulation	Python 2.7	Python 2.7

5.3.3 Flow-collector (Adaptive Polling Sampling)

In this Flow-collector module, we deployed a time-driven sampling mechanism with adaptive polling intervals shown in Figure 5.2. In this section, the polling scheme enables to fetch timely accurate switches statistics on a fine-grained level. Our polling mechanism instructs all active switches stream flows by giving limited bandwidth channels and time intervals. It is mandatory to adjust all active flows polling intervals. The main objective of this polling based sampling is to focus, if the number of flows is exponential rising then polling intervals between control-plane and data-plane also increase, which utilizes very large bandwidth.

It is also mandatory to maintain polling bounds given as LB_{min} and UB_{max} for each flow passing through switches, where stable flows are placed in higher polling intervals and lower polling intervals will be used for heavy, busy and unstable flows [214]. We manipulated the tuning frequency by sending FlowStatisticsRequest Messages for individual flows. Control-plane messages are not capable to capture acknowledged flow traffic statistics, instead, we gathered flow statistics by simple multiplication of sampling ratio with the number of bytes in each flow, addition to this we also utilized sampling based adaptive polling interval algorithm elaborated in Algorithm 2. The equation 5.8 depicts rate of change with unit value if the predicted status is very closer to the actual status. All other values must satisfy given condition of $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, where 0 and 1 values represents minimum value of M and maximum value of M respectively.

In the Table 5.4, we depicted feasible rules to manipulate $\Delta Time_{New}$ based on values of M , where M_{min} is set to 0.6 seconds and M_{max} is set to 1.4 seconds [215]. The main reason to set these values is to acquire the best performance of switches polling query. Our adaptive polling-based sampling inside all switches mainly focuses on time-oriented configurations to maintain the network data sampling for higher

Figure 5.2: Data Acquisition with Adaptive Polling Interval Sampling.

accuracy. If the upper bound limit is set to a large value, then network data after sampling will not be up to date, majority of live network traffic will not be recorded. Similarly, if we reduce lower bound time to live (TTL) in the polling algorithm, then it also causes degrade the sampling accuracy . In our algorithm, we tried various upper bound and lower bound conditions based on network traffic in our test-bed and configurations mentioned in Table 5.4, these parameters of adaptive polling achieves best sampling performance in switches across the test-bed.

Table 5.4: Rules to adjust intervals for Polling sampling.

Calculated M Values	New Sample Values
$M < M_{min}$	$\Delta Time_{New} = M \times \Delta Time_{curr}$
$M_{min} \leq M \leq M_{max}$	$\Delta Time_{New} = \Delta Time_{curr}$
$M_{max} < M$	$\Delta Time_{New} = \Delta Time_{curr} + 1_{sec}$
M not defined	$\Delta Time_{New} = 2_{sec} \times \Delta Time_{curr}$

5.3.4 Snort-IDS (Adaptive Polling Sampling)

In this module, we deployed Snort as NIDS with promiscuous enabled mode. The traffic from adaptive switches query with a sampling threshold is propagated to Snort detection engine to log data streams. Sampled traffic is visually analyzed and

Table 5.5: Snort Traffic Acquiring Modes with AP sampling.

Description	Snort Two Modes	
	SM1 (Malicious)	SM2 (Benign)
TCP rules	15 signatures	8 signatures
UDP rules	10 signatures	6 signatures
ICMP rules	6 signatures	6signatures
CSV Database	Barnyard2	Barnyard2
Log file	snort.log.xx3	snort.log.xx4
Traffic Monitor	Ntopng	Ntopng
Traffic Manipulation	Python 2.7	Python 2.7

maintained with Ntopng tool [208]. This module uses two modes of packet logging with Snort IDS. SM1-mode is slightly different from the previous mode as shown in Table 5.5. SM1-mode is applied for malicious traffic collection and SM2-mode for benign traffic collection. This module uses Ntopng tool with OpenFlow enabled switches and software-based Ryu controller, which helps traffic engineer to predict and regulate the sampled traffic based on traffic behaviour and relevant features. In our proposed work, we created a SDN based application to collect sampled traffic with Snort signature based modes.

5.3.5 CSV-storage (sFlow and adaptive polling Sampling)

This module is very fundamental for classifying different feature extractions and collecting network traffic as a CSV file. In this module, we used Barnyard2 a well known MySQL database, which collaboratively works with Snort IDS. It is capable to reduce the workload of Snort as it writes Snort events in human readable modes either on console, text or CSV file. We utilized Barnyard2 to read all binary outputs from Snort into a MySQL database in the CSV form. In Barnyard2 database we deployed unified barnyard2 plug-in and CSV plug-in to acquire easily readable CSV file such as snort.sflow-log.xxx for benign and malicious traffic flow. However, data is gathered in CSV form in two different ways of SM1-mode and SM2-mode. Similar to sFlow this module also uses Barnyard2 with unified plug-in and csv-plug-in for adaptive polling sampling, where Snort creates two separate files such as snort.asq_log.xxx for normal traffic and malicious traffic.

5.4 Traffic Analysis

Data acquisition with virtual machine (VM) is utilized in our work, where both benign data and malicious data is collected based on signature-based IDS with sampling approaches. Our research work mainly focuses on real-time network data

acquisition. Our data acquisition methodology uses two types of sampling sFlow and adaptive polling interval sampling approaches. In data-plane, we deployed both sampling approaches individually and we gathered malicious and benign datasets with Snort SM1-mode and SM2-mode. We utilized two virtual machines, where VM1 is only used for data-plane and implementing sampling, VM2 machine is created with signature-based Snort IDS, Barnyard2 and central SDN Ryu controller. Both virtual machines communicated via OpenFlow 1.3 protocol and sFlow protocol, which is depicted in Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2. To lower down the workload from detection engine of Snort, Barnyard2 is implemented that supports to capture maximum data with monitoring ability. Snort detection engine file is configured with specific rules to generate DDoS alerts.

In sFlow sampling we used 15, 10 and 6 rules for TCP, UDP and ICMP respectively in *snort.conf*, refers to Snort-mode (SM1) file for malicious dataset. Similarly, we utilized 8, 6 and 6 simple rules in *snort.conf* refers to Snort-mode (SM2) file for acquiring normal dataset as show in Table 5.3. In adaptive polling based sampling we also used 15, 10 and 6 rules for TCP, UDP and ICMP respectively in *snort.conf* refers to Snort-mode (SM1) file for the malicious dataset. Similarly, we utilized 8, 6 and 6 simple rules in *snort.conf* refers to Snort-mode (SM2) file for acquiring normal dataset detail is provided in Table 5.5.

Snort is capable to offer various functional outputs such as `alert_syslog`, `alert_fast`, `alert_full`, `alert_unixsock`, `tcpdump` log and `alert_csv`, any of these standard Snort directives can be utilised in *snort.conf* file to achieve desirable network output packets file.

Our chapter utilises the `alert_csv` output plugin in collaboration with SM1-mode and SM2-mode. We have utilised SM1-mode with 15-10-6 rules and SM2-mode with 8-6-6 rules. The main reason for using limited signatures is to write network alerts details in a csv file to process with DNN DDoS detection model. We did not use various Snort signature on *snort.conf* as it significantly reduced the quality of features extracted from malicious and benign traffic.

In SM1-mode, we configured all TCP, UDP and ICMP signatures with specific field values, such as port numbers, content numbers, threshold types and values, priority values, `track by_src`, `track by_dst` and `classtype`. These signatures values were filtering and classifying network data as malicious output. In SM2-mode we utilised only default signature values from Snort repository to record each and every packet, SM2-mode is used to collect only benign data. Further details of this implementation are also provided in Table 5.3.

Our traffic collector section examines all incoming OpenFlow messages at controller, where signature-based Snort IDS and Barnyard2 extracts various header fields based on sampled flows to make CSV files. The flow is TCP and UDP proto-

col combination, which comprises similar values of the type of protocol, source IP addresses and destination IP addresses, source ports and destination ports. ICMP contains the majority of similar fields other than source and destination port numbers. We used Barnyard2 *alert_csv* plug-in by editing *barnyard.conf* with csv features such as *timestamp*, *msg*, *proto*, *src*, *srcport*, *dst*, *dstport*, *ethsrc*, *ethdst*, *ethlen*, *tcpflags*, *tcpseq*, *tcpack*, *tcplen*, *tcpwindow*, *tll*, *tos*, *id*, *dgmlen*, *iplen*, *icmptype*, *icmpcode*, *icmpseq*.

Table 5.6: Common List of Extracted Headers for TCP, UDP and ICMP packets.

TCP	UDP	ICMP
Src-IP	Src-IP	Src-IP
Dst-IP	Dst-IP	Dst-IP
Src-Port	Src-Port	ICMP-code
Dst-Port	Dst-Port	ICMP-Type
protocol-Type	protocol-Type	protocol-Type
Packet-Length	Packet-Length	Packet-Length
TTL	TTL	TTL
SYN-ACK	Length	DF Flag
Window	Checksum	Timestamps

However, as shown in the Table 5.6, the features are extracted using Python and literature survey, Python and SAE unsupervised machine learning to derive proposed feature set depicted in Table 5.7, for 18 TCP flows, Table 5.8, for 15 UDP flows and Table 5.9, for 10 ICMP flows.

Table 5.7: Feature Extraction from TCP Flows.

1	No of packets in each incoming TCP-flows
2	No of packets in each outgoing TCP-flows
3	Change of packets in each incoming TCP-flows
4	Change of packets in each outgoing TCP-flows
5	No of distinctive Src-IP per incoming TCP-flows
6	Change of of distinctive Src-IP per incoming TCP-flows
7	Total Bytes per incoming TCP-flows
8	Total Bytes per outgoing TCP-flows
9	Symmetric windows length per incoming TCP-flows
10	Distinctive windows length per incoming TCP-flows
11	No of symmetric incoming TCP-flows
12	No of asymmetric incoming TCP-flows
13	No of symmetric TTL values per incoming TCP-flows
14	No of asymmetric TTL values per incoming TCP-flows
15	No of asymmetric src-ports per incoming TCP-flows
16	Change of asymmetric src-ports per incoming TCP-flows
17	No of asymmetric Dst-ports per incoming TCP-flows
18	Change of asymmetric Dst-ports per incoming TCP-flows
18	No of $Dst - ports \leq 1024$ per incoming TCP-flows

Table 5.8: Feature Extraction from UDP Flows.

1	No of packets in each incoming UDP-flows
2	No of packets in each outgoing UDP-flows
3	Change of symmetric packets each incoming UDPflows
4	Change of asymmetric packets each incoming UDP-flows
5	No different Src-IP in each incoming UDP-flows
6	Total Bytes per incoming UDP-flows
7	Total Bytes per outgoing UDP-flows
8	Total packets per incoming UDP-flows
9	Total packets per outgoing UDP-flows
10	No different Src-ports in each incoming UDP-flows
11	No different Dst-ports in each incoming UDP-flows
12	No different <i>Dstports</i> ≤ 1024 per incoming UDP-flows
13	No different <i>Dst - ports</i> < 1024 per incoming UDP flows
14	No of asymmetric TTL values per incoming UDP flows
15	No of symmetric TTL values per incoming UDP-flows

Table 5.9: Feature Extraction from ICMP Flows.

1	No of ICMP-flows in each incoming flows
2	No of ICMP-flows in each outgoing flows
3	No of symmetric incoming ICMP-flows
4	No of symmetric Src-IP per incoming ICMP-flows
5	Total Bytes per incoming ICMP-flows
6	Total Bytes per outgoing ICMP-flows
7	No of packets per incoming ICMP-flows
8	No of packets per outgoing ICMP-flows
9	Symmetric windows length per incoming TCP-flows
10	Different TTL values per incoming ICMP-flows

5.5 Evaluation

Our model mainly focuses to attack capture-failure rate with the false-negative rate. False-negative rate is highly used performance metrics of IDS systems, it is represented as when IDS systems fail to classify attacks that have been taken place on it. Our overall proposed model is based to improve the capture-failure rate and to provide a comparison between sampling approaches, which is another performance metric in this chapter. The capture-failure rate implies as unawareness of the system to detect the attack on network infrastructure. This chapter takes advantages of both sampling techniques with SDN flexibility such as sFlow sampling and adaptive polling sampling inside OVS switches with Ryu controller. In this work, the standard amount of sampled traffic flows are utilized with proposed sampling rather than deep packets sampling. In contrast, deep packets sampling utilizes many available network and processing resources. The detailed systematic overview of our proposed model is presented in this section.

Figure 5.3: Proposed System in SDN.

5.5.1 Experimental Setup

Our experiment is performed into two different virtual machines, which is created with Intel (R) Xeon (R) X5560 CPU with 2.88 GHz processor and 16 GB RAM (DDR3 ECC-Registered Memory PC3-12800) running TensorFlow 1.4 on Ubuntu LTS 16.04-64 bit. VMware Player is used for creating both virtual machines such as VM1 with 192.168.232.x1 IP address and VM2 with 192.168.232.x2 IP address. The VM1 machine, uses network emulator tool such as Mininet tool for creating and customizing IoT network topology presented in Figure 6.3, sFlow sampling agents and adaptive polling intervals based sampling parameters are also implemented in Mininet based Open vSwitch (OVS). Snort-IDS as NIDS is utilized to actively collect sampled normal and malicious traffic streams, then Snort output plug-in creates csv data files with Barnyard2. In the same VM1, various malicious traffic of DDoS floods is emulated with Metasploit, hping3 and LOIC tool. However benign traffic is generated to evaluate our detection model. VM2 utilizes more tools and technologies, so more CPU processing and memory are assigned for flexible performance. In VM2, the model utilizes central SDN Ryu controller, and the SAE a deep neural network model for intrusion detection, which classifies traffic features and detects malicious traffic, this will be further discussed in results section with more details. Figure 5.4, represents the simplified flow diagram of our proposed design.

SDN Ryu controller centrally controls VM2 to install sampling policies and other

Figure 5.4: Flow diagram of proposed work.

network manipulations via Rest APIs configuration. VM1 is developed as data-plane and VM2 for control-plane, where VM1 communicates with VM2 by OpenFlow 1.3 protocol. The SDN Ryu controller manipulates and manages OpenFlow OVS switches in data-plane. The `ovs-ofctl` utility is used to insert new policies into switches table. The `ovs-ofctl` programme is used for OpenFlow switch administration and monitoring purpose, this programme is configured with north-bound APIs. SDN Ryu controller and Snort are integrated with each other, where Snort utilizes promiscuous enabled mode at `eth0` interface which helps to collect all network traffic and propagate these packets to OpenFlow switch via port mirroring. On `eth1`, Snort and Ryu socket with IP `192.168.232.x1` is configured for collecting packets remotely. Snort continuously propagates data towards control-plane with `192.168.232.x2` IP address, this enables detection algorithms to work with the collaboration of Snort.

In VM2, OVS is remotely managed by Ryu controller inside Mininet simulator. The Snort switch (`switch_snort.py`) application is programmed on top of Ryu controller, this supports Layer L2 switch coding and redirects all traffic via OpenFlow switches with promiscuous enabled mode, traffic is redirected between one of the Snort port and Ryu (Unix Socket) port. The Snort supports two integration option with Ryu controller, the first option is very basic only suitable for demonstration purpose. On the other hand, we utilizing the second option, where Snort is implemented with a remote machine. SDN Ryu controller receives alerts from Snort with `unixsock` network socket. When the Snort uses `unixsock = false`, then it receives all network packets for forwarding to Barnyard2 log file. This is the main reason to manage data-plan of network and hosts packets within main SDN controller. The tools utilized in our work are presented in Table 5.11.

In VM2, Tcpreplay tool is also implemented for the purpose of classifying and analyzing benign and malicious traffic individually. Addition to this, Python is used for manipulating and saving computed features from each packet acquisition intervals. Finally, the dataset file is categorized into training and testing datasets. Table 5.10 depicts the dataset distribution, all feature values are positive non-zero numbers.

Minmax normalisation is a standardisation technique, which is capable to linearly transforms x to $y = (x - \min) / (\max - \min)$, where \min and \max values represent the minimum and maximum values belong to X , it can be seen that, if $x = \min$, then $y = 0$, and when $x = \max$, then $y = 1$. This includes mapping the minimum value in X to 0 and mapping the average value in X to 1. And the entire spectrum of X values from \min to \max is assigned to the spectrum 0 to 1. If the quantity distribution is natural, it should be standardized, otherwise, the data should be normalized. Once the amount size comes between the ranges of (10s, 100s), which stabilize the dimensionality of features, it also avoids too much compression. This model utilizes

unity based feature scaling, Min-Max normalization approach to breaks all real-valued into 0 and 1 ranges as shown in equation 5.9, where model uses 60 seconds time (start to end) fitting slot to extract features [183]. After data normalization, proposed work collaboratively works with widely used DNN model of SAE to detect malicious and normal activities.

$$P(X)_{normalized(0\ to\ 1)} = \frac{P(X)_i - P(X)_{min}}{P(X)_{max} - P(X)_{min}} \quad (5.9)$$

$$P(X)_{max} = \text{maximum value range in } P(X)_i$$

$$P(X)_{min} = \text{minimum value range in } P(X)_i$$

$$P(X)_i = \text{total set of observed values}$$

Table 5.10: Representation of normal and attack records for training and testing.

CSV Traffic Class 1	sFlow Traffic	
	Training	Testing
Normal	45,263	12,528
<i>All_{attacks}</i>	34,193	7,347
CSV Traffic Class 2	Adaptive Polling Sampling Traffic	
	Training	Testing
Normal	43,895	11,259
<i>All_{attacks}</i>	35,097	8,564

5.5.2 Results

This section mainly focuses on performance comparison of detection rate of DDoS within sFlow and adaptive polling based sampling approaches, the overall performance of the proposed mechanism is evaluated on the datasets presented in Table 5.10. Mathematically, the 80/20 law is a component sparsity principle, also known as the Pareto distribution [216], which says that roughly 80 percent of the results come from 20 percent of the causes for certain cases. Followed by the Pareto principle of distribution, we have divided our total datasets into training and testing as shown in Table 5.10.

As discussed in Section IV, traffic sampling can either be deployed as packet-oriented or time oriented. The control-plane uses SAE detection model with sampled and extracted features of data-plane and it also comprises of major sampling policies, flow policies, and OVS insertion rules.

In order to get feasible classification results, this work uses SAE, a simple DNN model with extracted features. Firstly, features based input vectors acquired from sFlow and adaptive polling based sampling datasets, then SAE applied to classify benign and malicious traffic. However, this type of dataset comprises a higher level

Table 5.11: Test-bed tools and technologies.

Technologies	Name (Version)	Description
Simulator	Mininet-2.2.1 [177]	Popular network emulator to create virtual switches, hosts and networks links. A realistic test-bed created on VM1 virtual machine, running real kernel, ovs switches, and application code. Data-plane and control-plane communicate with OpenFlow 1.3 protocol.
SDN-controller	Ryu-4.27[181]	Ryu is component based SDN development framework with well defined API to cater flexible and innovative network-management and control-applications. It is open source, works with OpenFlow, Netconf, OF-config etc. Ryu code is written with Python which is available under Apache 2.0 license
IDS-Sensor	Snort[178]	Open source, widely used intrusion detection system with various active detection and logging facility.
Traffic-Analyzer	Tcpreplay	Open source UNIX based utility to edit and replaying network traffic, helps to rewrite and classify traffic at various layers on client and server side. Specially works with IDS/IPS systems
Attacking Tools	hping3[180] LOIC [213]	Well known freely available application, mainly used for network stress testing with DoS/DDoS attacks emulation. These tools can emulate huge TCP, UDP, HTTP-GET floods to specific target via IP address of target machines.
Development-kit	Python-2.4	Python a well known scripting language is utilized for script development specially for routing flow management, traffic sampling and ovs-switches.

of unbalanced features, and in the real network there are very small portions of malicious traffic as compared to emulated malicious traffic. Most of the learning models create alarming situations for such reasons. Due to this fact, huge numbers of neural network models classify all traffic streams as benign and malicious as traffic noises. To achieve higher accuracy, a vast variety of approaches can be deployed to overcome this situation [217]. As a solution to this case, we utilize weighted loss functions to balance unbalanced feature frequencies, this work also utilizes selected feasible metrics such as *precision*, *recall* and *F1 score* on dataset specified in Table 5.10. These metrics provide useful information about the goodness of the detection rate of the proposed model. These parameters are depicted with the help of a confusion matrix.

Our study uses the two different dataset portions, based on sFlow and adaptive polling sampling as discussed before for training and testing, each dataset is divided into training and test sets followed by 80% of training and cross-validation and 20% of test sets. This work uses a combination of benign and normal datasets for training and cross-validation purpose, to make detection approach more realistic and enabling generalization for detecting new attack behaviours, which is a very crucial aspect for network security. Considering all these factors, the proposed solution employs a deep learning model with the appropriate classification. Where the model achieves great results as feasible evidence of our proposed study. For this mandatory purpose, we set SAE domain with only three hidden-layers with encoding/decoding elements of 10, 5, 2, all three layers processed following by descending order of 22-10-5-2-1, 22-10-5-1, 22-10-1. The hyper parameters and tested numeric values are depicted in Table 5.12.

Table 5.12: Proposed model configuration values.

Hyper parameters	Model values
Total hidden-layers	1, 2, 3
Hidden-layers size	10, 5, 2
Learning-rate	0.1, 0.01, 0.001
Activation-function	Sigmoid
Dropout	0.75, 0.50
Batch-size	100, 50, 50

This chapter utilizes the two-class classification model for normal and attack class including TCP, UDP and ICMP traffic streams. For better comparison, the SAE detection model is employed individually for sFlow and adaptive polling based datasets. After that the evaluation of the precision, recall, F-measure, accuracy and false-positive values is carried out for both traffic classes, these values are derived from confusion matrix shown in Figure 6.4. Value of comparison is depicted in Figure 5.6. Figure 6.4 presents evaluation results of sFlow and adaptive polling based sampling approaches, where, classification model evaluated with two class model separately for sFlow and adaptive polling sampling considering TCP, UDP and ICMP DDoS attacks into single class against normal class traffic. Figure 6.4 (a) confusion matrix for sFlow based two-class classification achieves nearly 95% of TP detection rate with only 4% of FP rate, on the other hand in Figure 6.4 (b), adaptive polling based sampling detection rate of TP rate was around 92%, whereas FP rate was higher than 8%. Figure 5.6 depicts detailed comparison between both sampling approaches by using standard classifier parameters as it can be observed from Figure 5.6, DNN model with sFlow class achieved accuracy of 91% with greater *F_{measure}* values of 88.10%. Similarly DNN model with adaptive polling based sampling achieved accuracy of 89% with 85% of *F_{measure}* values. Precision values for sFlow and adaptive polling based sampling was 95% and 92% respectively. Recall values were also nearly 5% higher for sFlow as compared to adaptive polling. Table 5.13 depicts the model summary of evaluation in term of Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F-scores, TP-rate, TN-rate, FP-rate and FN-rate.

Figure 5.7 depicts two classes ROC curve to provide overall DNN model detection performance, with sFlow based implementation model achieves greater sensitivity probability values of 94% for positive model test outcomes, however, this implementation model receives less than 4% of negative outcomes of DNN model test. In contrast, the polling based implementation model receives positivity of DNN model at 92% values of sensitivity with nearly 8% of negativity values of specificity. Moreover, the overall performance of sFlow based implementation was satisfying with our proposed DNN model in testbed in various network terms such as packets flows,

(a) sFlow Sampling.

(b) Adaptive Polling based Sampling.

Figure 5.5: Confusion Matrix of 2 Class Classification.

network, CPU and memory and network overhead.

Table 5.13: Summary of two class model evaluation for sFlow and adaptive polling sampling.

Sampling types	TP	TN	FP	FN	Accuracy-value	Precision-value	R-value	F-value
sFlow	95%	89%	4%	11.44%	91%	95%	83%	88.10%
Adaptive Polling	92%	74%	8.89%	24%	89%	92%	78%	85%

5.5.3 System Performance Evaluation

This section depicts the comparison of average CPU utilization for sFlow based and adaptive polling based sampling approaches between data-plane to control-plane locations, which is considered as highly influencing factor for detection model. Figure 5.8 (a) presents the different CPU usages such as CPU(TCP), CPU(UDP), CPU(ICMP), CPU(All).

The summary of CPU utilisation for sFlow and adaptive polling sampling with time is depicted in Table 5.14. The proposed model receives TCP, UDP and ICMP attack with 100 Kb/s to 600 Kb/s. Overall 290 M Bytes of total malicious traffic injected to observe CPU utilization individually only at control-plane after sampling,

Figure 5.6: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F-sores and FP-rate for two class model.

Figure 5.7: ROC Curve of 2 Class Classification.

(a) sFlow Sampling.

(b) Adaptive Polling based Sampling.

Figure 5.8: CPU Utilization of Controller over time.

Table 5.14: Summary of total CPU utilization of controller.

CPU Utilization(%)								
sFlow Sampling					Adaptive Polling Sampling			
Time(sec)	CPU(TCP)	CPU(UDP)	CPU(ICMP)	CPU(All)	CPU(TCP)	CPU(UDP)	CPU(ICMP)	CPU(All)
20	36	22	21	57	30	22	29	80
40	39	33	17	60	39	29	31	63
60	29	30	18	42	25	56	21	65
80	38	40	16	50	44	21	33	69
100	22	31	23	53	33	50	32	72
120	27	57	28	70	49	37	37	64
140	55	13	27	74	11	10	18	56

Table 5.15: Summary of total network load of controller.

Controller Network Load (KB/s)				
sFlow Sampling			Adaptive Polling Sampling	
Time(sec)	Control-plane (packets)	Data-plane (packets)	Control-plane (packets)	Data-plane (packets)
20	130	330	110	330
40	357	1400	250	1400
60	470	1078	430	1078
80	366	7600	380	7600
100	378	600	330	600
120	358	650	311	650
140	578	702	230	702

During CPU utilization, our model experienced random spikes, which were caused due to buffer memory overflow of CPU cache, our model was carried under Intel (R) Xeon (R) X5560 CPU with 2.88 GHz processor and 16 GB RAM, CPU has only 8MB cache memory, inside virtual machines, our model was consuming almost all buffer memory. from Figure 5.8 (a), it can be observed that CPU(UDP) only uses 29% of CPU utilization with 2164 encoding and decoding threads instructions. The CPU(TCP) utilizes only 38% CPU with 2479 CPU threads, In ICMP the CPU is constantly used at 26% with 2011 threads. Due to sFlow sampling, it can be observed that overall CPU utilization reduced from 90% to 52%. Similarly, in Figure 5.8 (b), based on adaptive polling sampling, CPU(TCP) utilization increased from 38% to 42% with threads execution of 2659. CPU (UDP) utilization also raised to 37% with 2551 threads. CPU utilization for ICMP stood at 6% higher than sFlow with some threads increment. However, in polling based sampling overall CPU usage was also higher as 74.25% during TCP, UDP, ICMP malicious data flow due to the nature of being calculating flows and packets equation individually in various switches.

Figure 5.9 depicts the network load of sFlow sampling and adaptive polling based sampling between two virtual machines VM1 data-plane and VM2 control-plane. In VM1 data-plane(packets) represents injected traffic flows before sampling, and control-plane(packets) represents flows received by the controller after sampling. The network overhead calculated with malicious packets of TCP, UDP, ICMP flooding attacks. Malicious traffic emulation rate was gradually changed from 150 KB/s to 1500 KB/s, which was kept the common flow for sFlow and adaptive based polling

(a) sFlow Sampling.

(b) Adaptive Polling based Sampling.

Figure 5.9: Controller Network Load over time.

sampling to calculate network overhead, where Ntopng tool is used to analyze network manipulating facts. Summary of the controller network load with time is also presented in Table 5.15. As shown in Figure 5.9 (a), once controller connected to sFlow agent enabled switches then it received accumulated average packets flows of 340 KB/s after sFlow sampling, due to link utilization and network queue packet flow was fluctuating nearly 500 KB/s after every 40 seconds. The controller received total control-plane (packets) 192 MB out of 290 MB. Similarly, as we can observe from Figure 5.9 (b), the controller was receiving accumulated average packets at the rate of 244KB/s, Due to polling-based sampling, controller received total 140MB out of 290 MB. Moreover, adaptive polling based sampling measures higher network load due to the fact that this sampling requires individual calculations and queering FlowStats Request inside all switches flow table, it utilizes more CPU which make flow slower to reach at controller detection model.

5.6 Discussion

Our proposed system is based on IoT nodes sampling which effectively works in collaboration of SAE deep neural network model. It collects flows from data-plane via

packet based sampling (sFlow) and time-based (Adaptive Polling) sampling respectively. Overall our model has clear advantage of detecting the enormous amount of malicious traffic either with packet-based or flow based sampling approaches which reduce the Snort and deep learning models overhead processing, as intrusion detection systems are limited with processing and detection capabilities. Similarly, DNN models are also demanding more training time and complex configurations during the event of heavy flows. This enabled us to parse all crucial malicious and benign traffic streams to classify and label correctly. In case of mitigation or blocking any switches or hosts unwanted incoming flow would be more accurate and reliable task for SDN controller with simple northbound APIs. In collaboration, an SAE model individually performs on the attack and normal classes, which successfully achieve accuracy nearly 99% on normal traffic to qualify our proposed model parameters before our proposed model test.

Most of the common features from both of proposed sampling extracted with 22 input vectors shown in Table 5.7, 5.8, 5.9. The proposed solution derives common features following the literature of [183] then merge all of the testbed features with only 22 feature vectors class. As observed from experimental results, sFlow achieved a higher detection rate of TP = 95%, TN = 90% with less than 4% of FP rate, whereas polling based implementation detection was around 5% less as compared to sFlow. Overall experiments represent that sFlow based implementation in our proposed work has significantly higher detection accuracy with minimal CPU and network load. There are some important factors that support this point, such as sFlow is flow oriented sampling technology, which utilizes sFlow agents in OVS switches with a sampling rate of 1/28, 1/ 64, 1/128, 1/256, 1/512 for s1 to s5 respectively. In this way, accurate sampled traffic was flexibly flowing to Snort IDS at the controller. The controller received around 192 M Bytes of total packets within 20 minutes of packets injection, the controller used 50% of total CPU overhead. On contrary the polling based implementation, we can observe that controller only receives 140 M Bytes within 20 minutes of packets injection, which is at least 27% fewer packets than sFlow at detection engine of Snort at the controller. Due to the fact of adaptive polling uses higher resource consumption to manipulate each packet inside switches and constantly sends each packet once match polling query. In this way, external traffic collectors have to wait for the next packets. Moreover, this implementation used 74% of total CPU, which is significantly higher for 140 M bytes of network packets as in real-time existing networks there large number of packets flows passing through ingress and egress ports of autonomous and service providers network.

Chapter 6

Entropy based Features Distribution for Anti-DDoS Model in SDN

6.1 Introduction

This Chapter:

depicts a fast and an effective DDoS detection mechanism in the SDN networks, in which we have deployed generalised entropy calculation by combining well-known Shannon entropy and Reyni entropy which enables to distribute most specific characteristics of DDoS traffic to deal heavy DDoS traffic. We collect data-plane traffic with signature-based Snort detection, then we analyse collected traffic with entropy formula. Secondly, we improve the detection accuracy of the deep learning model by utilising specific malicious distributed features.

Our modern technological society has become dependant on the majority of on-line services and Internet technology, these services have become nonexclusive life routine for almost everyone. Many of us check our official emails and social services as the very first thing in the early morning. To be dependant on this kind of services also introduced a large number of attacks on network services. The innovation of technologies also brought up new attacking tools for injecting numerous malicious attacks, however, network defenders use up to date and most sophisticated defence systems for their safeguard. Contrary to other attacks, Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks are most common amongst them, these DDoS are the extensions of traditional DoS attacks. These attacks make targeted services unavailable by sending overloaded false requests on service providers. After resources being depleted,

the service providers become unable to serve its potential legitimate users. Nowadays, DDoS is a commonly used attacking method which inflicts heavy financial losses after being attacked [218].

With the modern advancement of virtualization-based computing, such as Software Defined Networking (SDN) infrastructure has been widely adopted for a security solution in various service provider industries [219]–[221]. In SDN based networks, most of controlling decisions are carried out separate entity called control-plane [222]. This decoupling approach has brought enormous benefits to network management and caters a feasible and effective solution to improve network efficiency [223]. However, decoupling of data-plane and control-plane can guarantee to deploy a flexible and scale-able test-bed to meet the day by day ever-changing modern business need. Moreover, logical centralised architecture and its program ability approach enable the controller of SDN to detect malicious activities flexibly, but the controller itself becomes vulnerable for DDoS attackers [224].

Most of the forwarding decisions are managed by the controller, the table in OpenFlow based switches consistently searches new packets arrival, with a successful match, flow action is performed if packet_in doesn't match then it is propagated to SDN main control-plane for detailed analysis. In case of DDoS attack, if the arrival rate of packet_in is significantly higher then control-plane resources start to diminish soon, which results in discontinuity with data-plane and may overwhelm controller. Although a single point failure due to overhead could defunct whole infrastructure [225].

Accordingly, current security problems, DDoS attack is believed as one of the most urgent and hardest security issues [226]. So far, there are plenty DDoS detection approaches including [109], [120], [136], [151], [159], [227], [228], in SDN have been proposed. Most of the previous studies more likely focused on attack detection and mitigation method. Currently, the majority of work is based on time-based periodic detection. However, choosing a proper time-period to detect an attack is very hard. If a large time-period is selected for attack launch then response time for detecting attack will be increased, this creates extremely large attack overload over deployed switches and its major SDN controller. In contrast, if the time threshold is set with very low range then deployed attack detection module will continuously run, which unnecessarily consumes controller resources such as CPU, network up-stream and down-stream bandwidth. It also affects controller efficiency.

However, congestion at the controller is one of the major issues that could easily lower down the performance of deployed mechanism and easily left the entire infrastructure vulnerable especially for DDoS intruders. Currently, most of the researchers have not attracted to improve the accuracy of the controller in SDN, as most of the detection modules work from the SDN controller. However, it is mandatory to rec-

tify SDN controller efficiency with available characteristics of SDN. To solve the aforementioned issues, we propose a new-fashioned anti-DDoS detection mechanism with entropy-based feature distribution in SDN. Our detection model comprises on following four major units, such as Snort alert based Features, Entropy Calculation, Feature Distribution and Traffic Processing finally selecting machine learning classifiers. We summarised our contribution as below:

- An effective anti-DDoS detection mechanism is proposed, to speed up major SDN controller unit accuracy so that deep learning model easily classifies trade-off between benign and unknown malicious code.
- We have distributed specific traffic features with generalised entropy estimation of Shannon and Reyni formulas.
- By utilising Snort-Ryu implementation with entropy calculation, we acquired non-redundant traffic features.
- As detection classifiers, we utilise well known deep learning classifiers such as Stacked Auto Encoder (SAE) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to compare the accuracy and False-Positive alerts with 30% and 60% attack rate with normal traffic.

Rest of the Chapter is organised as follow: Sections 6.2 represent the related literature work and background in details. Our novel based DDoS detection model is provided with details in Section 6.3. However, experimental results evaluations are depicted followed by Sections 6.4.

6.2 Background Overview

In this section, the mechanism for DDoS attacks detection and major implementations of the model is depicted with details. The detection of the model relies on the specific DDoS feature distribution approach, which is achieved by generalised entropy (GE) calculation with Shannon and Reyni formulas, details of entropy distribution is provided in this section. Our model comprises of major stages: including data acquisition with Snort-Ryu, feature distribution with entropy calculation, data processing and traffic classification with two well-known classifiers such as Stacked Auto Encoder (SAE) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN).

6.2.1 Snort-Ryu based data acquisition

This section comprises on the huge amount of live datasets acquisition from the network, due to heavy network traffic human inspection and data analysis is unman-

Table 6.1: Existing DDoS detection literature survey in SDN.

Author	Year	Description	Methods	Detection	Mitigation	Analysis
[151]	2010	Proposed work uses six SDN based traffic features for detecting DDoS.	Neural network model,SOM.	✓		✓
[164]	2011	this work utilises different SDN approaches to collect DDoS traffic.	Maximum entropy, TRW-CB, Rate-limiting.	✓		✓
[227]	2013	Proposed approach lower down the control-plane and data-plane overhead.	Interface migration technique.	✓	✓	✓
[127]	2014	Flow-based traffic utilised to classify DDoS portscan, and worm propagation.	Entropy-based detection	✓	✓	✓
[163]	2015	To reduce requests burden by utilising scheduling technique in SDN.	Malicious traffic redirection approach.	✓		✓
[159]	2015	Model running on edge switch to detect DDoS with low control-plane burden.	Entropy-based Algorithm.	✓		✓
[162]	2016	To utilise Shanon entropy estimation to detect early-stage DDoS attacks.	Attack sources bypass method.	✓	✓	✓
[165]	2016	Sequential Probability Ratio Test used to classify high rate DDoS.	SPRT method.	✓	✓	✓
[152]	2016	ML-based approach with SDN flows to identify and mitigate the attack.	ML-SOM approach.	✓	✓	✓
[229]	2017	Proposed method is used to mitigate TCP flooding attack in SDN.	TCP request monitoring, Malicious hosts blocking.	✓	✓	
[150]	2017	multi-vector DDoS traffic analysis and detection system in deep learning.	SAE, deep learning.	✓		✓
[149]	2018	Extreme gradient algorithm utilised to detect DDoS traffic with low FP rate.	Machine learning model.	✓		

ageable. The Snort [230] is capable to be used as a signature-based detection engine or as a log_tcpdump module with various output files. Although, log_tcpdump can be utilised for storing test-bed datasets, which is limited to store the only 128MB of total packets. We extended storage module of Snort by implementing a Barnyard2 logfile. We have utilised Snort-Ryu modular implementation to collect the test-bed datasets. The Snort [230] engine consists on various traffic attributes such as *timestamp*, *sig_generator*, *sig_id*, *sig_rev*, *msg*, *proto*, *src*, *srcport*, *dst*, *dstport*, *ethsrc*, *ethdst*, *ethlen*, *tcpflags*, *tcpseq*, *tcpack*, *tcplen*, *tcpwindow*, *tll*, *tos*, *id*, *dgmlen*, *iplen*, *icmptype*, *icmpcode*, *icmpid*, *icmpseq*. Our proposed DDoS detection model based on feature distribution is dependant on the features such as time window, Protocol, Source IP, address, Source Port Address, Destination IP address, Destination Datagram length, Port address, Priority, etc. By utilising Snort, our model focuses to acquire relevant features in collaboration of entropy calculation. Snort utilises two different modes to capture unique and different features for malicious and benign network traffic. SM-1 mode depicted in Table 6.2 enables to collect malicious traffic features similarly SM-2 mode depicted in Table 6.2 is utilised for acquiring benign traffic features.

6.2.2 Entropy Calculation

The proposed methodology is depicted in Figure 6.2, to evaluate our research. The major aim of our model is to capture various types of DDoS attacks, for this purpose, this model mainly relies on the finding of most common attributes of the header of

Table 6.2: Two modes of Snort.

Description	Snort Two Modes	
	SM1 (Malicious)	SM2 (Benign)
TCP rules	20 signatures	8 signatures
UDP rules	10 signatures	6 signatures
ICMP rules	6 signatures	6 signatures

packets. One of the most common attributes is source IP addresses, which generate attacks. Once various types of features collected with SM-1 mode and SM2 mode, the proposed model take advantage of Shannon entropy estimation to generalise most relevant types of features that lead to successful DDoS attacks detection in SDN context. This model utilises $H_\alpha(Z)$ Shannon entropy formula to find out more accurate relevant features from Snort model. The uncertainty associated with probability distribution Z is calculated with higher values of entropy once probability distribution more randomly occurs in nature.

Addition to this least values of entropy is estimated in case of small uncertainty. The event distribution randomness is evaluated with Renyi entropy metric order with α , this enables Shannon entropy estimation towards more relevant features generalisation. The Generalised Entropy (GE) of discrete variables Z with possible number of outcomes such as, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n , which can be accumulated i.e. $\sum_{i=1}^N Z_i = 1, Z_i \geq 0$, then entropy of Renyi with order α can be defined as below:

$$H_\alpha(Z) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log_2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^N p_i^\alpha \right) \quad (6.1)$$

Here values of $\alpha \geq 0$ and $Z_i \geq 0$. Different entropy calculation is performed in order to quantifying various α orders. With substitute of $\alpha = 0$, we get maximum generated information and with substitute of $\alpha = 1$ we achieve GE values, which is given below:

$$H_1(Z) = \sum_{i=1}^N p(z_i) \log_2 \frac{1}{p(z_i)} - \sum_{i=1}^N p(z_i) \log_2 p(z_i) \quad (6.2)$$

Here, $p(z_i) = \text{probability}(Z = z_i)$ is the i th value of Z . The Eq.6.2 is known as Shannon Entropy, when we put $\alpha = 2$, then GE expression is depicted as:

$$H_2(Z) = -\log_2 \sum_{i=1}^N p_{i=1}^{\alpha=2} \quad (6.3)$$

The Eq: 6.3, is known as Renyi entropy estimation, the authors of [231] have depicted relationship between Renyi and Shannon, where GE estimation values more likely relies on α values, such as $\alpha = 1$ or $\alpha = 2$. However, GE values exponentially increase with various probability distribution as compared to Shannon entropy probability [232], [233]. Following this work, we classify our traffic as a normal and malicious probability distribution. To get GE values, our work also manipulates both different probability distribution values with a combination of attack and normal properties. Once we get higher uncertainty events then probability results in more GE information as compared to Shannon entropy [234].

By adjusting α values in GE, we can get different values of entropy's to meet our DDoS detection methodology. This chapter utilises Information Distance (ID) to estimate events similarities, it is legacy methodology, which is depicted with two different probability distribution such as

$P_{ID} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$ and $Q_{ID} = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n\}$ as below:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N p_{i=1} = \sum_{i=1}^N q_{i=1} = [1 - 0] \quad (6.4)$$

The ID equation can be derived as below

$$D_{\alpha}(P_{ID}, Q_{ID}) = \frac{1}{1 - \alpha} \log_2 \left(\sum_{id=1}^N p_{id}^{\alpha} q_{id}^{1-\alpha} \right) \quad (6.5)$$

Information Distance (ID) always focuses non negative values, such as $\alpha \geq 0$. However, if both probability distribution occurrences are similar then $D_{\alpha}(P_{ID}, Q_{ID}) = 0$. GE entropy expression can be achieved by varying α orders as given below:

$$D_1(P_{ID}, Q_{ID}) = -\log_2 \left(\sum_{id=1}^N p_{id} \right), \Rightarrow \alpha = 1 \quad (6.6)$$

$$D_2(P_{ID}, Q_{ID}) = -\sum_{id=1}^N p_{id} \log_2 \left(\frac{p_{id}}{q_{id}} \right), \Rightarrow \alpha = 2 \quad (6.7)$$

The Eq: 6.7 known as Kullback-Leibler divergence (KL) distance. This equation is utilised for measuring information distance with identical, triangular inequalities and symmetrical properties of KL divergence. However, GE and ID both use these mentioned properties for DDoS detection to rectify DDoS most relevant traffic features with the help of Eq:6.3 and Eq: 6.5. In our approach, probability distribution is calculated by $H_{\alpha}(Z)$ as shown in Eq: 6.1, where z_i depicts packets header variation between source and destination communication junctions comprises of *Src-IP*, *Src-Port*, *Dest-IP*, *Dest-Port*, *Source-Bytes*, *Destination-Bytes*, *TTL*, *Flags*, *proto*, *Distinct Datagrams*. In Figure 6.1, a flow diagram is provided for the distribution

Table 6.3: Selected Traffic Features with GE.

Features	Description
Src-IP (src_{IP})	Source IP address
Src-Port (src_{Port})	Source Port
Dest-IP (dst_{IP})	Destination IP address
Dest-Port (dst_{Port})	Destination Port
Source-Bytes (dst_{Bytes})	Total Bytes from source
Destination-Bytes (dst_{Bytes})	Total Bytes to destination
TTL Flow-Duration (TTL_{FD})	Time To Live duration
Flags	TCP, UDP, HTTP, ICMP flags
Proto ($prot$)	Types of various protocol
Distinct Datagrams ($Datagrams_{\Delta}$)	Various Datagrams values

of features. This is achieved by combining Shannon entropy and Reyni entropy formula. Our proposed work utilises probability distribution measuring approach to generalised most common relevant features from DDoS and malicious packet header. We manipulated all incoming packets with GE and ID metric to formulate our SDN based test-bed network to effectively detect DDoS traffic. Major aim focuses to lower down redundant features with GE and ID entropy estimation such as:

In DDoS detection event, the packet flowing rate is significantly higher than benign traffic, subsequently, packet diversity is also changing to generate entropy. In real-time traffic which is a complex form of different data rate, which remains stable with packet diversity and it also results irrelevant data pattern flows due to different traffic services. However, this is why entropy values are exponentially changed w.r.t to each second. Due to the fact of such variation, setting a proper threshold to detect DDoS in the network is unmanageable.

6.2.3 Feature Distribution and Traffic Processing

This section depicts major features selections and processing of datasets for our effective DDoS detection model, a major focus of selecting features rely on GE and ID entropy estimation to qualify relevant features as discussed before. However, an effective DDoS classifier needs many important kinds of traffic features distribution. In reality, this kind of traffic anomalies randomly changes during the distribution of most feasible addresses, ports, data length etc in an observed traffic area. The classification of traffic is depicted in Table 6.3, which is achieved by distributing more specific feature from test-bed datasets with the help of Shannon and Reyni joint entropy.

We developed dataset to evaluate our proposed method, our dataset is a combination of real-time legitimate data and synthesised malicious traffic, which is emulated with DDoS attacking tools comprises of Metasploit tools, Scapy, HPing and

Low Orbit Ionic Cannon (LOIC). We run Scapy and HPing DDoS scripts with various attributes of DDoS from the remote virtual machine as shown in Figure 6.2. For the validation purpose, we simulate various DDoS attacks reflections on widely targeted ports. However, most important realistic network traces are less publicly available due to privacy concern and another problem with real traces is to label properly which require some manual entries. With the help of deep domain knowledge and feasible tools and methodology, this approach enables to create realistic dataset.

Our proposed model calculates and classify benign and malicious traffic using entropy estimation following by two major components as, firstly, Windows size, we have utilised number of packet received as windows size parameter, where entropy values are estimated based on incoming packets occurrences with windows size, such as, if number of frequencies for each (dst_{IP}) is equitably and stably distributed then maximum value of entropy is established. If there is a sudden deviation such as rapid decrements in entropy values for the same network results possible malicious traffic flow event. Similarly, we also calculate average entropy values with the help of Algorithm 2 for all features, which are depicted in Table 6.3. SDN program-ability approach enables in collaboration with GE and ID to rectify specific features with more malicious attributes. Algorithm 2 helps to compute average entropy values and ID values. Secondly, we have utilised two threshold values, one δ_1 to calculate entropy and δ_2 to calculate ID. However, GE and ID are calculated for benign and malicious traffic by using Eq: 6.5, such as if $ID \geq \delta_2$ or $H_\alpha(Z) \leq \delta_1$.

Algorithm 2 Entropy-based feature distribution.

- 1: **Input:** Traffic data, Feature set S, δ_1 δ_2
 - 2: **Ensure Output:** AverageEntropy GE, ID hash-table H_{tb} (src_{IP}), (src_{Port}), (dst_{IP}), (dst_{Port}), (src_{Bytes}), (dst_{Bytes}), (src_{TTL}), (dst_{TTL})
 - 3: $TW \leftarrow 3 \text{ min}$
 - 4: $H_{tab} \leftarrow \{S\}$
 - 5: **for all** $IF \in H_{tb}$ **do return** True find GE, ID of both flows with Eq: 6.1
 - 6: **if** incoming packets $\in TW$ **do** search in S
 - 7: **else**
 - 8: **if** $ID \geq \delta_2$ and $Z_\alpha(IF_{at})$ or $Z_\alpha(IF_{be}) \leq \delta_1$ then do;
 - 9: Utilise $p(z_i) \leftarrow (\sum_i^N z_i)/N$ Estimating mass function probability
 - 10: Utilise $H_i(z) \leftarrow H(z)/\log n$ Entropy normalisation
 - 11: Utilise $H_{tab} \leftarrow H_{tab} \cup H_i(z)$
 - 12: **end**
 - 13: AverageEntropy (GE, ID) $\leftarrow \text{sum } H_{tab}/4$
 - 14: **end**
-

In the Algorithm 2, entropy estimation based pseudo-code is depicted which works with time-based sliding. The Algorithm 2 initialises with time windows size setting, which effectively maintains resources utilisation and network flow deviations.

Figure 6.1: Flowchart of features distribution in SDN-Ryu-controller.

We have used only three minutes time slot, as using larger time needs more resources for processing and storage. The algorithm 2 produces average output with estimated entropy of feature set S , which uses only two threshold such as Lower δ_1 and upper δ_2 for every S feature order.

The flows are evaluated within fixed intervals of time (TW = 3 as default every 3 min). Our approach utilizes the bidirectional flows, according to some research work of [235], unidirectional flows can result in biased and redundant outcomes [236]. The values of TW as fixed time intervals can be adjusted according to the numbers of features.

Major aim focuses to classify and maintain very specific features from incoming network. The rectified features from network connection are processed with the help of two feasible tasks of time slots, which has AverageEntropy values beyond normal ranges of δ_1, δ_2 . First of all, each abnormal subset of network traffic time slot is cleared by adding empty values rows to maintain a stable and unique column and row-based format. Secondly, cleared subsets are normalised by using *MinMax* function. The MinMax function generates feature values between scale ranges of 0 and 1 only. The *MinMax* feature normalisation function is depicted below:

$$Z_i^{nor} = \frac{z_i - \min(Z)}{\max(Z) - \min(Z)} \quad (6.8)$$

Where Z represents subsets of malicious traffic features and x_i represents most current values of Z to make normalisation. The term Z_i^{nor} is called final normalised features within the ranges of 0 and 1.

6.3 Experimental Setup

Our research experiment is conducted with three different virtual machines on a workstation by using Intel (R) Xeon (R) X5560 CPU with 2.88 GHz processor and 16 GB RAM (DDR3 ECC-Registered Memory PC3-12800MHZ), we run TensorFlow 1.4V and Mininet on supported Ubuntu LTS 16.04-64 bit operating system. The proposed functionality is illustrated in Figure 6.2. We have used VMware player to create these virtual machines such as VM1 with 192.168.202.x1 IP address, VM2 with 192.168.202.x2 IP address and VM3 with 192.168.202.x3 IP address. In VM1 machine, the network emulator tool such as Mininet tool is utilised for creating 6 hosts with 6 OpenFlow switches. As our work is based on simulation, which is carried out with MiniEdit tool. Kernel name-space properties of Mininet enables to prototype overall network environment within a single workstation. In Mininet, each process has own network interfaces, a routing table and so etc, these features enable to virtualise all network elements in Kernel. We connect these switches with

Figure 6.2: Proposed system of features distribution in SDN-Ryu-controller.

Ryu controller with the help of OpenFlow (OF) version 1.3.

In VM2, the Ryu controller is implemented with Snort-IDS as network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) and entropy algorithm, which is depicted in Section 6.2. This virtual machine plays a vital role to collect up networks traffic then apply entropy probabilities property for feature distribution. The Snort-IDS collects every *incoming_packet* in Barnayrd2 log file, then Ryu based GE and ID entropy estimation reduces redundant features from all network traces. Our detection model uses these rectified more specific features for the deep learning classifiers. We have distributed malicious features, also recorded benign traffic features in VM2. However, SDN major controller is deployed in VM2, which centrally handles all virtual machines of our test-bed. We install network policies via REST APIs. In our system, VM1 considered as data-plane and VM2 as a control-plane. We used *ovs-ofctl* utility to insert network policies in the switches table, addition to this, the *ovs-ofctl* utility is also utilised for monitoring and administration purpose between data-plane and control-plane.

In VM2, Ryu uses two network interfaces, one is set promiscuous mode on *eth0* interface to collect all OpenFlow traffic traces with Snort from VM1, while another *Eth1* is utilised as a port mirror for entropy calculation on Snort-Barnyard2 packets. Snort as NIDS plays a very vital role to acquire all raw network traffic from our

proposed model. Snort switch (*switch_snort.py*) application is implemented on the top layer of Ryu controller, which helps to support Layer L2 switch code and also redirects feasible traffic by using OpenFlow enabled promiscuous mode. The Ryu controller receives Snort alerts by utilising *unixsock = false*, which helps to collect network packets and then store log-file in Barnyard2, this property helps to manipulate data-plane traffic.

The VM3 utilised to launch malicious traffic remotely, which is depicted in Figure 6.2. This virtual machine utilises Scapy DDoS tool, Low Orbit Ion Cannon (LOIC) DDoS tools, and Kali Linux based Metasploit DDoS penetration testing frameworks such as Network Mapper (NMap) and Nessus Vulnerability Scanner. However penetration framework is used to ensure modern updated malicious traffic with some payloads, addition to this Metasploit framework is utilised for launching HTTP/TCP attacks. Moreover, Scapy tool is considered powerful and feasible to launch real flooding attacks but our proposed work uses Scapy tool and LOIC tool to launch various TCP, UDP ICMP malicious packets. To validate our proposed work, we perform an attack and normal traffic on same VM1 data-plane area which is directly connected on the main SDN controller with deployed parameters. A python script was created to generate attack traffic and benign traffic with Scapy tool, where we selected different hosts and source nodes during all injection. Our work also generates benign traffic by web activities such as searches and streaming.

The probability of GE and ID entropy is applied on all test-bed datasets to acquire more special features set with no redundant features attributes, which are provided in Table, 6.3. Tshark and Tcpreplay tools are utilised to manipulate and analyse benign and malicious traffic individually. Once malicious traffic traces are classified with GE and ID as depicted in Section 6.3, then we categorise normal and benign CSV files into training and the testing datasets shown in Table 6.5. All datasets have values of non-zeros numbers due to unity based *MinMax* normalisation. We break our proposed CSV datasets into *0s* and *1s* values, normalisation as defined in Eq: 6.8. After normalisation we will utilise Deep Neural Network (DNN) model to classify as an attack and non-attack values, this will be depicted into result section.

6.3.1 Performance Evaluation

This work presents a framework for detecting DDoS by using Shannon entropy and Reyni entropy to distribute the features in network. In this work Snort IDS is also used for collecting all data-plane traffic from test-bed. Snort with two different modes such as SM1 mode to acquire only malicious traffic and SM2 mode for acquiring benign traffic, these two modes are configured with specific signature

Table 6.4: Different Threshold values according to attack rate.

Parameters	20% Attack traffic	30% Attack traffic	60% Attack traffic	70% Attack traffic
Mean-value	0.7862	0.7388	0.6475	0.3426
St-deviation	0.0249	0.0289	0.0381	0.0389
Max-confidence	0.7806	0.7438	0.6518	0.3815
Min-confidence	0.7899	0.7318	0.6437	0.3699
δ values	0.7901	0.7636	0.6478	0.3910

rules of Snort detection engine as depicted in Table 6.2. After that, we process Snort alerts for feature distribution and generalisation. We utilised GE and ID matrix to analyse and calculate *Src-IP*, *Src-Port*, *Dest-IP*, *Dest-Port*, *Source-Bytes*, *Destination-Bytes*, *TTL*, *Flags*, *proto*, *Distinct Datagrams*.

In order to validate the effectiveness of model detection with proposed GE and ID feature distribution on the SDN controller, in proposed work, we are using two different scenarios. In the first one, we have used different attacking intensity, which is launched from a single host but remotely connected with Mininet data-plane VM1. We randomly generate attacks by using Scapy DDoS tool, LOIC tool and Metasploit penetration testing. The first scenario uses 20%, 30% and 40% attack rate. In the second scenario, we used 60% and 70% malicious traffic. In both scenarios, we generate benign traffic by using normal web searches and audio-video streaming. These searches are performed within VM1, where test-bed data-plane is created with Mininet. We maintain the attack intensity by using the following percentage equation:

$$Attack_{intensity} = \frac{Z_{attack}}{Z_{total}} \times 100 \quad (6.9)$$

In the above equation, Z_{attack} represents the attacks packets and Z_{total} represents total number packets flowing in our test-bed. We run our code around 10 times in each case for setting threshold values, we run a simulation 10 times. We found False-positive (FP) rate decrements but False-negative (FN) rate was stable. After that, we take threshold values. Table 6.4 represents threshold values during different attacks scenario. Following steps were carried out to set up threshold values:

- We calculate possible maximum attack traffic values, this is achieved by combining attack traffic mean entropy values and confidence interval values.
- After taking the difference between these values, we derive δ_1 values for mean and standard deviation values.

We performed our model with different traffic intensity rates such as the first case is evaluated with 30% and 40% of attack traffic with benign traffic, the second case is also evaluated with a 60% to 70% attack rate. The first case uses more benign

traffic and the second case uses more attack rates. The main reason to use different attack rates is to achieve more realistic results based on live network traffic. This can also prove that whether the proposed approach can effectively deal with massive DDoS attacks or not. However, from Table 6.4, it can be seen that a 60% attack rate has mean values of 0.6475, and 70% attack rate achieved 0.3526 mean values. The attack rate of 70% achieves the minimum uncertainty as compared to 30%, 40%, and 60% of attack traffic. Overall, once the network is under attack by massive DDoS floods, then our model effectively responds and distributes the common features more associated with DDoS nature. During DDoS attacks, malicious traffic ratio is significantly higher than benign.

In the Figure 6.3, we utilised 30% and 40% attack rate, while, Figure 6.4 uses 60% to 70% attack rate, each points on horizontal line represent windows size and vertical line represents entropy values, such as E_{values} . In these pictures, blue curve represents the normal traffic and orange curve represents malicious traffic. We stabilise network by injecting manipulated malicious traffic remotely and run algorithm 2 nearly 10 times. However, benign traffic entropy values was common in all attack rates as shown in Figure 6.3, 6.4.

We have considered different attack scenarios with a single victim and multiple victims, in single attack victim only single host is under attack. On the other hand multiple victims attacks, we have launched attacks on five hosts. During simulation time, The deviation and sudden drop of entropy values are considered to be used for traffic feature distribution. The rapid drop into flows represents malicious activity based on this phenomenon. From Fig 6.3, it can be seen that entropy values drop is least significant in case 30%, 40% of attack rate. However with 30% attack traffic, the mean entropy values are found as 0.77 on 53 windows interval, 0.72 on 57 windows interval, 0.76 on 63 windows interval, 0.72 on 71 windows interval. After every 25 windows intervals, entropy values dropped at average values of 0.72 to 0.77. With 40% attack rate, we found mean-values of entropy drops from 0.82 to 0.74 on windows on windows interval of 55, after every 25 consecutive intervals, mean values repeatedly fall between 0.73 to 0.71.

Moreover, there is significant entropy values change in the case of 60%, 70% of the attack rate. In Figure 6.4(a), the mean-value of entropy drops to 0.64% after every 25 windows intervals. Similarly, 6.4(b), the mean value of entropy exponentially drops to 0.35% on 55 windows interval after 25 consecutive windows intervals mean values constantly falls to 0.35%. As compared to benign traffic mean values, attack traffic means values drops around 0.50%, which is significantly higher with 70% attack rate through all experiments. This entropy value is far less than the threshold values, which is very feasible to classify this event as malicious.

Benign traffic was common in all attacks experiments, it was fixed threshold

values to compare entropy values deviations. In Figure 6.3 and Figure 6.4, entropy deviation values were less than the fixed threshold or some times it was higher than the fixed threshold. However, we have acquired traffic and classified based on mean values, which are significantly less than a fixed threshold as already depicted in both Figure 6.3 and Figure 6.4.

(a) 30% Attack Traffic.

(b) 40% Attack Traffic.

Figure 6.3: Entropy variation with attack rates.

6.4 Results

The major objective of our proposed work in SDN network is to improve the accuracy of the deep learning-based model to detect various DDoS attack traffic. For which we mainly rely on malicious traffic features distribution and manipulation. We have utilised collaborative estimation of Shannon and Reyni entropy such as GE and ID with SDN based programmability features. This approach is able to lower down the unnecessary and redundant features from malicious traffic, which enable classifier to improve detection accuracy rate. Similar work has already been discussed in [162], the authors have utilised Shannon entropy calculation as detection metric in their proposed work. However, in our contribution, we have utilised combined entropy

(a) 60% Attack Traffic.

(b) 70% Attack Traffic.

Figure 6.4: Entropy variation with attack rates.

calculation with Shannon and Reyni formulas to generalise DDoS traces from tested with traffic distribution approach.

Based on the various parameters, which are depicted in Table 6.4, we classify our specific malicious traffic features comprise of only *Src-IP*, *Src-Port*, *Dest-IP*, *Dest-Port*, *Source-Bytes*, *Destination-Bytes*, *TTL*, *Flags*, *proto*, *Distinct Datagrams*. We carried out our various experiments based on the above design. We utilised 4 various attack rates with normal traffic. We fixed windows size to 180 for five hosts, we carried various attacks and generate normal traffic on these hosts.

6.4.1 Selecting DDoS Classifier

In order to get feasible detection results, we selected two deep learning models such as Stacked Auto Encoder (SAE) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). First, we acquired input vector based on entropy feature distribution then we compare SAE and CNN detection accuracy and FP rates based on collected datasets depicted in Table 6.3.

Our work uses different malicious rate such as 30% and 60% of attacks intensity with benign traffic, which results in a higher level of unbalanced features. In such cases, SAE and CNN detection algorithms fail to classify attacks. To overcome

Table 6.5: Representation of normal and attack records for training and testing.

CSV 1	30% attack rate traffic	
	Training	Testing
Normal	94,330	22,016
<i>All_{attacks}</i>	67,794	17,348
CSV 2	60% attack rate traffic	
	Training	Testing
Normal	51,730	16,518
<i>All_{attacks}</i>	113,350	27,750

Table 6.6: Proposed model configuration values.

Hyper parameters	Model values
Total hidden-layers	1, 2, 3
Hidden-layers size	6, 3, 2
Learning-rate	0.1, 0.01, 0.001
Activation-function	Sigmoid
Dropout	0.75, 0.50
Batch-size	100, 50, 50

this issue, the authors of [217] have improved higher accuracy of detection model by using weighted loss function to stabilise the test-bed features. Our proposed SAE and CNN detection model use well known metrics such as *precision*, *recall* and *F1 score* on datasets specified in Table 6.3. These metrics are very useful for the goodness of the detection rate of the proposed model.

Our work uses two types of CSV files with different malicious and benign traffic. In the first one, we combined 30% attack rate with normal traffic and the second one utilises 60% of attack rate with normal traffic as shown in the Table 6.5. These CSV files also divided by training and testing section followed by 80% and 20% training and testing respectively. We adjusted the SAE detection algorithm with only three hidden layers and these three hidden layers are set as descending order with the following hyperparameters which are depicted in Table 6.6.

In this chapter, we have compared performance metrics by using SAE and CNN detection classifiers. We have utilised two-class classification model for SAE and CNN model. However, we compare the SAE model and CNN separately with the same traffic mainly consists of TCP, UDP, ICMP packets depicted in Figure 6.5, 6.6. The first case uses 30% attack combined with normal traffic and the second case, utilises only 60% attack traffic with normal for better evaluation purpose.

Figure 6.5 represents the confusion matrix for SAE and CNN detection model for 30% attack rate. The Figure 6.5 (a) confusion matrix of SAE depicts 91.47% of TP detection rate with only less than 9% of FP rate. SAE model achieves more

(a) Confusion matrix of SAE Algorithm

(b) Confusion matrix of CNN Algorithm

Figure 6.5: SAE and CNN Confusion matrix with 30% Attack Traffic.

than 12% of FN rate with first case traffic. Similarly, as shown in Figure 6.5 (b), the CNN model is not receiving higher correct detection as compared to SAE. The CNN detection model with 30% attack traffic can only classify Only 80% and 82% of TP rate and TN rate respectively, FP rate is also stood around 17% of false triggers.

Comparing performance metrics of SAE and CNN with confusion matrix with 30% attack, SAE achieves 82.4% accuracy rate for detecting real anomalous events, whereas CNN detection model achieves only 76.52% accuracy. Although SAE detection model is lightweight with only three weighted hidden layers, which require very time for training and testing as compared to CNN model.

In Figure 6.6, comparison of SAE and CNN confusion matrix is depicted with 60% of attack rate, where Figure 6.6 (a) shows 97% and 91.22% of TP rate and TN rate respectively for SAE detection model. However, the FP rate is also acceptable, which is only 6%. Moreover, Figure 6.6 (b) depicts more than 92% and 95% of TP rate and TN rate respectively for the CNN model. With 60% of higher attack intensity, CNN false alerts are also less than 10%.

Although SAE achieves an accuracy of 94%, on the other hand, CNN detection model also achieves nearly 93% detection accuracy. However, in this case, we com-

(a) Confusion matrix of SAE Algorithm.

(b) Confusion matrix of CNN Algorithm.

Figure 6.6: SAE and CNN Confusion matrix with 60% Attack Traffic.

bined more attack traffic as compared to benign traffic with 60% of malicious ratio, so both models perform well by utilising specific feature distributed traffic, which was obtained by entropy-based GE. In the Table 6.7, we have depicted an average conclusion of a confusion matrix for SAE and CNN detection model, addition to this, we have also provided the accuracy results of both classifiers without utilising proposed entropy-based feature distribution for validation purpose.

We have validated our test-bed performance, with a comparison of selected classifier accuracy detection with GE entropy-based feature distribution and without entropy-based feature distribution, as depicted in Figure 6.7. In Figure 6.7 (a), we provided SAE and CNN classifier accuracy results with only 30% attack intensity. In this figure, we can observe that accuracy of both SAE and CNN classifiers with normal features is comparatively less than entropy-based features class. For 30% attack rate without entropy-based feature distribution, the CNN classifier achieves the average accuracy of around 62%, similarly, SAE classifier receives an average accuracy of 68%. However, when we performed classifiers test with GE entropy-based feature distribution with 30% of attack intensity, SAE classifier performs better with 84% accuracy scores, and CNN classifier was at an average of 77% accuracy score.

Table 6.7: Performance Metrics of Confusion Matrix for SAE and CNN Model.

SAE model (With feature distribution)	30% attack traffic	60% attack traffic
Avg. Accuracy	84%	94%
Avg. FP rate	8.9%	6.01%
Avg. FN rate	12.11%	10.6%
CNN model (With feature distribution)	30% attack traffic	60% attack traffic
Avg. Accuracy	77%	93%
Avg. FP rate	17%	9%
Avg. FN rate	10%	6%
SAE model (Without feature distribution)	30% attack traffic	60% attack traffic
Avg. Accuracy	68%	86%
CNN model (Without feature distribution)	30% attack traffic	60% attack traffic
Avg. Accuracy	62%	86%

Although, with the attack intensity of 60% as shown in Figure 6.7 (b), SAE and CNN accuracy were recorded as 94.3% and 93% respectively, this result was obtained with entropy-based feature distribution. In contrast, we also run both classifiers before proposed entropy algorithm, the CNN classifier and SAE classifiers achieved an average accuracy of 86%, which is nearly 10% accuracy less as compared to proposed GE entropy-based feature distribution, which was combined work of Shannon and Reyni formula.

6.4.2 Performance Evaluation with CPU Usage at Controller

AS our model is focused to improve Anti-DDoS model accuracy by reducing controller burden. However, we have used combined entropy to distribute malicious features from data-plane to control-plane. In order to evaluate model performance we have provided the comparison of CPU usage, after entropy calculation to distribute malicious traffic from test-bed, and before entropy calculation, which is depicted in Figure 6.8, Figure 6.9 respectively. During the event of DDoS attacks, control-plane was under heavy traffic as incoming-packets so attack incoming-packets to SDN controller is measured in MB. Moreover, Shannon and Reyni entropy generalisation are deployed in the main controller, so that every attack incoming-packet was calculated with GE to distribute more specific features.

The Figure 6.8 (a), represents the CPU utilisation with only 30% attack rate traffic with corresponding Incoming-packets in (MB) and Outgoing-packets in (kbps). In this figure, the average CPU is utilised between 75% to 81% of the total. As shown from the above graph, when incoming-packets was reaching to Avg: of 4 Mbit/sec, then nearly 80% of total CPU is used, when incoming-packets reduced to Avg: of 2.6 Mbit/sec after 5 seconds fraction then CPU fluctuates between 60% and 75%. At some time intervals of around every 55 seconds CPU falls as lower as 50%. Following entropy calculation, when we double the attack rate of 60% to our test-bed, then avg: CPU utilisation also increased up to 85% and 93% as depicted in Figure 6.8 (b). This figure represents around 93% of CPU usage during the event

(a) With 30% attack rate accuracy comparison.

(b) With 60% attack rate accuracy comparison.

Figure 6.7: Accuracy comparison between Normal and Entropy based features.

of around 9 Mbits/sec incoming packets. When incoming-packets reduced to around 5 Mbit/sec then CPU of 85% utilised. However, as the graph shows that we receive only 60% of minimum CPU consumption, which is not frequent.

However, outgoing-packets during both attack rates scenarios stood almost common, in Figure 6.8 (a) and 6.8 (b), outgoing packets were changing in between 80kbps to 96 kbps.

In our work, we have also calculated CPU usage before entropy-based feature distribution with respect to incoming packets and outgoing-packets of 30% and 60% attack rate traffic. The Figure 6.9 (a), shows CPU usage with only 30% attack rate without entropy calculation, the graph depicts the avg: CPU of 52% during the event of 3 Mbit/sec incoming-packets towards proposed design. In this graph, CPU utilisation also rises to 65% when incoming-packets reaching to around 5.5 Mbit-s/sec level, minimum CPU usage was calculated 45% in some instances. Similarly, Figure 6.9 (b) depicts CPU usage with 60% of attack rate without GE calcula-

(a) 30%Attack Traffic CPU utilisation.

(b) 60% Attack Traffic CPU utilisation.

Figure 6.8: CPU utilisation after feature distribution with different attack rates.

tion. This figure shows nearly 80% of CPU found busy with 5 Mbit/sec then it frequently increased up to 90% of total CPU with 9.8 Mbit/sec incoming-packets flows. Outgoing-packets were also common as Figure 6.8.

However, it can be seen from Figure 6.8 (a), feature distribution with entropy generalisation uses 20% more CPU than the normal traffic, when we use low-intensity attack rate such as 30% attack rate. On the other hand, when we increase attack intensity such as 60%, then avg: CPU rises around 7% after comparing values from Figure 6.8 (b) and Figure 6.9 (b). Overall, the distribution of features with entropy generalisation is not consuming more CPU resources with higher attack intensity in test-bed.

In another experiment, we evaluated results of FP and FN reports with 30% and 60% of attack rates, we provided a comparison between SAE classifier and CNN classifier. We run both algorithms 10 times to acquire different results. As depicted in Figure 6.10 and Figure 6.11. However, with 30% of attack rates, the average number of FP alerts and FN alerts are 10% and 12% respectively for SAE classifier

(a) 30% Attack Traffic CPU utilisation.

(b) 60% Attack Traffic CPU utilisation.

Figure 6.9: CPU utilisation without feature distribution with different attack rates.

as depicted in Figure 6.10 (a). Similarly, from Figure 6.10 (b), Figure 6.10, depicts the total numbers of FP rate and FN rate for SAE and CNN classifier with a 30% attack rate. With each simulation run, each model randomly fluctuates with FP and FN rate, however, the total average rate of FP rate stood at 11% and the total average rate of FN rate stood at 13% for SAE. Similarly, the CNN classifier achieved an average of 10%, 14% of FP rate, and FN rate. Overall both classifiers performed equally with 30% attack.

Moreover, with 60% of attack rate, both classifiers perform very well due to low false results, as depicted in Figure 6.11 (a), we observe total average rate for FP and FN as 6%, and 11% respectively in SAE. However, we did not observe any drastic change in the results of CNN evaluation, as CNN classifier also achieves FP alert with 9% and FN alert 7%. Overall, we can observe that higher attack intensity enables both classifiers to achieve significant results, but SAE results more accurate due to its lightweight processing.

(a) SAE Algorithm False reports.

(b) CNN Algorithm False reports.

Figure 6.10: SAE and CNN False reports with 30% Attack Traffic.

(a) SAE Algorithm False reports.

(b) CNN Algorithm False reports.

Figure 6.11: SAE and CNN False reports with 60% Attack Traffic.

Chapter 7

Trust aware Blockchain based Collaborative Intrusion Detection in SDN

This Chapter:

Converges the blockchain and Collaborative intrusion Detection Networks (CIDN) networks in SDN, the main purpose of this proposed work is to classify and detect major seven types of common DDoS attacks in current networks with trust communication of blockchain protocols, where detection is more responsive and much secure via CIDN Snort agents implementation.

7.1 Introduction

Due to the rapid increment of the cyber-attacks, intrusion detection system (IDS) is shifting towards collaborative approaches. There is a huge demand for securing larger networking environments for providing a safeguard against threats. In order to optimize the feasible detection performance, Collaborative Intrusion Detection Networks (CIDN) approaches have been adopted in practical scenarios, which enables a group of IDS nodes to mutually share and exchange mandatory information with each other, for example, IDS-signatures, attacks alarms. However, CIDN networks are distributed in nature, such networks still face plenty of implementation problems, especially, insider intruder can easily dominate any of security node and leave the entire security system vulnerable. To achieve the trust-based communication between each of IDS node, the recent advancement in blockchain applications is considered as a good fit to create trust-based communication in CIDN networks. This work converges CIDN network and blockchain in SDN context. We utilised three collaborated Snort IDS to receive the latest signature update from Ryu and then

to securely share such signatures updates to all other Snort nodes within test-bed. Our work is motivated to detect seven types of common attacks with collaborated signature-based IDS, which feasibly processes more packets to achieve satisfactory detection results. In our proposed CIDN approach, we have utilised three different autonomous networks with unique Snort IDS, which actively collects the network data, in addition, it also provides fast and effective trust communication with the help of distributed ledger of block chains implementation. Overall the evaluation results show that with the adoption of blockchain protocols, the proposed CIDN network achieves 96% of TP rate detection rate for TCP, UDP and ICMP packets.

In Software Defined Networking (SDN) environment, building a customised network architecture is a game changer, where, we can flexibly transfer legacy network infrastructure to an innovative, open source and programmable infrastructure. The authors of [57] depicted that most of the current public and private networks are exponentially increasing due to our busy online life, where network complexities and issues are also arising during implementation. With a significant increment of cyber attackers, most of the single IDS detection applications have failed to accurately discover attacks in large networks, IDS collect limited information about attacks when these are deployed against heavy traffic [237]. Most of the legacy IDS based implementations could easily be bypassed by complex attacks such as Denial of Services (DoS), Slowris and by highly experienced cybercriminals. To maximise the performance pragmatically, Collaborative intrusion Detection Networks(CIDN) have been deployed, in which group of IDSs collectively achieve the huge amount of data from other nodes [238]. Although, IDS nodes are capable to share their signature-rules with each deployed nodes of the system, in order to improve detection efficiency and reducing false alarms [239], [240], [241]. However, such IDS deployment can become vulnerable for insider attack, due to the fact of interconnected and distributed nature. If any of that node is severely infected then it can lower down the detection performance at other nodes [242]. To deal with this issue, there is significant demand to create an effective security mechanism to provide potential safeguard to signature sharing rules within CIDN networks.

With the motivation of impact and adoption of Bitcoin, blockchain technologies and IDS based security systems are being widely attracted towards industries and academia, this system enables trusted individuals to easily connect other potential network entities with verifiable approach without the interception of any complex centralised application [243]. By utilising consensus approaches, the blockchain helps to provide transparent and protected data storage, in which the majority of stored data blocks can not be modified unless to update all sub-blocks. This approach in the blockchain is significantly required to share IDS signature rules in a protected way for various CIDN platforms.

From the recent development of blockchain applications, we are motivated to propose a collaborated signature-based IDS model, which implies blockchain application to securely share Snort signature rules with all integrated Snort nodes. Our work mainly focuses to apply blockchain for deploying a trusted Snort signature database with the help of SDN Ryu [181]. This idea ensures verified signature rules from the relevant domain, which enables collaborative CIDN to improve detection accuracy with heavy and unknown malicious traffic, this also helps to lower down manipulation and management efforts. Major contributions of our work are provided below:

- To process more packets with collaborative Snort nodes for the purpose of higher detection accuracy in seven major attacks types.
- To create a trusted Snort signature rules sharing channel in Ryu and reducing HIDS influencing burden in CIDN. We utilised blockchain implementation with distributed Snort IDSs in SDN context, SDN Ryu controller only updates NIDS Snort signature rule then all integrated HIDS Snort nodes are automatically updated by the trusted channel of blockchain.
- For evaluation, we carried out two different experiments, in the first experiment, we investigated the performance of the proposed system with IDS based attack detection. In the second, experiment, we investigated the proposed system accuracy with packet-drop and packet-processing with various input traffic intensity by using Ryu and Snort integration in a virtual machine.

The rest of this Chapter is organised as: Section 7.2 introduces the background and related work. The Section 7.3 depicts main implementation and design. Section 7.4 evaluates proposed model results.

7.2 Background

In legacy networks, stand-alone IDS carries less information for implemented networks, where it tries to provide a potential safeguard against unknown malicious activities, this enables the system to become vulnerable for potential attackers. For example, a cyber attacker can initiate a complex attack like Distributed Denial of Services (DDoS) to compromise a single Intrusion Detection System (IDS), due to the fact that it is less able to acquire overall network traffic status. To resolve this IDS issue, there is an alarming need to provide a collaborative IDS based solution to optimize detection ability [238].

The existing literature widely represents distributed monitoring based work for decades. Some of the existing systems such as Distributed Intrusion Detection System (DIDS) [244], which was proposed in late 1991, this system was capable to monitor distributed heterogeneous computer networks. Addition to this, Event Monitoring Enabling Responses to Anomalous Live Disturbances (EMERALD) [245] was also proposed in 1991, this system was capable to record various intrusion activities within an abstract layer of a big network. This model was able to merge high volume events from legacy distributed IDS.

7.2.0.1 Collaborative intrusion detection (CIDN)

For feasible detection performance, a CIDN system utilises IDS nodes to share its mandatory information to every collaborated node. The authors of [246] in 2006 discussed that each IDS node centrally dependant in CIDN networks. For motivation of this issue, they designed new CIDN systems based on decentralised locations and routing infrastructure. Moreover, their system assumes a trust-based peer system, which could easily be targeted by inside intruders. In collaborative intrusion detection systems, attacks from inside can easily create the biggest loss, from which point an intruder can easily consume resources and become dominant in that system.

In order to provide a safeguard against inside attackers, a CIDN system more likely requires an appropriate and feasible trust-based solution, in which each IDS nodes can ensure trust factors to improve reputation amongst all IDSs. The authors of [247] proposed an IDSs system, which was created on the basis of the P2P overlay. The trust-aware engine is utilised to correlate triggers and addition to this it also correlates adaptive scheme for IDS trust management. Similarly, the authors of [248] designed a game theory model for analysing the processes of P2P network reporting. They investigated that if system reputation is not compatible then a number of system peers nodes results in false malicious reporting.

Based on the aforementioned facts, the other authors of [249] also depicted CIDN model, in which IDS nodes trustworthiness is dependant on received answers, firstly they depicted a Host-based IDS (HIDS) framework, where each HIDS node achieve trustworthiness following by its CIDN experience. To improve this model effectiveness, the authors in [250] have differentiated that various IDSs may vary for detection purpose.

7.2.0.2 Blockchain based IDS

Most of the industries and many researchers are focusing to deploy blockchains based applications since last six years, most of these applications are utilised for specific use-cases with unique and specific blockchains requirements with unique and cus-

tomised characteristics. For example, in existing literature, there are large number of cases, which are developed on the bases of improving privacy with different parties in the system, the major aim was to focus for storing data completely private [251]. Similarly, more implementations use identity schemes with cryptography application, this mechanism caters full unavailability and anonymity between different transactions [250]. Based on these versatile approaches, most industries and researchers have been trying to investigate blockchain based application potential.

The blockchain based technologies are widely used to store information in a decentralised way to provide safeguard against any deviations. It is also very vital to find out the feasible way how to deploy the blockchain system in intrusion detection systems. Most of the current research is investigating this gap, the authors of [252], have provided a blockchain based CIDN framework, in this method, set of false alarms from IDSs are considered as blockchain transactions. Then, most of collaborating IDSs nodes utilised unique communication protocol for stable transaction connection before generating them in a specific block. This approach can be used as a safeguard against intrusion in blockchains. However, the authors did not provide a systematic implementation in detail, addition to this they did not evaluate results with practical implementation. To deal with this issue, authors in [253] utilised some early insights based on the interception of IDSs and blockchains units, they also addressed some issues and challenges in this platform. According to the authors, blockchains can provide a positive impact on a distributed intrusion detection system with regard to data sharing, exchange of alarms and trust based processing. Similarly, authors of [254] also introduced a CIoTA framework to utilised the blockchain mechanism for collaborative anomaly detection, but there were limited resources. Moreover, IDS agents can also help to protect blockchain applications.

In contrast, there are some works , which have been published with OpenFlow based protocol, such as authors of [255] discussed a ChainGuard, which is developed on OpenFlow based firewall, this approach is feasibly created for securing SDN based blockchains system. In this method, OpenFlow based switch traffic is propagated to the blockchain based ChainGuard node. The main purpose of this system is to lower down the unknown malicious activities from participating system nodes. Moreover, the authors of [256] also developed an effective DistBlockNet system, also known as SDN based distributed system for IoT security, in which blockchains were utilised as key elements. This mechanism enables other nodes interaction without the interception of any trust-based central controller.

7.3 Design of Snort based CIDN Network with blockchain

Figure 7.1: Proposed Test-Bed of Snort IDS with DNN Co-Detection in SDN.

In this section, we depict major SDN based deployment and implementation. Our proposed model comprises blockchain based collaborative intrusion detection network, which uses Snort IDS as Host-based (HIDS) and Network-based (NIDS) with Ryu programmable flexibility. The major aim of the research is to provide a safeguard against insider attacks and improve attack detection accuracy by utilising collaborative Snort node with blockchains certificates between control-plane Ryu application and all Snort nodes signature database. We deployed *Ethereum Geth* to create Ethereum environment in Ubuntu 16.04 LTS, This environment enables to create genesis block with major digital transaction signatures, we combined and connected all transaction ID as a unique hash function. Each Snort node utilizes this hash value and newly processed transaction ID. Similarly, previous hash value and transaction ID is to be used as a new hash value for the next Snort node in the new block of the chain. However each Snort IDS node in blockchain links with its previous block via hash values, which results in a chain which is directly connected to unique genesis block. This procedure provides secure communication to all Snort IDS to accept rule-set from control-plane.

In VM-2, *Ethernum Geth* and Snort nodes were deployed, each node constitutes secure SSH key pair to establish the connection. We utilize python class for employing blockchain, where SHA256 hash function is utilized for encryption.

The Fig. 7.2 depicts the blockchain network between collaborative CIDN nodes, where Snort-1, Snort-2 and Snort-3 node communicate each other by using a hash function such as a public key and a private key pairs. In our proposed CIDN network, Snort-1 node connects to Snort-2 node via previous hash value, similarly, Snort-2 node connects to Snort-3 node. In this way, every node of Snort invites each other by the signed transaction. Moreover, after establishing secure communication, these nodes start to share Snort rule-set with each other with appropriate block key pairs.

Figure 7.2: Blockchain trust communication inside CIDN Snort nodes.

The proposed system detects unknown DDoS, including seven different types of attacks mentioned in TABLE 7.1. This system helps to keep protected from insider attackers. In SDN architecture, IDS nodes are integrated with blockchain trusted channel which enables SDN controller to effectively share signatures rules to Snort nodes, which are implemented in data-plane. Our design systematically operates as a loop of three components such as Ryu controller, IDS nodes and blockchain trust certificates, as depicted in Fig.7.1. The IDS depicts the DDoS attack detection mechanism, data-plane represents the network in which different

Table 7.1: Seven Different Attack types.

No	Attack-types	Description
1	DDoS-attacks	DDoS Floods (Metasploit)
2	SSH-attacks	SSH Exploits (Metasploit)
3	FTP-attacks	Brute Force (Metasploit)
4	HTTP-attacks	HTTP Floods (Kali Linux)
5	ICMP-attacks	Smurf Attacks (Metasploit)
6	ARP-attacks	ARP Spoofing (Kali Linux)
7	Scan-attacks	Port Scans (Kali Linux)

Snort nodes are integrated by blockchain to share signature automatically. However, SDN Ryu controller plays a very vital role to manipulate and update the blockchain hash table and all other Snort and OpenVswitch entries.

7.4 Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate the performance of our proposed system in SDN based environment, where we use CIDN network to calculate the collaborative based Snort CIDN network performance with the implementation of blockchain. In our proposed model CIDN, uses blockchain based Snort nodes, which can monitor, identify unknown malicious activity and also share Snort signature rule-set with neighbouring nodes. Each node needs to sign privately for qualifying rule-set, each remaining node has to follow this rule-set. In this way, blockchain nodes expanded when these nodes are verified then these blocks receives the trusted rules only.

To evaluate this work, we carried out two different experiments with three virtual machines, which are created with Ubuntu LTS 16.04 64 bit OS. VM-1 machine is created with SDN Ryu and Snort integration. SDN controller primarily programmes the network operation such as updating Snort signatures rules and data-plane flow. This programme is initiated once Ryu receives the Packet_in message from OpenFlow. The Ryu controller changes the data-plane of proposed CIDN network by utilising Link-A, in this virtual machine, Link-B is used for Snort signature sharing towards CIDN network. VM-2 machine represents the network domain, where a network emulator (eg. Mininet) is utilised to create CIDN virtual network with Mininet simulator. CIDN network comprises of three Snort IDS nodes [141], all nodes were deployed with default signature rules. When a new packet_in arrives with malicious attributes then main HIDS Snort node receives new signature updates from Ryu via Link-D, then all other CIDN nodes are also updated via blockchain. SDN based switches use the OpenFlow protocol to communicate the VM-1 and VM-2. Once all Snort nodes from CIDN receives packets, then integrated switches use a port mirror

approach for sending entire traffic streams to Link-B. We carried two experiments with CIDN with 100 Mbps data intensity to validate our model performance. This machine also utilises NAT node as a gateway so that some hosts can launch attacks as a malicious injection. VM-3 is used for launching attacks towards CIDN-1 and CIDN-2 nodes. This virtual machine acts as a Host-Only adapter.

7.4.1 Attack modelling

VM-3 is used for attack modelling as a server, in which we are running HTTP, FTP and SSH services. We utilised the Metasploit framework and Kali Linux [212] in order to generate seven types of malicious traffic as shown in TABLE 7.1. The purpose of using Metasploit framework is to generate malicious traffic with different payloads and exploitation for various operating systems such as Windows, Linux or Mac OS. All seven major attacks along with legitimate traffic injected to CIDN IDS nodes. All blockchain based IDS starts to inspect malicious and legitimate traffic and trigger alarms if the input traffic matches the rule set which is shared via blockchains to Snort IDS. These number of alarms (comprises as false-positive, false-negative and true-positive) will classify network traffic.

7.4.2 Evaluation with malicious and legitimate traffic in CIDN network

In this experiment, we investigated the performance of collaborated Snort IDS with blockchain based CIDN network. CIDN network is deployed to investigate performance between malicious and legitimate traffic. We have utilised three collaborated Snort IDS nodes with blockchain, each node is also integrated with SDN based switch. In this experiment, we have launched seven different types of malicious attacks into CIDN network, where each node is utilising Snort signature rule-set. We utilised only 3 nodes in CIDN network.

In CIDN, collaborated Snort IDS nodes were configured with the default rule set. However, We run our proposed test-bed for around two hours as shown in TABLE 7.4. The seven different attack types were injected with different speed to CIDN. In the first test, collaborated Snort IDS with default rule set performance was not acceptable. This is due to the fact that Snort is rule-based, it mainly focuses on rules set once input traffic attack matches then Snort generate an alarm. In this work, we are utilising seven attack combination with legitimate traffic. Snort collaborated IDSs of CIDN with a default rule set, only detected average combined TP rate 73.5% , 74% and 76% for Snort-node-1, Snort-node-2 and Snort-node-3 respectively. In the second run time, we enable collaborated IDS to receive rule set from Ryu controller by utilising trusted blockchain. As shown in TABLE 7.2 , we

Table 7.2: Different attacks detection accuracy with blockchain based CIDN.

Malicious-traffic	Snort-node-1		Snort-node-2		Snort-node-3	
	Snort-FP	Snort-FN	Snort-FP	Snort-FN	Snort-FP	Snort-FN
SSH-attacks	9.0%	2.0%	8.0%	4.0%	11.0%	2.0%
DDoS/DoS-attacks	5.0%	4.0%	6.5%	2.0%	8.0%	4.0%
FTP-attacks	10.0%	7.0%	9.0%	8.0%	14.5%	4.0%
HTTP-attacks	4.0%	8.0%	6.0%	3.0%	8.0%	2.0%
ICMP-attacks	13.0%	4.0%	9.0%	6.0%	11.5%	4.0%
ARP-attacks	12.0%	5.0%	11.0%	9.0%	12.5%	3.0%
Scan-attacks	44.0%	19.0%	50.0%	17.0%	44.5%	21.0%

have depicted the three Snort collaborated nodes values, which are integrated with blockchain rules set sharing approach. The Snort-node-1 achieved average FP rate of 10% with six major attacks types, in this node, Snort-FN rate was recorded nearly 6%. In Snort-node-2 and Snort-node-3, ARP-attack, FTP-attack, ICMP-attack and FTP-attack achieved average of 10% FP rate. The average detection rate of true positive rate was calculated around 97% for each of six malicious traffic with Snort-node-1, Snort-node-2, Snort-node-3. However, Snort-node-1 only achieved 44% TP rate, Snort-node-2 achieved 44% TP rate and Snort-node-3 achieved less than 51% TP rate with Scan malicious traffic.

Fig. 7.3 depicts the average performance of Snort IDS nodes TP rate with respect to various traffic input intensity with Mbps. The overall detection performance of the proposed test-bed is evaluated with background running of the blockchain mechanism, which enables each IDS node to adopt new signatures from Ryu, which helps to detect more accurately and effectively. When the proposed system processes the 10 Mbps of combined legitimate and malicious traffic, the average TP detection rate of six attacks was stood more than 60%, where SSH-attacks and Scan-attacks were recorded with 74% of TP rate and 44% of TP rate respectively. Scan-attacks TP rate was not good and overall it was recorded up to 50% of TP rate. Average TP rate of DDoS-attacks, FTP-attacks, HTTP-attacks, ICMP-attacks and ARP-attacks were recorded more than 80% of TP between 30 Mbps to 60 Mbps traffic intensity. Similarly, all of these six attacks types achieved more than 90% of TP rate with 70 Mbps to 100 Mbps combined input traffic intensity. More over, our proposed work achieved an average of 96% of TP detection rate once we increase traffic intensity up to 100Mbps, this detection accuracy was achieved within six major common attacks types only detail is depicted in Fig. 7.3.

Figure 7.3: CIDN network different attacks TP-rate with different traffic intensity.

7.4.3 Evaluation with legitimate traffic in CIDN network

In this experiment, we have utilised same CIDN network, which also comprises the same three Snort IDS, these nodes are collaborated with blockchain. To validate the proposed design, we observed the collaborated Snort IDS performance with the help of legitimate traffic. We generated legitimate traffic by utilising (Ostinato tool). We performed an experiment to investigate the performance of all collaborated Snort nodes with a network speed of 100Mbps. We injected 1,250 bytes of TCP, UDP and ICMP packets. As shown in Fig.1, we run Snort IDS nodes individually on the proposed test-bed. In this CIDN network, we have utilised a number of tools to record and investigate CPU utilisation, memory/network utilisation, and packet drop rate. The tools include dstat, Snort Barnyard2 logfile, TCP-dump, nmap and Metasploit framework etc. In this experiment, we manually injected packets with 300packets/sec to all nodes. Background network link speed is divided into the range of 1 to 100 Mbps. All collaborated Snort IDS were investigated with total accumulated packets of 10,800,000 TCP with 300 packets/sec intensity. Similarly, total accumulated packets of 10,800,000 of UDP and total accumulated packets of 10,800,000 of ICMP were also injected to CIDN network nodes in order to validate. The TCP, UDP and ICMP packets were manually injected with 300 packets/sec rate. The CPU-utilisation and memory-utilisation of CIDN network with blockchain

Table 7.3: Different CPU and memory utilisation with blockchain based CIDN.

Traffic-intensity	Snort-node-1		Snort-node-2		Snort-node-3	
	CPU-usage	Memory-usage	CPU-usage	Memory-usage	CPU-usage	Memory-usage
10 Mbps	64%	3.0 Mbps	61%	2.0 Mbps	60%	1.2 Mbps
20 Mbps	66%	3.5 Mbps	64%	3.3 Mbps	62%	3.0 Mbps
30 Mbps	67%	5 Mbps	65%	4.0 Mbps	65%	4.5 Mbps
40 Mbps	68%	6.6 Mbps	69%	6.0 Mbps	66%	6.0 Mbps
50 Mbps	71%	8.9 Mbps	70%	9.0 Mbps	69%	7.0 Mbps
60 Mbps	71%	9 Mbps	72%	9.1 Mbps	71%	8.1 Mbps
70 Mbps	74%	10 Mbps	74%	11.0 Mbps	72%	9.0 Mbps
80 Mbps	76.0%	10.9 Mbps	75%	12.0 Mbps	74%	9.11 Mbps
90 Mbps	77.0%	11 Mbps	76%	12. 2 Mbps	76%	10.0 Mbps
100 Mbps	81.0%	12.3 Mbps	78%	12.9 Mbps	77%	10.1 Mbps

based collaborated Snort IDS is depicted in the TABLE 7.3.

The CPU utilisation of CIDN network with blockchain based collaborated Snort IDS is calculated in such a way as CIDN network contains three Snort IDSs nodes (eg Snort-node-1, Snort-node-2 and Snort-node-3) each of that nodes utilises shared processor unit, not overall CPU. The CPU consumption of all three nodes is investigated with Intel (R) Xeon (R) X5560 CPU with 2.88 GHz processor and 16 GB RAM (DDR3 ECC-Registered Memory PC3-12800MHZ).

From the collected data, we observed that all collaborated Snort IDS nodes were utilising almost the same CPU and memory. Snort-node-1 memory and CPU utilisation were almost identical with Snort-node-2 and Snort-node-3. From the TABLE 7.3, it can be seen that each node CPU-utilisation is increasing due to the increment of input traffic intensity. The average CPU-utilisation of Snort IDS node is 65% when these nodes were receiving input traffic intensity 10 Mbps to 40 Mbps, then CPU exponentially increase nearly 80% CPU utilisation in all three collaborated Snort nodes. Each Snort node utilises only shared 2-cores CPU or 4-core CPU out of 8-core CPU.

In this experiment, each Snort node is able to classify nearly 2 Mbps out of 10 Mbps. With 20 Mbps and 30 Mbps input traffic intensity, all three nodes were able to inspect only 4 Mbps traffic. When we injected 80 Mbps,90 Mbps and 100 Mbps traffic burst then Snort-node-1 only processed 11 Mbps, Snort-node-2 only processed 13 Mbps and Snort-node-3 only processed 10 Mbps respectively. These calculation were for individual Snort IDS.

Moreover, Snort IDS is signature based and its processing is limited if used as stand-alone IDS during heavy network traffic burst. Once we inject 10 Mbps input traffic to CIDN based network then all nodes with the help of blockchain can easily process all input traffic. This enables CIDN network to correctly identify intrusions with very less false triggers. Blockchain based approach also helps Snort IDS to accept new signatures from Ryu controller.

When input network traffic intensity started to increase, the CPU and memory

Table 7.4: Different packet-processing and packet-drops with blockchain based CIDN.

Traffic-input		UDP-packets		TCP-packets		ICMP-packets	
Bandwidth	time-elapsed	Pkt-processing	pkt-drops	Pkt-processing	pkt-drops	Pkt-processing	pkt-drops
10 Mbps	450	20,000	5.3%	21,000	7.0 %	23,000	1.2 %
20 Mbps	900	30,000	6.0 %	32,000	6.3 %	28,000	6.0 %
30 Mbps	1,350	40,000	6.8 %	40,000	4.0 %	34,000	5.5 %
40 Mbps	1,800	55,000	7.6 %	57,000	5.0 %	50,000	6.0 %
50 Mbps	2,250	58,000	8.4 %	56,000	9.0 %	58,000	8.0 %
60 Mbps	2,700	58,000	9 %	57,000	11.1 %	60,000	11.1 %
70 Mbps	3,150	61,000	11.5 %	62,000	12.0 %	60,000	9.0 %
80 Mbps	3,600	62,000	13.9 %	63,000	15.0 %	63,000	13.11 %
90 Mbps	4,050	63,000	15 %	60,000	19. 2 %	64,000	16.0 %
100 Mbps	4,500	65,000	17.3%	63,000	21.9 %	60,000	19.1 %

consumption also started to increase, this results in packets drop as well. We injected almost total accumulated packets of 10,800,000 for UDP, TCP and ICMP with 300 packets/sec intensity. From TABLE 7.4, we can observe that Snort IDS nodes with blockchain approach can process 20,000 UDP, 21,000 TCP and 23,000 ICMP packets with the 10 Mbps traffic intensity, TCP-packets drop rate was higher at this stage such as 7.0%. Once we increase the input traffic intensity up to 50% Mbps then the proposed CIDN test-bed processed an average of 58,000 of UDP, TCP and ICMP packets with the packet-drop rate of around 8%. We continued to double up input network traffic such as the 100 Mbps intensity of malicious and legitimate traffic then 63,000 of total UDP, TCP and ICMP packets were processed with blockchain-based IDS nodes, the packet drop rate was higher such as 21% of the total injected packets. Overall, we can observe that after combining all Snort nodes, the packet processing of the proposed system is feasibly improved to catch various attacks types rapidly.

Chapter 8

Conclusion and Future Directions

This Chapter:

Concludes the aforementioned work, which comprises of our contributions, implementations and results evaluation in very precise form. In addition to this, we also concluded some of the future directions as results of this work.

As mentioned in previous chapters that Software-Defined Networking has emerged as a great enabler to change the way of designing and building network architecture. Despite inserting security policies in the SDN environment, the SDN carries plenty of issues for its security perspective, and these issues create alarming situations which must be resolved prior to build a robust and protected SDN based architecture. In SDN, most of the security issues are caused by control logic centralization and network programmability, Moreover, SDN also effectively deals with various network security issues also plays a vital role to strengthen network security. In addition to this, SDN mainly relies on the simplest functions of switch-based packets forwarding with rule-set. SDN components can perform various network task with the help of additional software applications, which also provide the user-controlled management to support the hardware-based forwarding elements. Overall, SDN based networking mainly focuses to create the logically centralised controller with decoupling of data-plane and control-plane, this centralised SDN feature helps to lower down the majority of the network complexities.

In our thesis, firstly we have utilised integration of Snort Ryu and DNN learning algorithm to develop a collaborative technique for detecting malicious activities in a network. Our model achieved 85% accuracy for normal and attack classes. We have presented the advantage of using deep learning with Snort Ryu IDS to detect anomalies in different attack categories. In the SDN, the valuable information about network traffic is extracted inside its main controller, and then the detection model is evaluated by DNN algorithm.

Secondly, we created a co-detection model of deep learning with Snort IDS,

to detect unwanted DDoS traffic with the help of sFlow and polling-based traffic sampling at data-plane. This work analyzes network overhead between the SDN controller and data-plane with each sampling implementation to improve detection of IDS and DNN model capabilities. sFlow as flow-oriented sampling utilized 50% of CPU with propagation rate of 340 KB/s packets towards detection unit of the controller, whereas adaptive polling-based uses more than 70% total machine CPU at parsing rate of around 240 KB/s. Moreover, sFlow measures very low CPU and network overhead without sacrificing detection accuracy of deep learning model, also sFlow consistently stood superior for proposed DDoS detection model in term of accuracy, low CPU, and network overhead.

Thirdly, we have utilised feature distribution technique by entropy generalisation of Shannon and Reyni combined formula. Although Shannon entropy is already used in existence work for classification results, our paper uses generalised entropy (GE) for the purpose of information distance (ID). This combined entropy technique helps to reduce controller overhead as GE removes redundant and unnecessary traffic feature, which enables the SDN controller to identify attack packets at early stages. Entropy calculation utilises around 25% more CPU, when we merge 30% of attack traffic, however, our implemented GE technique to distribute traffic features uses only 5% more CPU when attack intensity was 60% in test-bed. This is due to the fact that we fixed $TW=3$ threshold, which is higher time windows and also feasible to manipulate and distribute huge attack traffic. Our work uses two well-known classifiers such as SAE, and CNN to perform classification with distributed traffic. With 60% attack intensity, SAE and CNN achieved an average accuracy of 94% and 93% respectively with only 6% of FP alerts in SAE traffic classification.

Finally, we have utilised blockchain technology, which is widely considered for providing verifiable information-sharing approach without using any complex trust-based mechanism. With the motivation of current blockchain applications, we utilised three collaborated Snort IDS, which securely receive new signature updates from SDN Ryu controller. This collaborated approach of CIDN network with Snort IDS generates very less false alerts such as the average of 5% of FP rate and FN rate for DDoS and HTTP attacks. However, the average FP rate and FN rate for all other different attacks types were stood nearly 10%. Due to the fact that each collaborated IDS individually detects burst attack input traffic.

In the future, we aim to improve accuracy and to extract more valuable features using a flexible approach of SDN. We will also improve DNN model performance by providing non-redundant data-sets of real-time based networks. There are several directions being considered. First, to implement intelligent periodic polling-based sampling only at SDN-enabled edge switches with real-time traffic streams that can help to lower down the crucial overhead. Secondly, it is very vital to train

unsupervised deep learning model with two individual training of rule-based and signature-based real-time network datagrams, which could help to maximize DDoS detection accuracy as a whole, which is suitable for small to larger networks, we will deploy our model in a real-time environment with huge network traffic flows, we focus to reduce controller's bottleneck by traffic sampling and feature extraction and entropy-based anomalies traffic collection as raw packets of SDN networks.

We also intend to investigate a more robust, efficient and lightweight approach to perceive the identification errors such as security enforcement rules for data plane and control plane, we also implement our northbound API-based solution based on open source controller, then we validate and test the implementation on our private cloud server. In our proposed solution, we mainly focus on multidomain networks by utilizing more than one SDN controller, investigation and mitigation of DDoS attacks with multiple domains of SDN controller will be communicated with specific interfaces such as North-South interfaces or East-West interfaces. The proposed model will only be implemented based on a higher detection rate with low processing overhead, meanwhile a trust between the nodes will be carried out. We believe that the proposed works will be capable to expand our approach to satisfy the numerous and complex application specifications towards the DDoS attack detection and mitigation in various environment.

The most of security enhancement contributions are limited as compared to security issues contribution presented in Table 3.2. In order to achieve the full security of SDN network, most of the security implementation must be carried out in collaboration of interoperability with multi-vendor platforms, third party-based network applications and network function virtualization, which helps to lower down the larger number of network security vulnerabilities during SDN framework development. However, based on the development perspective, SDN is not clear in the development area, how to optimise the operational security functions such as forwarding-rules, system-reliability, system-audit, system-recovery etc. Overall existing literature shows that SDN-based security solutions are still limited that cannot completely replace the traditional functions. In order to achieve the improved SDN based security practices, there is a feasible demand to provide the detailed security development assessment that how an SDN-based infrastructure is designed, created and managed with real-time data-based infrastructures. Following such technical assessments, fast, effective and up to date security solutions such as collaborative techniques and novel algorithms can easily be designed and proposed, that can enable to develop the wide ranges of the dynamics of security in network infrastructures in future.

Appendix A

Appendix Title

A.1 Datasets

Figure A.1 depicts the overview of data collection with Ntop tool in SDN. In Figure A.2, we provided the overview of data analysis and collection with Wire shark.

Figure A.1: Overview of data collection with Ntop tool in SDN.

- **Data Acquisition** - Data were acquired with the Snort IDS log output-alert in the csv file of Barnyard2 database, we also utilised Wireshark, Ntopng, and TCPDUMP tools in Linux OS to validate and process data for research evaluation. Two major modes of data collection are provided below:

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
1	0.000000000	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 3, seq 25877, 8 samples
2	0.007229759	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 1, seq 25878, 8 samples
3	0.059025543	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 3, seq 25878, 8 samples
4	0.061727958	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 1, seq 25849, 8 samples
5	0.068052795	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 3, seq 25878, 8 samples
6	0.095446266	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 1, seq 25842, 8 samples
7	0.129353227	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 3, seq 25886, 8 samples
8	0.159388725	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 1, seq 25842, 8 samples
9	0.189902442	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 3, seq 25882, 8 samples
10	0.208326278	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 1, seq 25843, 8 samples
11	0.229299965	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 1, seq 25844, 8 samples
12	0.233099598	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 3, seq 25882, 8 samples
13	0.254030165	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 1, seq 25845, 8 samples
14	0.297793561	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 3, seq 25883, 8 samples
15	0.331438209	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 3, seq 25884, 8 samples
16	0.332938482	192.168.119.129	192.168.119.130	sFlow	1382	VS, agent 192.168.119.129, sub-agent ID 1, seq 25846, 8 samples

Figure A.2: Overview of data analysis and collection with Wire shark.

1- Snort-mode (SM1): This data capturing mode comprises Snort IDS sensor with 20 DDoS attack signatures for (DDoS attacks), output alert_csv as CSV1, Barnyard2 as snort.log.1xx file.

2-Snort-mode (SM2): This data capturing mode comprises Snort IDS sensor with 10 signatures for (normal traffic, and anomalous traffic), output alert_csv as CSV2 and, CSV3 Barnyard2 snort.log.2xx.

- **Data Processing** - After collection, we normalized data with the different process of formatting, cleaning and encoding from categorial values to refined numbers as a vector. This process is carried out with Python libraries and Pandas libraries to scale and aggregate the transformed data for ML/DL algorithms with higher accuracy.

A.2 Performance Evaluation Methods

Figure A.3 depicts the overview of data evaluation in Stacked Auto Encoder Algorithm (Training and Testing) in SDN.

- **Data Training and Testing** - This research mainly utilises the two different dataset portions, based on sampling/entropy calculation as discussed before for training and testing, each dataset is subdivided into training and testing sets followed by 80% of training and cross-validation and 20% of testing sets. Moreover, a combination of benign and normal datasets for training and testing is used, to make detection approach more realistic and effective.
- **Performance Evaluation** - This research utilizes feasible metrics such as *precision*, *recall* and *F1 score*, which are already discussed in Chapter 5 and 6. These metrics provide useful information about the goodness of the detection rate of the proposed model. These parameters are calculated with the help of a confusion matrix.

Figure A.3: Overview of data evaluation with (Training and Testing) in SDN.

A.3 Testbed Experiment

Figure A.4 depicts the overview of testbed with feasible network application elements in SDN.

Our experiment testbed is created with Intel (R) Xeon (R) X5560 CPU with 2.88 GHz processor and 16 GB RAM (DDR3 ECC-Registered Memory PC3-12800) running TensorFlow 1.4 on Ubuntu LTS 16.04-64 bit. VMware Player is used for creating both virtual machines such as VM1 with 192.168.232.x1 IP address and VM2 with 192.168.232.x2 IP address.

- **SDN-controller Ryu** - A Python component-based SDN development framework with well-defined API to create a flexible and innovative network application.
- **Switches** - OpenFlow based switches are created with Mininet-2.2.1 [177] Popular network emulator tool.
- **NIDS Module** - Python, a well-known scripting language is utilized with Snort IDS for the purpose of for routing flow and traffic management.

```

root@ubuntu:~# sudo mn --topo linear,6 --controller remote,ip=192.168.119.130
*** Creating network
*** Adding controller
*** Adding hosts:
h1 h2 h3 h4 h5 h6
*** Adding switches:
s1 s2 s3 s4 s5 s6
*** Adding links:
(h1, s1) (h2, s2) (h3, s3) (h4, s4) (h5, s5) (h6, s6) (s2, s1) (s3, s2) (s4, s3) (s5, s4) (s6, s5)
*** Configuring hosts
h1 h2 h3 h4 h5 h6
*** Starting controller
c0
*** Starting 6 switches
s1 s2 s3 s4 s5 s6 ...
*** Starting CLI:
mininet> pingall
*** Pings: testing ping reachability
h1 -> h2 h3 h4 h5 h6
h2 -> h1 h3 h4 h5 h6
h3 -> h1 h2 h4 h5 h6
h4 -> h1 h2 h3 h5 h6
h5 -> h1 h2 h3 h4 h6
h6 -> h1 h2 h3 h4 h5
*** Results: 0% dropped (30/30 received)
mininet>

_barnyard2ue@ubuntu:~$ sudo -s
[sudo] password for barnyard2ue:
root@ubuntu:~# sudo ovs-vsctl -- --id=sflow create sflow agent=ens33 target="\192.168.119.130:6343\" sampling=512 polling=20 -- -- set bridge s1 sflow
root@ubuntu:~# sudo ovs-vsctl -- --id=sflow create sflow agent=ens33 target="\192.168.119.130:6343\" sampling=512 polling=20 -- -- set bridge s2 sflow
root@ubuntu:~# sudo ovs-vsctl -- --id=sflow create sflow agent=ens33 target="\192.168.119.130:6343\" sampling=512 polling=20 -- -- set bridge s3 sflow
root@ubuntu:~# sudo ovs-vsctl -- --id=sflow create sflow agent=ens33 target="\192.168.119.130:6343\" sampling=512 polling=20 -- -- set bridge s4 sflow
root@ubuntu:~# sudo ovs-vsctl -- --id=sflow create sflow agent=ens33 target="\192.168.119.130:6343\" sampling=512 polling=20 -- -- set bridge s5 sflow
root@ubuntu:~# sudo ovs-vsctl -- --id=sflow create sflow agent=ens33 target="\192.168.119.130:6343\" sampling=512 polling=20 -- -- set bridge s6 sflow
root@ubuntu:~#
*** Starting CLI:
mininet> pingall
*** Ping: testing ping reachability
h1 -> h2 h3 h4 h5 h6
h2 -> h1 h3 h4 h5 h6
h3 -> h1 h2 h4 h5 h6
h4 -> h1 h2 h3 h5 h6
h5 -> h1 h2 h3 h4 h6
h6 -> h1 h2 h3 h4 h5
*** Results: 0% dropped (30/30 received)
mininet>

```

Figure A.4: Overview of testbed with feasible network application elements in SDN.

A.4 Snort Rules and Signatures for TCP, UDP and ICMP

Figure A.5 depicts the overview of TCP, UDP and ICMP signatures with specific field values, such as port numbers, content numbers, threshold types and values, priority values, track by_src, track by_dst and classtype. Each rules of TCP, UDP and ICMP is capable to record more than one malicious activity as shown in Figure A.6.

Our paper utilises the alert_csv output plugin in collaboration with SM1-mode and SM2-mode.

```

*local.rules (/etc/snort/rules) - gedit
Open
# Raja Ujjan Rules for Snort.conf
alert any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 any (flags: A; ack: 0; msg: "NMAP TCP ping");
alert tcp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 111 (rpc: 100000,*,3; msg:"RPC getport (TCP)");
alert udp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 111 (rpc: 100000,*,3; msg:"RPC getport (UDP)");
alert udp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 111 (rpc: 100003,*,*; msg:"RPC ttodb");
alert udp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 111 (rpc: 100232,10,*; msg:"RPC sadmin");
alert udp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 1524 (flags: S; resp: rst_all; msg: "Root shell backdoor attempt");
alert tcp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 1524 (flags: S; resp: rst_all; msg: "Root shell backdoor attempt");
alert udp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 31 (resp: icmp_port,icmp_host; msg: "Hacker's Paradise access attempt");
alert tcp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 1524 (flags: S; resp: rst_all; msg: "Root shell backdoor attempt");
alert udp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 31 (resp: icmp_port,icmp_host; msg: "Hacker's Paradise access attempt");
alert tcp any any -> 192.168.1.0/24 80 (content: "cgl-bin/phpf"; flags: PA; msg: "CGI-PHF probe");

alert tcp any any -> any any (msg:"Facebook accessing here"; sid:1000004);
alert icmp any any -> any any (msg:"Getting ping from 146 UMS PC"; sid:1000002);
alert udp any any -> any any (msg:"Nmap emulation DoS"; sid:1000003);
alert udp any any -> any any (msg:"SLR - LOIC DoS Tool UDP Mode"; sid:1000005; priority:1)

```

Figure A.5: Overview of TCP, UDP and ICMP signatures with specific field values.

Feature Extraction from TCP Flows.

1	No of packets in each incoming TCP-flows
2	No of packets in each outgoing TCP-flows
3	Change of packets in each incoming TCP-flows
4	Change of packets in each outgoing TCP-flows
5	No of distinctive Src-IP per incoming TCP-flows
6	Change of distinctive Src-IP per incoming TCP-flows
7	Total Bytes per incoming TCP-flows
8	Total Bytes per outgoing TCP-flows
9	Symmetric windows length per incoming TCP-flows
10	Distinctive windows length per incoming TCP-flows
11	No of symmetric incoming TCP-flows
12	No of asymmetric incoming TCP-flows
13	No of symmetric TTL values per incoming TCP-flows
14	No of asymmetric TTL values per incoming TCP-flows
15	No of asymmetric src-ports per incoming TCP-flows
16	Change of asymmetric src-ports per incoming TCP-flows
17	No of asymmetric Dst-ports per incoming TCP-flows
18	Change of asymmetric Dst-ports per incoming TCP-flows
18	No of $Dst - ports \leq 1024$ per incoming TCP-flows

Feature Extraction from UDP Flows.

1	No of packets in each incoming UDP-flows
2	No of packets in each outgoing UDP-flows
3	Change of symmetric packets each incoming UDPflows
4	Change of asymmetric packets each incoming UDP-flows
5	No different Src-IP in each incoming UDP-flows
6	Total Bytes per incoming UDP-flows
7	Total Bytes per outgoing UDP-flows
8	Total packets per incoming UDP-flows
9	Total packets per outgoing UDP-flows
10	No different Src-ports in each incoming UDP-flows
11	No different Dst-ports in each incoming UDP-flows
12	No different $Dstports \leq 1024$ per incoming UDP-flows
13	No different $Dst - ports < 1024$ per incoming UDP flows
14	No of asymmetric TTL values per incoming UDP flows
15	No of symmetric TTL values per incoming UDP-flows

Feature Extraction from ICMP Flows.

1	No of ICMP-flows in each incoming flows
2	No of ICMP-flows in each outgoing flows
3	No of symmetric incoming ICMP-flows
4	No of symmetric Src-IP per incoming ICMP-flows
5	Total Bytes per incoming ICMP-flows
6	Total Bytes per outgoing ICMP-flows
7	No of packets per incoming ICMP-flows
8	No of packets per outgoing ICMP-flows
9	Symmetric windows length per incoming TCP-flows
10	Different TTL values per incoming ICMP-flows

Figure A.6: Overview of Extracted TCP, UDP and ICMP signatures

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